

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D5.2 FINAL DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION, EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLANS DECEMBER 2025

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D5.2 FINAL DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION, EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLANS

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Abstract	D5.2 presents the communication and dissemination tasks, efforts and results, as well as the exploitation and sustainability plans. Linked to WP5.

Keywords	Dissemination, communication, growth hacking, stakeholder engagement, exploitation
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report details the comprehensive Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Sustainability outcomes of the Horizon Europe CATALISI project (Grant Agreement No.: 101094917).

The **D5.2 Final Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability Plans** consolidates the overall strategies, actions, and outcomes that have shaped the visibility, impact, and long-term value of the CATALISI project. This deliverable demonstrates how the consortium has ensured effective communication, broad dissemination, and robust exploitation pathways, while embedding sustainability principles into institutional transformation. In particular, the deliverable illustrates the following actions and outcomes:

- **Communication and Dissemination:** A strong, unified brand identity was established. The project's digital presence was highly effective, with the website recording over **12,200** visits and social media channels actively engaging target audiences.
- **Outreach:** The project actively participated in over **20** international events and created a wide array of open-access resources, including success stories and the replicable framework of acceleration services. The consortium created a strong network of Media contacts with a high impact on the dissemination of their work locally and internationally.
- **Network and Liaison with other projects and European Initiatives:** The joint efforts on policy briefs, events, and communication activities with the sister and other synergy projects directly contribute to the ERA's objective of empowering HEIs, ensuring the project's transformative model is available beyond the project finalisation.
- **Key Exploitable Results (KERs):** Three primary KERs were identified and refined with support from the Horizon Results Booster and a sustainability plan for long-term impact was drafted.

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ABBREVIATIONS

C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CA	Consortium Agreement
CoP	Community of Practice
D	Deliverable
DCO	Dissemination and Communication Objectives
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Agenda
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
IP	Intellectual Property
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KOM	Kick off meeting
LL	Living Labs
M	Month
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
MoU	Memoranda of Understanding
OS	Open Source
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1. INTRODUCTION

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the EU have been recognized for their global leadership in the fields of Research and Innovation (R&I). In order to maximize research impact and institutional transformation, HEIs need to strengthen their European University collaborations.

By bridging the gap between HEIs disparities in terms of R&I performance, HEIs can navigate and cooperate in the production and dissemination of high-quality knowledge to maximize the value of research and its impact within the European Union. This reflects a broader policy effort within the European Research Area (ERA) and the Higher Education Transformation Agenda to reinforce the role of universities as central actors in shaping Europe's scientific, economic and social future.

In this context, CATALISI contributes to the EC's objective of spreading and embedding institutional transformation across HEIs by supporting 7 universities in the design, implementation and consolidation of tailored strategies for change. The project helps HEIs to develop individual pathways for institutional transformation, combining short-term achievements with medium- and long-term structural reforms meant to persist beyond the project's lifetime.

To support this process, CATALISI has identified three domains of intervention (Research careers and Talent support, Research Modus Operandi and Sustainable Research and Education), each articulated into specific intervention areas where institutional change is deemed necessary. In parallel, the project has developed a set of seven Acceleration Services (Living Labs, Design Lab for transformational pathway, Counselling, Capacity Building and Outreach, Predictive Studies on Skills Anticipation, Community of Practice, and Marketplace) designed to facilitate, accompany and accelerate transformation. Through these services, HEIs are not only supported in implementing institutional change within their own organisations but are also progressively empowered to become service providers themselves, contributing expertise to their peers across Europe.

2. CATALISI COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION STRATEGY AND RESULTS

CATALISI Deliverable 5.2 serves as the final evolution of the project's visibility framework. It documents the transition from the initial planning phase (D5.1) to a fully realised, evidence-based strategy that has been updated to reflect real-world impact of the project outputs, and the maturation of the project's results. The most significant development is the shift from activity-based planning to result-based evidence:

- D5.1 described how implementers would use acceleration services. D5.2 presents the validated results from 7 European universities, proving that the model is scalable and flexible.
- D5.2 includes concrete evidence of institutional change rather than just a list of proposed tasks.
- The "Acceleration Services" in D5.1 were concepts; in D5.2, they have been refined into a Replicable Framework report ready for adoption by university alliances outside the consortium.
- In D5.1, the strategy was focused on individual outreach. By D5.2, this was updated to a Clustered Ecosystem approach with a complete communication and dissemination synergy approach together with the CATALISI Sister projects (aUPaEU and Accelerate

Future HEI) creating our own brand and a formalised partnership under a unified slogan: "Together for HEI Transformation." The updated strategy replaced isolated project updates with joint social media campaigns and shared visual templates, effectively tripling the project's reach and establishing a more authoritative voice within the European Research Area (ERA).

- Based on feedback from the 7 university implementers, the "Marketplace" was renamed the "Catalyst Hub". This change was a strategic update to better align the tool with academic values (collaboration) rather than commercial ones (buying/selling). The final strategy shows that the Hub became a dynamic repository, integrating the Learning Hub, Collaboration Hub, and a Funding opportunities
- D5.1 planned for traditional email newsletters (Mailchimp). D5.2 reveals a strategic shift to a LinkedIn-based newsletter ("Transformational Times"). This update allowed the project to move from a "one-way" email to a "two-way" professional dialogue, significantly increasing subscriber growth (reaching 277) and professional engagement with HEIs and policymakers.
- Instead of separate project results, they created a Joint Zenodo Community titled *"Acceleration Services in support of the institutional transformation of HEIs."* This ensures that all research outputs are FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) in one single location.
- In May 2024, the website was redesigned to move away from general project info toward Partner Success Stories. Each university (implementer) now has a dedicated dropdown section showcasing their specific "path for transformation."

To sum up, the transition from the First Strategy (D5.1) to the current deliverable (D5.2) showcases a shift from a "launch" mindset to a "legacy" mindset.

By using targeted tools and audience-specific channels, the project has effectively raised awareness and ensured wide dissemination and exploitation of its results. This environment played a key role in reinforcing CATALISI's impact among HEIs, policymakers, and the public, and will continue to support its legacy beyond the project's duration.

2.1. TARGET GROUPS

The first step toward developing a strong DC strategy is a deep understanding of the target audience and tailoring both dissemination and communication activities to the specific needs of each target group. Each target group has its own sphere of communication, and our aim was to address our target audience in a more meaningful way.

Understanding each target audience allows us to address them with effective content through the appropriate communication and dissemination channels, and with more relatable, non-generalised content. Target audience for CATALISI was mainly:

Policy Makers:

Policy and decision-makers at the European, national, and regional levels represent a very important target group for the CATALISI project. Their role is critical in fostering a regulatory and funding environment that supports the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda and the ongoing ERA Act consultations. CATALISI, in close synergy with its sister projects, facilitated a dynamic, iterative dialogue designed to bridge the gap between institutional reality and legislative frameworks:

- **Evidence-Based Policy Feeding:** Directing real-world insights from HEI Implementers and technical methodologies from Facilitators into the policy-making pipeline.
- **Validation and Co-creation:** Utilising high-level forums to present, validate, and debate policy recommendations. Key milestones included dedicated sessions at the CATALISI Final Conference, the ERA Webinar series, and exclusive closed-door workshops in Brussels.
- **Multi-Level Alignment:** Addressing Member State governments and ministries at the national and regional levels. Engaging these decision-makers is essential for harmonising national strategies with European frameworks, ensuring a unified approach to the HEI transformation agenda.

Higher Education Institutions and Alliances:

Higher Education Institutions formed a cornerstone of the CATALISI dissemination strategy. Our outreach included research institutions, university alliances, and academic bodies across Europe, ensuring the project's findings resonated deeply within the scholarly community.

Our engagement strategy focused on four key pillars:

- **"CATALISI Stories":** carefully curated narratives designed to showcase the tangible results and transformative journeys of those involved in our Implementation Pathways and Resources for inspiration and replicability.
- **Acceleration Services:** We actively promoted the specialised services provided by CATALISI Facilitators.
- **Knowledge Exchange:** We facilitated a continuous flow of information through our Community of Practice (CoP), webinars and events. These platforms allowed HEIs to access our core methodologies and "inspiring actions" directly from their peers.
- **Collaborative Ecosystems:** Engagement extended beyond individual universities to include our partner projects and wider research networks, such as the APRE R&I network. This ensured that the project's outcomes were embedded into research, education, and "third mission" (societal engagement) activities.

Civil Society

This target group represents a diverse ecosystem of actors positioned outside of formal government or academic structures. This group is essential for ensuring that institutional transformations in HEIs are aligned with societal needs and market realities:

- **Associations & Interest Groups:** Organizations representing specific societal causes, student bodies, or professional collectives with a vested interest in how HEIs evolve.
- **Industry Actors:** Private sector entities, SMEs, and corporate partners who seek to bridge the gap between academic innovation and market application.
- **Engaged Citizens:** Individuals with a proactive interest in institutional shifts, particularly those advocating for more open, inclusive, and sustainable university models.

Civil Society and Industry actors are integrated into the project through several key mechanisms:

- **Stakeholder Mapping in Living Labs:** They are core participants in the "quadruple helix" model (Academia, Government, Industry, and Civil Society), helping to co-create solutions within the CATALISI Living Labs.

- **Specialized Networks:** This group is reached and activated through established innovation networks, such as the F6S network (connecting startups and founders) and the Accelerate Future network.
- **Community of Practice (CoP):** They are active members of the CATALISI CoP, contributing to the shared learning environment and ensuring that the project's outputs remain grounded in practical, real-world application.

2.2. CATALISI VISUAL IDENTITY

In January 2023, an integrated and cohesive visual identity was created to serve as the foundation for all communication and dissemination products and tools. It was first presented in the KOM (26-27 January 2023) and further developed in the D5.1 *First Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability plans*.

The visual branding, including the project logo and style, ensured that external audiences can easily recognise CATALISI and contribute to raising awareness of the project by presenting a unified identity right from the project's start.

All dissemination and communication tools, such as the project website, X account, and LinkedIn page, as well as presentations, posters, roll-ups, documents, etc., adhere to the visual identity developed for the project. This chapter outlines the key elements of the project's visual identity.

Logo design

CATALISI logo was presented and chosen during the project Kick off meeting. The choice was made by the entire consortium based on the associations that project keywords invoke, along with the brandbook, and colour palet guidelines.

The shapes are deeply connected to the keywords that we associate with the project, namely: education, transformation, training, policy and acceleration. The CATALISI Logo is presented in its two versions

Figure 1: CATALISI logo with slogan

CATALISI fonts and colour palette

In addition to the logo, colour is the first visual clue which represents the project. Blue is the main colour used as a sign of stability and reliability. Moreover, blue is often used by businesses and initiatives that want to project an image of security as well as to inspire creativity and productivity. CATALISI colours are showcased below:

Figure 2: CATALISI colours palette

The primary font used throughout CATALISI materials is Raleway, chosen for its simplicity, readability, and broad accessibility across digital and print platforms.

Figure 3: CATALISI font

EU Funded acknowledgement

Across all outputs of the CATALISI project, and accompanying the logo, a text concerning the source of the project's funding is provided along with the European flag, as shown in Figure below:

Figure 4: CATALISI funding acknowledgment

In addition, any dissemination of results indicates the following:

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or (name of the granting authority). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them." In the case of CATALISI, the granting authority is the European Research Executive Agency (REA).

Furthermore, in May 2025, celebrating the **25th anniversary of the European Research Area** (ERA), the ERA Platform, which was launched in 2024 to provide information on the

implementation of the ERA Policy Agenda, gave CATALISI the opportunity to be part of its repository. This platform enables researchers, innovators, citizens, and policymakers to connect, collaborate, and access the latest information, data, and resources related to the European Research Area.

Therefore, the CATALISI project displayed the specific visuals and disclaimer along with a link to the ERA Platform on our project's website.

Figure 5: CATALISI ERA platform disclaimer

Website hyperlink to: <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/>

Disclaimer: "CATALISI | Catalysation of institutional transformations of Higher Education Institutions through the adoption of acceleration services supports the European Research Area aimed at creating a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology in the EU."

Figure 6: Screenshot of the ERA acknowledgement on the CATALISI website

Unified templates

CATALISI partners were provided with a Word Deliverable Template as well as PowerPoint template and simple meeting minutes template, Website headers, and social media posts templates (layouts for news, LinkedIn/X/Instagram posts). This is important to ensure the standardisation of the project documentation. Also, it contributed to coherent representation of visual identity throughout the project lifetime. The templates were made available through the internal repository system established by APRE as coordinator.

Figure 7: Deliverable template

Figure 8: Example of CATALISI Agenda, simple document and participants sheet templates

Figure 9: CATALISI Power Point template

Figure 10: CATALISI Social Media templates

Additionally, infographics were designed to illustrate core concepts and methodologies in alignment with the CATALISI visual identity such as consortium map differentiating the partners location and whether they are a Facilitator or an Implementer, CATALISI domains and Intervention areas concept, Transformational pathways, goals, acceleration services Replicable framework of acceleration services and an interactive map in the website where the visitor can hover over the countries and “play” with the visuals.

Figure 11: CATALISI Infographics

2.3. CATALISI COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION CHANNELS AND TOOLS

All CATALISI communication and dissemination channels were fully aligned, with content carefully unified in terms of key messages transmitted and visual identity. This consistency across platforms helped reinforce the project's visibility and recognition among its target audiences. The table below outlines how CATALISI C&D channels were used throughout the project, including the frequency of use and the target audiences reached.

Channel	Action	Frequency used	Target Audience
Website	<p>The CATALISI website https://catalisi.eu/ was launched in M3 (March 2023).</p> <p>During 2025, the website underwent a full update to make it more structured and increase the available content, with a special focus on the Partners section to showcase their success stories, the resources and the</p>	2 or 3 times a week with regular content in the news section, synergies section, the CATALYST Hub and the resources section	All project stakeholders: HEI, SMEs, Research Communities, synergy projects, and General public

	Catalyst Hub for sustainability purposes.		
Newsletter	A total of six Newsletters were published over the course of the project providing the subscribers with timely updates.	2 Newsletters per year, available in the CATALISI website: https://catalisi.eu/newsletters/	275 subscribers
Social Media	Social Media channels were actively managed during the project namely: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/catalisi-project • CATALISI CoP LinkedIn group: https://www.linkedin.com/groups/14298159/ • X: https://x.com/catalisi-project • YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@catalisiproject 	Regular posting ranging from a minimum of 2 to a maximum of 4 times per week with a call to action to find more information and updates on CATALISI website, link to events and other resources.	General public All project stakeholders R&I Communities outside the project
Zenodo	CATALISI open-access repository is available in Zenodo and in the Acceleration Services in support of the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions Zenodo community with our sister project	Update new resources every 4 months	Project stakeholders

Table 1: Communication and Dissemination channels

Website

CATALISI website (<https://catalisi.eu/>) was officially launched on M3. A significant redesign and improvement of the website was carried out in May 2024 transforming it into a more visually coherent and engaging, better structured, and comprehensive platform to reflect the full maturity of the project adding the results for each partner. This updated version introduced a refined layout with enhanced design elements and improved navigation.

Homepage

The Homepage (<https://catalisi.eu/>) now features key highlights of the project, including:

- More visually appealing and interactive description of the acceleration services, with an icon design for each and a learn more button to read the full report and work done by each partner.
- Stories of transformation: A quick access to CATALISI Success Stories Booklets and stories, featuring the transformational pathways for each implementer and the acceleration services for each facilitator
- CATALISI domains and intervention areas infographic for easy visualisation
- CATALISI Goals
- CATALYST Hub: An easy entry point to CATALISI space that helps HEI find funding opportunities, learn from peers and foster collaboration
- CATALISI Community of practice: a group of experts who share knowledge and expertise in transforming Higher Education Institutions. Members will offer advice, share tools, and participate in discussions to help improve university governance and promote European collaboration.
- Latest news

The purpose of the Home page is to present the CATALISI project's mission and structure in a concise and compelling way. Therefore, we have included banners to highlight key activities such as the final conference.

The image displays a collage of six screenshots from the CATALISI website homepage. The top-left screenshot shows the navigation menu (HOME, ABOUT US, COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE, THE CATALYST HUB, NEWS & EVENTS, RESOURCES, GET IN TOUCH) and the main mission statement: "CATALISI: CATALYSATION OF INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS THROUGH THE ADOPTION OF ACCELERATION SERVICES". The top-right screenshot details "ACCELERATION SERVICES" including Living Lab, Counselling, Transformational Pathway, and Predictive Study on Skills Anticipation. The middle-left screenshot features a banner for the "FINAL CONFERENCE: SHAPING THE FUTURE OF INSTITUTIONAL CHANGE IN HEIS" held on 11 November 2025. The middle-right screenshot shows a video player for the conference. The bottom-left screenshot highlights "STORIES OF TRANSFORMATION" from seven HEIs. The bottom-right screenshot is an infographic titled "CATALISI DOMAINS" listing research careers and talent support, research modus operandi, and sustainable research and education.

Figure 12:: CATALISI home page screenshots

About us

The About us (<https://catalisi.eu/about/>) page invites visitors to learn more about the project and provides access to dedicated pages related to the project, the methodology, the consortium behind CATALISI, the success stories and sister and synergy projects. (<https://catalisi.eu/synergy-projects/>)

We have created a dropdown menu for each partner to learn more about their path for transformation, and Acceleration services. (<https://catalisi.eu/consortium/>)

Each implementer has information divided by:

- About the university
- Their goals within the CATALISI scope
- Success Story webinar (if applicable)
- Their intervention areas
- Challenges
- Transformational pathways overcome those challenges
- Accomplishments
- Team

Each Facilitator has their information divided by:

- About the organisation
- About their acceleration service and relevant links
- The goals of the acceleration service within CATALISI framework
- Methodology
- Accomplishments
- Team

CATALISI SYNERGY PROJECTS

Synergy projects that share some of the objectives and scope with the CATALISI project

- + GILL project
- + DoTalent4EU
- + PATTERN
- + ERA TALENT
- + REINFORCING
- + Netherlands Research Integrity Network (NRIN)
- + Verity
- + Skills4EOSC
- + INSPIRING ERA

CONSORTIUM

Agency for the Promotion of European Research

← RETURN

APRE is a non-profit association established in 1989 by the Italian Ministry of Education and various public and private entities to address the need for information on EU research programs.

With a network of over 150 members, including research centers, universities, and trade associations, APRE promotes the exchange of best practices and advocates for its members. It hosts HORIZON EUROPE National Contact Points and serves as the EURAXESS Bridgehead Organisation for Italy.

TESTIMONIAL

Miriam van Loon
Assistant Professor at Amsterdam UMC

"Capacity building and Outreach has helped UVMC to further define the action plan at university level and increase understanding of stimulating responsible conduct of research in an international context. Participants came from different universities across Europe so we were able to gather opinions and ideas from many different perspectives."

CATALISI SUCCESS STORY

Universitat Jaume I (UJI) showcased its successful transformation in research ethics and Open Science during a recent CATALISI project webinar featuring Ramón A. Feenstra and Laura Bernal Sánchez.

ACCOMPLISHMENTS

The Universitat Jaume I (UJI) has made significant institutional changes in their research, innovation, and open-access areas, underscoring its commitment to advancing scientific knowledge and ethical standards.

UJI has been driving systemic changes that align with national and European frameworks, such as the National Open Science Strategy (ENCS) and CoARA initiatives.

Highlights of these accomplishments include the launch of its Open Science Strategy, implementation of innovative cross-disciplinary training programs for doctoral students, and multiple conferences on research ethics and scientific evaluation practices.

CONSORTIUM

European Network of Living Labs (EnoLL)

← RETURN

The European Network of Living Labs (EnoLL) is a non-profit association of benchmarked Living Labs aimed at promoting open innovation ecosystems through co-creation and collaboration.

Its mission is to provide value by enhancing members' capacities and knowledge, helping them develop innovative products and services. EnoLL currently has 324 members from 35 countries across five continents.

LIVING LABS

Leverage a co-creation methodology for university innovation development

A participatory and collaborative framework that emphasizes co-creation, stakeholder engagement, and real-world settings for innovation.

Living Labs are practical, real-world environments where new ideas and strategies are tested and refined. Living Labs includes stakeholders such as university staff and students and external partners.

Living Labs Goals

1. Identification of the key players across the entire value chain, clarifying their roles and influence, and categorising them using a 4-Helix model.
2. To analyse the local context, including any barriers and framework conditions that might affect institutional change.
3. Understand the values, concerns, needs, and expectations of the identified stakeholders through interviews, surveys, and workshops.
4. Elaboration of targeted and effective action plans within selected intervention areas based on the findings.
5. To oversee and put into action the institutional changes within the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).
6. To assess the progress of each HEI against the identified KPIs, using indicators aligned with

Catalyst Hub Goals

1. To provide access to funding opportunities, follow-up financing, and public procurement opportunities to HEIs.
2. To foster collaborations or alliance processes between Higher Education Institutions based on their complementary competences.
3. To enable Higher Education Institutions collaborate and share knowledge and experiences.
4. To provide opportunities for researchers to commercialise their research results to SMEs.
5. To expand the reach of HEIs through collaboration with experts, business and other HEIs alliances.
6. To provide a hub for knowledge transfer through trainings and resources.

Violeta Naydenova
Project Manager

Sandra Grano de Oro Tuñón
Communication Manager

Figure 13: CATALISI About us page: Methodology, sister and synergy projects, Consortium and success stories from the Implementers and Facilitators.

Community of practice

The **Community of Practice (CoP)** section (available at <https://catalisi.eu/catalisi-community-of-practice/>) serves as a central hub for professional engagement and peer-to-peer learning. The CoP is a multidisciplinary ecosystem composed of experts and practitioners from various sectors, including academia, industry, public administration, and civil society, who share a unified interest in the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions.

By bringing together individuals with diverse and valuable expertise, the CoP is designed to build a robust body of practical knowledge and provide actionable insights into the challenges and pathways of institutional reform. The CoP section is divided in 3:

1. Learn More (<https://catalisi.eu/catalisi-community-of-practice/>): this page serves as an invitation and information hub for their Community of Practice (CoP):

- What is the CATALISI CoP?

The Community of Practice is a group of diverse professionals (from education, ICT, policy-making, and civil society) who collaborate to transform the governance of Higher Education Institutions, particularly in the fields of Research & Innovation. It functions as a "safe learning environment" where members share expertise and "learn by doing."

- Benefits of Joining
 - Knowledge Access: Benefit from innovative practices, workshops, and mutual learning events.
 - Networking: Connect with a wide community of stakeholders across Europe.
 - Influence: Contribute strategic guidance and new ideas to shape the project's impact on HEI governance.
- Eligibility and Requirements
 - Who: Professionals from EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon Europe.
 - Expertise Needed: Interest/experience in Open Science, digitalization, gender and inclusiveness, commercialization of research, and public engagement.
 - Commitment: Participation is voluntary (unpaid) and requires involvement at least twice a year.
- Application Process
- Site Navigation and Meta-Data

2. Connect with CoP members open to collaboration: A section to enhance networking with our members. It allows them to showcase their specific expertise, intervention areas, and professional backgrounds, facilitating easier matchmaking and collaboration between peers across the European Research Area.

3. Join us: We maintain a constantly active Open Call for new members, ensuring the community remains dynamic and continues to grow. This call has been recently updated to integrate with the new profile system, allowing incoming experts to be featured on the website immediately upon joining.

Whether one is looking to share their own experiences or learn from the transformational journeys of others, the CoP provides the tools and the network to support systemic change in Higher Education.

CATALYST Hub

The CATALYST Hub¹ previously called the *Marketplace* (<https://catalisi.eu/catalisi-marketplace/>) was renamed following feedback from our implementers. Since one of our main target groups consists of HEIs—which generally cannot or do not wish to engage in activities implying monetary benefits—the term Marketplace could discourage them from accessing the hub. The updated name better reflects its purpose and is more inclusive for all stakeholders.

This section is divided by 3 subsections:

Figure 14: Catalyst Hub screenshot in the CATALISI website

Learning Hub

Learning Hub (<https://catalisi.eu/learning-hub/>): an online platform designed to facilitate knowledge exchange, supporting HEIs through their transformation processes. It acts as a central space for learning, sharing inspiring examples, and driving positive change in research and innovation aspects. The Learning Hub hosts a comprehensive array of materials, including all Success Stories webinars, 13 webinars dedicated to each implementation area with a link to the materials produced and presented (e.g. PPTs), and two Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops with Community of Practice members. Additionally, it provides other webinars from our partners in their respective languages, such as an Open Science workshop offered by UJI. Functioning as a versatile and easily navigable central space, the Learning Hub is instrumental in promoting continuous learning, facilitating the critical sharing of inspiring examples and best practices, and ultimately accelerating positive, systemic change. Designed as a sustainable digital repository, the platform offers a wealth of training and educational resources that extend beyond the project's immediate partnership and lifecycle. This open-access library provides users with the essential tools to spearhead significant institutional improvements and ensures a lasting legacy of knowledge sharing. Key content housed within the Learning Hub includes:

- **Success Stories Webinars:** A comprehensive and highly valuable collection of webinars was produced, each dedicated to showcasing successful implementation stories and detailed case studies sourced from various Higher Education Institutions.

¹ Based on feedback from the 7 university implementers, the "Marketplace" was renamed the "Catalyst Hub". This change was a strategic update to better align the tool with academic values (collaboration) rather than commercial ones (buying/selling). The final strategy shows that the Hub became a dynamic repository, integrating the Learning Hub, Collaboration Hub, and a Funding opportunities

The primary objective of these webinars was to move beyond theoretical concepts and offer practical, real-world insights into effective institutional transformation within the sector.

- **Implementation Area Webinars:** 13 webinars, each focused on a specific critical area of implementation such as Mainstream of Open Science, Digitalisation of research, Academic freedom, Gender inclusivity, CoARA, Lifelong learning... providing in-depth guidance and expert perspectives. Every webinar is accompanied by direct links to supporting materials, including PowerPoints presentations used, ensuring users can delve deeper into the subject matter.
- **Community of Practice (CoP) Workshop & Resources:** Recording, documentation and materials from two dedicated workshops with the CATALISI CoP members, which fostered peer-to-peer learning, collaborative problem-solving, and the development of shared knowledge among practitioners in the topics of: *Inspirational examples on institutional transformation of HEIs in R&I* and *Preparing for the Future: Key Skills for Research Careers*
- **Partner-Contributed Resources:** Expanding its value through collaboration, the Hub integrates other pertinent information and specialized webinars contributed by project partners. These resources are often available in their respective languages to maximize accessibility and relevance for a broader European audience. A notable example is the high-value Open Science workshop made available by one of our key partners, the Universitat Jaume I.

To ensure a high level of attendance and maximise reach, a targeted and multi-phased communication strategy was implemented for each webinar:

- **Pre-webinar Social Media campaigns:**
 - A social media campaign was developed and executed to promote each upcoming session, highlighting key speakers, core topics, and the practical value attendees would receive. This campaign aimed to generate buzz and significantly increase registration and live attendance.
 - The communication material was also sent to our sister and all synergy projects, including the flyer, objectives of the webinar, information on the topic and the registration link.
- **Post-Webinar dissemination:** Following the live event, a rigorous process ensured the content's continued life and accessibility:
 - The raw webinar video was professionally edited and published.
 - A blog article highlighting the key topics and the PDF materials shared
 - A second, dedicated social media campaign was launched to promote the new blog article. This campaign specifically directed audiences to the published resources, including the link to the edited webinar video and access to the PDF presentation materials and key highlights shared by the presenters during the session.

CATALISI SUCCESS STORIES

A series of reports on the lessons learned from our Implementers partners

Evaluating HE Institutional Change Through a Participatory Approach

Interested in innovative approaches to evaluation and impact assessment in Higher Education? Watch to learn:

- Why the Theory of Change is such a powerful approach for evaluation and impact assessment.
- Key lessons learned about the use of Key Performance Indicators from the CATALISI project.
- The significant difference a participatory approach to evaluation and impact assessment can make to institutions.

Shaping the future of quality & sustainable education

During the European Sustainable Development Week, CATALISI had the opportunity to explore how EU-funded projects are driving progress towards SDG 4: Quality Education through innovation, collaboration, and inclusion. The webinar brought together five inspiring Horizon Europe and Erasmus+ initiatives – GREENVERITY, CATALISI project, DS4Skills – Data Space for Skills, XR4ED and YouLead.

Transformational pathway towards enhancing participation in research

Eglė from Kaunas University of Technology (KTU) shared how the university has been actively engaging with citizens to become a truly interdisciplinary and internationally competitive institution, one that drives transformation, knowledge, and innovation.

Transforming Research Ethics: Open Science and Reform of Ethical Governance

Universitat Jaume I (UJI) showcased its successful transformation in research ethics and Open Science during a recent CATALISI project webinar featuring Ramon A. Feenstra and Laura Bernal Sánchez.

CATALISI WEBINARS

A series of online seminars designed to provide Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with insights and strategies for institutional transformation. These webinars feature expert speakers who discuss best practices, research findings, and actionable strategies.

The goal is to equip institutions with the knowledge and tools necessary to drive sustainable innovation.

Recognition of Qualifications in Research Careers: Skills in Research and Beyond

[Agenda](#)
[Feliziani presentation](#)
[EY Webinar presentation](#)

Reinforcing the role of universities in local innovation system

[Agenda](#)
[CATALISI Speech UniverC](#)

Digitalization of Higher Education Institutions

[Agenda](#)

Accurately Addressing Live Long Learning

[PROFESS. DR. FLORIM GALLOPENI – Beyond the classroom](#)
[PROFESS. DR. BUJAR GALLOPENI – Bottlenecks for](#)

The CATALISI Community of Practices (CoP) is a collaborative network composed of experts from various sectors who share common interests and valuable expertise in institutional transformation within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). CATALISI CoP offers advice and guidance for transforming HEI governance. [More information and link to join here](#)

INSPIRATIONAL EXAMPLES ON INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION OF HEI IN R&I

[Inspirational examples on institutional transformation of HEIs in R&I agenda](#)

The CoP workshop has been actively engaging in gathering a wide pool of experts and professionals in the field of institutional transformation of HEI around the priorities of the [European Research Agenda](#). Illustrating the profound interest in the topic as well as the urgent need to continue creating mutual learning spaces.

The presentations from our speakers [can be found in this link](#).

PREPARING FOR THE FUTURE: KEY SKILLS FOR RESEARCH CAREERS

[Preparing for the future key skills for research careers agenda](#)

Organized by APRE with the support of EY, the workshop achieved significant results in terms of engagement and knowledge-sharing. In fact, the online event brought together members of the CATALISI [Community of Practice](#) together with more than 80 participants from over 50 organizations around Europe.

The presentations from our speakers [can be found in this link](#).

V Research Ethics Conference: Open Science and the Future of the University. 25 September 2024: "CoARA and the Reform of Research Evaluation: What Can We Do from the University?"

Inauguration: Jesús Lancis, Vice-Rector for Research at Universitat Jaume I

Speaker: Pastora Martínez Samper (Universitat Oberta de Catalunya)

Session Moderator: Ramón A. Feenstra

More information: <https://tinyurl.com/zxmrdk3>
[Link to presentation](#)

The programme features several important talks, including the **opening session** by Pastora Martínez Samper (Universitat Oberta de Catalunya) on "CoARA and the reform of research evaluation. What can we do from the university?". A notable highlight will be the talk by Joan Subirats (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona) titled "The dilemmas of research in a transforming world. University and society in an era of change". The conference will conclude on **27 September** with a session by Enrique Orduña (Universitat Politècnica de València) on "Ethics and transparency in alternative scientific evaluation metrics"

Figure 15: CATALISI Learning Hub platform

Funding opportunities

Funding opportunities (<https://catalisi.eu/funding-opportunities/>): This section is designed for Higher Education Institutions, researchers, and administrative staff. Its primary objective is to streamline the identification of grants by consolidating fragmented data into a single, actionable resource.

The value of this tool is to provide comprehensive access to funding data, including eligibility criteria, submission deadlines, and thematic alignment. By centralising these details, the platform empowers users to:

- Identify high-relevance calls for HEIs-led projects.
- Minimise administrative burden and "search fatigue."
- Accelerate the transition toward sustainable operational and educational models across Europe.

While the European Commission's Funding & Tenders Portal serves as the official repository for all EU programmes, it can be notoriously difficult to navigate due to its sheer volume of generic data.

Unlike the official portal, the CATALISI API acts as a curated filter. It specifically extracts and organises "HEI-relevant" opportunities, removing the noise of unrelated calls. CATALISI API cross-references data from 18 different programmes simultaneously including HORIZON,

DIGITAL, ERASMUS+, CREA, and IMREG to deliver a targeted, thematic feed tailored specifically to the needs of the HEI community.

Figure 16: CATALISI Funding Opportunities

Collaboration

The Collaboration (<https://catalisi.eu/collaboration/>)

To ensure the project delivered maximum value, we conducted a series of iterative brainstorming sessions and co-creation workshops with CATALISI partners. These collaborative sessions allowed us to align our objectives directly with the needs of our partners and stakeholders, ensuring the final outcome was both high-impact and practically applicable. After these sessions, we divided the collaboration section into four subsections:

- *Find Services to Transform Your HEI:* Access acceleration services provided by CATALISI partners.
- *Connect with the CATALISI Community of Practice:* Join our Community of Practice and benefit from shared acceleration services and peer exchange.
- *Explore Other HEI Transformation Initiatives:* Discover complementary initiatives and expand your network of alliances.
- *Commercialization of Research Results:* Explore research outcomes from our universities that are available for collaboration with industry.

Figure 17: Result scheme of the Collaboration section in the Catalyst Hub after brainstorming sessions and the final design of the collaboration subsections

Collaboration subsection: Find Services to Transform Your HEI

This section serves as a digital repository and matchmaking tool designed to facilitate institutional transformation. It provides an interface to access a curated suite of **Acceleration Services**, specialist interventions developed by CATALISI partners.

To ensure the effective alignment of services with institutional needs, the marketplace employs dual taxonomy for filtering and matching:

- Services offered by our partners, including counselling, evaluation, mentoring, bespoke training, impact assessment, and product development.
- Thematic Intervention Areas: including Open Science, research assessment reform, digitalisation, gender equality, talent mobility, and the reinforcement of local innovation ecosystems.

This filtering ensures effective matchmaking of the services our visitors need on the scope they are looking for.

The technical architecture of the marketplace was collected by F6S through a survey to partners to capture the technical specifications of each service. This information was deployed into the website: <https://catalisi.eu/acceleration-services-provided-by-catalisi-partners/>

The current portfolio of services within the marketplace includes Living Lab methodologies for practical research application, Transformational Pathways for long-term strategic planning, and Capacity Building toolkits designed to enhance international competitiveness. By acting as a central node for expertise.

Figure 18: survey sent to partners to collect information and ownership in the Marketplace and F6S platform

Find Services to Transform your HEI

The Marketplace showcases **acceleration services** designed and provided by the CATALISI partners, acting as a facilitators of institutional transformation.

These services are intended for **Higher Education Institutions and Alliances**, as well as **Researchers and Research Organizations**, supporting their efforts to implement strategic change and foster innovation.

Whether you're seeking guidance on governance, digital transition, stakeholder engagement, or sustainability, in the marketplace tool below you can browse a **curated list of acceleration services** tailored to your specific domains of interest, and find the right tools and expertise for your transformation journey.

Categories type: Acceleration Ser.: Intervention area: Partners: Search:

Services	Acceleration service type	Category type	Intervention area (topic)	Partner	More info
Transformations Pathways	Transformational Pathway	Assessment, Monitoring, Training	Digitalisation of higher education. Enhancement of HEI public engagement and outreach to society to solve social challenges. Lifelong learning. Open science / Citizen science. Reinforcement of the role of universities in the local innovation ecosystems. Sustainability in education & funding schemes. Sustainability in research & academia/business alliances. Talent circulation and/or mobility.	EY	Read more
Multi-level knowledge sharing and strengthening ICT/business and academic institutional reforms	Capacity Building and Outreach	Mentoring, Open Product / service development	All: Digitalisation of higher education. Enhancement of HEI public engagement and outreach to society to solve social challenges. Gender equality & inclusiveness. Lifelong learning. Open science / Citizen science. Recognition of qualifications & research careers. Reinforcement of the role of universities in the local innovation ecosystems. Sustainability in education & funding schemes. Sustainability in research & academia/business alliances. Talent circulation and/or mobility.	APRE	Read more
Living Labs LOGISTICS SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT SCM	Living Lab (LL)	Assessment, Evaluation, Expertise, Open Product / service development, Research	Research assessment. Sustainability in research & academia/business alliances	University of Odense	Read more
Living Labs BIOACTIVE COSMETICS SCREENING ON AGING/BIOTECH AND/OR IT LIFECYCLE MODELS LOGS/MAL KENITE	Living Lab (LL)	Assessment, Evaluation, Expertise, Open Product / service development, Research	Research assessment. Sustainability in research & academia/business alliances	University of Odense	Read more
Living Labs AIR TRANSPORT, SPORTS, INSURANCE, MOBILITY		Assessment, Evaluation, Expertise	Research assessment	University of Odense	

Living Labs AIR TRANSPORT, SPORTS, INSURANCE, MOBILITY	Living Lab (LL)	Assessment, Evaluation, Expertise, Open Product / service development, Research	Research assessment. Sustainability in research & academia/business alliances	University of Odense	Read more
Living Lab Methodology for Institutional Transformation: A Practical Guide to Becoming a Living Lab	Training		All: Digitalisation of higher education. Enhancement of HEI public engagement and outreach to society to solve social challenges. Gender equality & inclusiveness. Lifelong learning. Open science / Citizen science. Recognition of qualifications & research careers. Reinforcement of the role of universities in the local innovation ecosystems. Sustainability in education & funding schemes. Sustainability in research & academia/business alliances. Talent circulation and/or mobility.	ENoLL	Read more
Living Lab Hub	Living Lab (LL)	Expertise, Other	Enhancement of HEI public engagement and outreach to society to solve social challenges. Lifelong learning. Open science / Citizen science. Reinforcement of the role of universities in the local innovation ecosystems. Sharing of research infrastructures and capacities. Sustainability in education & funding schemes. Sustainability in research & academia/business alliances	UCC	Read more

[Back to Services](#)

Partner

ENoLL

Category (type)

Training

Contact details

Mariem Chebraou
Senior Project Manager
European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)

[Get in touch](#)

Living Lab Methodology for Institutional Transformation: A Practical Guide to Becoming a Living Lab

Intervention area (topic)

All

Experience/expertise

ENoLL: European Network of Living Labs is the global reference point for Living Lab methodologies, with over 35 years of experience supporting institutions, cities, and organizations in adopting participatory innovation approaches. Within the CATALISI project, ENoLL has co-developed and piloted the Living Lab Methodology for Institutional Transformation with European HEIs, ensuring its practical relevance and adaptability. Our expertise covers capacity building, stakeholder engagement, evaluation of Living Labs, and the design of frameworks and tools that foster systemic change.

Living Lab Methodology for Institutional Transformation: A Practical Guide to Becoming a Living Lab

The service provides a practical methodology to support Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in becoming Living Labs and embedding participatory, user-driven innovation into their transformation strategies. It offers: This service empowers institutions to move beyond traditional innovation models by integrating real-life experimentation, continuous feedback and inclusive stakeholder engagement into their organizational practices.

Figure 19: Listing of Acceleration services and cooperation opportunities with Facilitators and Implementers in the CATALISI website and F6S platform

Collaboration subsection: Connect with the CATALISI Community of Practice

The **Community of practice section** described above, focus on the following objectives:

- To aggregate diverse expertise from members in different sectors including academia, ICT, policy-making, and civil society to feed into HEIs activities.
- To connect with members that provide guidance on the evolution of HEI governance, ensuring that CATALISI outcomes are grounded in real-world applicability.
- To co-create tools and methodologies that strengthen European university alliances and foster the adoption of shared European values.

To ensure a high-impact and diverse membership, a formal recruitment process was established via a **Membership Application Survey** created by APRE. This instrument serves as both a gateway for participation and a data-collection tool for community mapping. Applicants are categorised according to:

- Stakeholder Profile: Identifying representatives from HEIs, business, government, funding organisations, and civil society.
- Thematic Specialisation: Mapping expertise across 13 core domains, including Open Science, Gender Equality and Inclusiveness, Research Assessment Reform, and Talent Mobility.
- Contribution Mode: Defining how members engage, ranging from sharing best practices and providing strategic advice to participating in joint workshops and peer-to-peer mentorship.

Finally, the CoP members that agreed to be included in the **CATALISI Member Directory** can participate in direct peer-to-peer collaboration. The directory allows users to filter the

community by Area of Expertise and Interest, enabling targeted matchmaking for research collaboration, publication co-authorship, and the sharing of case studies.

By featuring member profiles and professional biographies, the platform increases the visibility of individual experts' expertise for collaboration while reinforcing the collective impact on the European Research Area (ERA).

Figure 20: CATALISI Community of Practice collaboration sections: Description, Member Application Survey, Member directory with filtering features, and Member profile example

Collaboration subsection: Other HEIs Transformation Initiatives

This section is a strategic mapping of the project's external ecosystem. It highlights how CATALISI avoids siloed operations by fostering institutional synergies and cross-project collaboration.

The "Sister Projects" Framework: CATALISI operates in close alignment with two primary "Sister Projects" funded under the same Horizon Europe call (*HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-51*). The consortium maintains an active and formal collaboration with:

- [Accelerate Future HEI](#): Focuses on developing roadmaps for change through expert coaching and training within entrepreneurial networks.
- [aUPaEU](#) (A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities): Utilises an "Acceleration Agora" to provide digital technologies and coaching for long-term R&I transformations in HEIs.

To reinforce this partnership, a Common Branding Guideline (WIDERA branding) has been adopted and made available for download, ensuring a harmonised visual identity for shared outputs and policy recommendations. More information can be found in the section 2.5 Networking and liaison with other initiatives

Synergy Projects: In addition to the core sister projects, the Catalyst Hub serves as a gateway to a broader ecosystem of transformation initiatives. These Synergy Projects share overlapping objectives in specific thematic domains, allowing for the cross-fertilisation of ideas:

Key Synergy Partners	Collaborative Focus
GILL	Reducing gender barriers in innovation through Living Lab methodologies.
DocTalent4EU, ERA TALENT	Enhancing doctoral training, skills recognition, and researcher mobility hubs.
PATTERN, Skills4EOSC	Creating pan-European training ecosystems for Open RRI and FAIR data management.
VERITY, Netherlands Research Integrity Network (NRIN) REINFORCING	Strengthening research integrity, stakeholder engagement, and societal trust in science.
INSPIRING ERA	Accelerating the adoption of ERA Policy Agenda outcomes across Member States.

Table 2: Synergy partners

Beyond informal networking, CATALISI has established a structured collaboration framework through the signing of Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with its sister projects and key synergy partners. These agreements formalise a commitment to:

- Joint Dissemination & Outreach: Synchronised communication campaigns to maximise the visibility of ERA advancements.
- Shared Event Participation: Co-organising thematic workshops, mutual learning events, and policy webinars.
- Sustainability and Legacy: Developing joint exit strategies to ensure that the tools, such as the Catalyst Hub, remain interoperable with the platforms of our partners.

Collaboration subsection: Commercialisation of Research Results

This section describes the methodology for transitioning project outputs into a market-ready environment. It focuses on the commercialisation of research and the long-term sustainability of acceleration services into the F6S platform, ensuring that the directory remains accessible to the research community beyond the formal conclusion of the project's web lifecycle: <https://www.f6s.com/catalisi/about>

A core component of the CATALISI exploitation strategy is the transition of institutional expertise from a project-based repository to a global professional ecosystem. To achieve this, the project leverages the F6S platform, a leading global network for start-ups and research innovation. By integrating partner profiles into F6S, CATALISI ensures:

- Post-Project Sustainability: Services remain discoverable and accessible after the formal conclusion of the grant period.
- Commercial Viability: Research outputs are positioned within a marketplace context, facilitating "matchmaking" between HEI service providers and external industrial or academic "customers."

To populate the F6S portal, a structured data-collection survey was shared among the partners, requiring auditing their internal capacities and define their offerings, collaboration opportunities and Acceleration Services as well as a contact person. Each submission required an evidence-based background of the institution's previous experience in service provision to ensure high-quality delivery. Every service is tagged against pre-defined Intervention Areas (e.g., Digitalisation, Open Science, Talent Circulation) to ensure efficient searchability within the F6S and Catalyst Hub ecosystems.

This commercialisation pathway directly supports the ERA's objective of creating a borderless market for research and innovation. The reason behind using F6S platform was:

- It bridges the gap between high-level institutional reform and the practical, market-based application of research expertise.
- For GDPR consideration (website cannot collect data from external stakeholders)
- For taking advantage of existing online based community of nearly 2 million entities registered at F6S platform (incl. SMEs)
- For using the existing and up-to-date database of published: funding, collaboration and events opportunities
- For sustainability and exploitation reasons – F6S platform will remain and be sustained by the company at own expenses more than 5 years after the end of the project
- Responsibility from F6S for managing and maintaining the platform beyond the project lifespan

Figure 21: Partners services listed in F6S platform

News

A separate **News** page was created to fit in all latest announcements and events related to the project.

Figure 22: News section in the web

Resources

CATALISI Resources section serves as the definitive knowledge hub for the CATALISI project, offering a structured repository of all intellectual outputs. This section provides methodological frameworks employed throughout the project lifecycle, alongside an exhaustive analysis of the empirical results achieved. Furthermore, it hosts a specialized suite of transferability toolkits, specifically curated to facilitate the replication of CATALISI interventions by external stakeholders and institutional partners: Key components available within this section include:

- **Branding and Identity:** Branding guidelines and a complete logo pack are provided to ensure consistent visual representation of the CATALISI project across all internal and external communication channels.
- **Media and Communication:** A detailed Media kit is available, designed to facilitate communication and outreach efforts. This kit encompasses the official project presentation, factsheets for quick reference, informative posters for visual dissemination, and an archive of the four official Press Releases issued throughout the project's lifecycle.
- **Newsletter Archive:** Users can access the complete Newsletters archive, offering a chronological overview of project progress, milestones, and events.
- **Deliverables and Reports:** The repository is categorized into three strategic pillars:
 - a. **Public Deliverables:** This section foundational aspects such as the Acting Living Labs (LLs), Mutual Learning Plans, and Coaching Methodologies. These documents provide the theoretical and operational backbone of the CATALISI project.
 - b. **Reports and Success Stories:** Moving beyond administrative reporting, this area provides real-world insights from our partner's experiences through the Acceleration Services booklet, and Implementers' Success Stories, it also provides a Replicable Framework of acceleration services report with easy steps for HEIs replicability. These resources are designed specifically for external stakeholders seeking to mirror the project's success in their own institutional contexts.
 - c. **Multimedia Assets:** A comprehensive Final Conference presentation to adopt, adapt, and scale the CATALISI methodologies.

This centralized structure underscores the project's commitment to transparency, knowledge dissemination, and sustained communication, making the Resources section the definitive go-to source for all things CATALISI. Moreover, it highlights the methodology used, the results achieved and provides all necessary materials to support transparency and enable easy replication.

Figure 23: Resources section on the website

Get in touch

Finally, visitors can contact us through our **“Get in Touch”** section.

Website metrics

The website meets the **accessibility** rules and requirements, allowing users to adjust settings to accommodate a wide range of needs and provide optimum experience on different devices and settings. The CATALISI domain will be active for 5 more years after the project lifespan. To ensure compliance with GDPR and improve data transparency, CATALISI transitioned its analytics tracking from Google Analytics to Matomo, an open-source and fully privacy-compliant analytics tool. Matomo allows detailed tracking of user behaviour, including page views, downloads, countries of origin, return visits, device types, and goal completions, all while maintaining data sovereignty.

Figure 24: Google Analytics from September 2023-May 2024

Figure 25: Matomo Analytics from May 2024 - November 2025

From September 2023 to 26 May 2025, using Google Analytics, the website recorded 2.249 visits, with an average visit duration of 3 minutes and 29 seconds, being Italy (511), United States (228) United Kingdom (213), and Spain (160) the most active users.

After switching to Matomo Analytics in May 2024, the data collected shows: from May 2024 to November 2025, the site had 9.917 visits and 28.724 page views, an average visit duration of 2 minutes and 45 seconds being United States (19.8% 1.959), Italy (13% 1.286) Spain (11.3% 1.116), and Ireland (6.8% 678) the most active users.

Overall, the website served as a vital hub for the project engagement, and visibility, centralising all relevant resources and reflecting the values of transparency, inclusion, and accessibility that are at the centre of CATALISI. It is expected to continue serving as a lasting reference for CATALISI's results and methodology, sustaining the project's impact well beyond its formal conclusion.

Newsletter

A dedicated CATALISI newsletter was established as a key communication and dissemination tool to keep stakeholders informed about the project's progress, achievements, and upcoming activities. Initially planned on a biannually basis, the newsletter was designed to reach an opt-in subscriber base that included stakeholders in the scientific community, HEIs, and policymakers. The original production and distribution of the newsletter was in Mailchimp Ensuring GDPR compliance and data integrity.

The first two newsletters were sent to 65 and 96 subscribers respectively. Afterwards we sent an email to all subscribers announcing that the CATALISI newsletter was moving to LinkedIn with a new name called Transformational Times (<https://www.linkedin.com/newsletters/catalisi-transformation-times-7226517172129263617/>) a name that inspire transformation for HEIs.

This decision was driven by our continuous effort to enhance reach and engagement. LinkedIn serves as a natural meeting point for professionals, fostering connections, idea sharing, and keeping up with industry trends. Given the strong presence of HEIs and policymakers already on the platform, integrating the newsletter there allowed us to tap into a wider community, leading to increased impact and subscriber growth. We facilitated the transition by sharing a video guide that includes a direct subscription link.

We effectively increased the subscriber base to **277** subscribers. The newsletter served as a newsroom and project update channel, providing stakeholders with timely updates on activities, key results, upcoming events, and policy developments. To ensure coherence and reader engagement, a standardised structure was introduced for all issues, with clearly defined sections:

- **Introduction:** Editorial message from the consortium. A brief, personal welcoming message from the Project Coordinator or the consortium. It included a key highlight of the project's recent progress or strategic direction, effectively positioning the context for the detailed articles that follow.
- **Breaking News:** The latest most important update to ensure subscribers are immediately aware of the most significant and time-sensitive achievement.
- **Inside the CATALISI consortium:** Events, workshops, deliverables, and internal milestones that provide a comprehensive overview of the internal and collaborative activities that drive the project forward.
- **The Learning Hub:** a compilation and repository of the latest knowledge sharing, including success stories, webinars, and presentations
- **Voices from the community:** A dynamic recap of partner-led activities and perspectives such as local events, regional workshops, opinion articles, and media coverage,
- **Interviews** (if applicable): A series of short interviews conducted with various project partners discussing their experiences, objectives, implementation areas...
- **Events:** Twinning and Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops. This section reports on the crucial face-to-face and virtual learning exchanges that form the bedrock of the project's collaborative approach.
- **Sister projects and synergies:** A dedicated section to highlight key news, major achievements, and upcoming events from synergistic projects. We proactively contact sister and synergy projects in advance of the newsletter publication to gather their most current and relevant news, events, publications, and results. This not only strengthens the network but also provides subscribers with a broader view of the European HEI transformation landscape.

Efforts to build the subscriber base included:

- Sign-up prompts on high-traffic pages of the website.
- Social media campaigns.
- Calls-to-action embedded in blog posts and event pages.
- Collaboration with sister projects and similar initiatives.
- Cross-promotion in relevant online communities.

Total number of subscribers: **277 subscribers.**

Newsletter no.	Issue Date	Key Themes	Link
#1	Fri, Sep 15, 2023	An introduction of the project, objectives, partners and sister projects	https://mailchi.mp/b9276ad43078/catalisi-newsletter
#2	Feb 28, 2024	Highlights of the first general assembly, first resources already available on the web for HEIs to start their transformation. Key informative messages and opinion articles from the partners related to their intervention areas and acceleration services being used.	https://mailchi.mp/a0b6852061c/catalisi-newsletter-12680414?e=3afb1d6b7b
#3	September 2, 2024	A formal invitation from our Coordinators to the CoP and first set of interviews to the partners, a repository of webinars and other resources in the CATALYST Hub and first joint campaigns with the sister projects with a common branding	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/catalisi-newsletter-3-catalisi-project-3vphf/?trackingId=FaTaT%2FtLS8qXB3tTdedp8A%3D%3D
#4	April 1, 2025	First look into our newly rebranded website, how to navigate it and the new resources available to help HEIs on their systematic transformation. Highlights on the GA and new synergy project resources available.	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/catalisi-newsletter-4-catalisi-project-e38pf/?trackingId=hyafkIRZSX%2BwAXgp9%2FU8sA%3D%3D
#5	September 19, 2025	Official invitation to CATALISI Final Conference with a call for papers, a recap on the CATALISI success stories webinars, Transformational pathways from partners and MML/Twinning exchanges	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/catalisi-newsletter-5-catalisi-project-djxtf/?trackingId=LsmiFpf6S6yh6yAOk2ufDA%3D%3D
#6	December 23, 2025	A goodbye message with a recap on all the information available including resources, webinars, deliverables and synergy project outcomes. A closer look on the CATALYST hub and how to contact our partners and experts to establish new collaborations also in the future, after the project end.	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/catalisi-newsletter-6-catalisi-project-aa2ue/?trackingId=LN3%2F3oBSgLodm9CLWqhDWA%3D%3D

Table 3: CATALISI Newsletters

Figure 26: CATALISI Newsletters 1-6

Social Media

Throughout the project, CATALISI has maintained a strong and consistent presence across key social media channels. This presence supported communication & dissemination, and the visibility of research outcomes and Transformational resources for HEIs. The platforms were selected based on their relevance to different target audiences, and their use evolved as the project progressed, and communication needs shifted.

LinkedIn

CATALISI LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/catalisi-project/>), quickly became CATALISI's most influential communication channel. Chosen for its reach among policymakers, and HEIs, the platform allowed the project to engage deeply with its most relevant audiences.

- The page grew steadily to **829 followers** with a notable increase during major project milestones and events namely: Newsletters, General Assembly information, and joint activities with sister projects.
- Posts were consistently branded using standardised and custom templates and structured content categories, including event promotion, publication highlights, and CATALYST Hub tools.

Figure 27: CATALISI LinkedIn

X (formerly Twitter)

Since early 2024, the CATALISI project has strategically shifted its primary focus from X (formerly Twitter) to LinkedIn. This decision is underpinned by two critical factors that directly impact the project's reporting integrity and compliance standards:

- **Data Inaccessibility and Analytics Paywalls:** Following significant structural changes to X's business model, essential analytics tools and data extraction capabilities are now done through paywalls. This has rendered the consistent, high-fidelity monitoring of KPIs and audience reach.
- **GDPR Compliance and Data Privacy Concerns:** The project team has identified substantial risks regarding the reliability and legal standing of data processing on X. In 2024 and 2025, the European Commission intensified its scrutiny of the platform, culminating in a landmark €120 million fine in December 2025 for breaches of the Digital Services Act (DSA). The Commission highlighted deceptive design practices and a lack of transparency in the platform's advertising and data repositories. Furthermore, ongoing concerns raised by European Data Protection Authorities regarding X's non-compliance with GDPR, specifically concerning the unlawful processing of user data for AI training without consent². This have made the platform an unsuitable environment for an EU-funded project committed to the highest standards of data ethics.

Although the current environment on X presents challenges, the platform remained until the end of the project completion reaching a total of **58** followers.

² <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/xs-data-privacy-controversy-kitemetric-5rehe/>

Figure 28: CATALISI X

Videos and YouTube

CATALISI YouTube acted not only as a social media channel to share contents, but also as the official video repository of the project and hosted content central to its C&D activities.

- A total **44 videos** have been published, and the channel currently has 15 subscribers.
- Content includes:
 - The official project explanatory video (KPI related) (<https://youtu.be/sXOUFWFSRQ4>);
 - 10 video Interviews all the partners (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN76rxvn8nt60WX9PxsuhtJ9ZV2Gx2qKy>);
 - Recordings of key events, such as the CATALISI General Assembly (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN76rxvn8nt6dh9pwkGeiMKW07DPzTjcx>);
 - Learning Hub webinars repository: (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN76rxvn8nt60WX9PxsuhtJ9ZV2Gx2qKy>);
 - Community of Practice workshops and explanatory cards: (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN76rxvn8nt6jfh4g2dkPM6NTOQDLOW33>);
 - 8 Acceleration services short explanatory videos: (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN76rxvn8nt4isqDmba-1Rc-Ls5l68Lvc>);
 - 3 Intervention areas explanatory videos (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN76rxvn8nt4GjrbrEtTTPfz5EEoYkHHW>);
 - 5 Success Stories from partners (KPI related): (<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN76rxvn8nt45LMwNZPGuvqXxQmifFeCr>);

The videos with the highest views are:

- [UG Success Story | Transforming Research Ethos](#) with **278 views**. This webinar offers a blueprint for success in university-business collaboration.
- [Interview with Rrap Kryeziu, senior consultant at EY](#) with **198 views**. It discusses how a consultancy can play a crucial role in the HE ecosystem

- [1st CoP workshop: "Inspirational examples on institutional transformation in HEIs](#) with **109 views**. It discusses how HE can improve connections and activities with industry and business, with the scientific and academic community and with civil society.

Figure 29.: YouTube analytics: General from the channel, and most successful videos

The Learning Hub recorded webinars (organised in the context of T2.1) achieved their highest viewership with:

- [Gender inclusion in HE](#) with 74 views
- [Digitalisation of HE](#) with 41 views

Figure 30: YouTube analytics of the most successful webinars

This comprehensive analysis reveals a pronounced and strategic interest around Higher Education Institutions transformation agendas in several key areas. Specifically, for actively commercialising their research results and establishing a more robust, symbiotic connection with commercial and business partners. This shift underscores a desire to move beyond purely academic pursuits and translate knowledge into tangible economic and societal benefits.

It is recognised, however, that commercial cooperation is never easy, requiring significant effort to create meaningful and productive partnerships that align the differing cultures and objectives of academia and industry. A crucial element of this necessary transformation is a commitment to inclusive collaboration with industry.

During the CATALISI project lifespan in YouTube, we had a total of **1,575 views**, and a total **watch time of 73 hours**.

Zenodo

Zenodo community or repository is crucial for the CATALISI project primarily to comply with the Open Science requirements of its European Union funding, and to maximize the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) of its research outputs (see D.6.1 DMP for further information on data sharing and data management).

Zenodo community ensures the CATALISI project's work on transforming HEI governance and acceleration services is preserved, made widely available, and compliant with its funding obligations, ultimately maximizing the project's impact on the European Research Area (ERA).

We also participate in the “Acceleration Services in support of the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions” community together with our sister projects. It is part of the **EU Open Research Repository** and this aspect will be deepened in the “Networking and liaison with other initiatives” section further below.

Figure 31: CATALISI Zenodo communities

CATALISI social media channels: a summary and achievements

All of CATALISI's social media channels were actively maintained, with a clear effort to adapt the content and format to the expectations of each platform's audience. Templates and branding ensured consistency, and collaborative efforts with partners and sister projects helped grow, reach and strengthen the network.

Social media became a space for dialogue, visibility, and resources sharing. A section for key analytics data from each channel is included below and can be completed later at the final reporting stage with the updated follower counts and engagement metrics.

Platform	Followers/ subscribers	Engagement (clicks, likes comments and repost)	Impressions	Content	Comments
LinkedIn	829	54.594	118.636	385	The data is from November 27th
X	74	3 average per post	32 average per post	263	
YouTube	15	2 average per video	1575 views	43	
Newsletter	277	16 average	748	N/A	Count of 3 newsletter in LinkedIn

Table 4: CATALISI Social Media results

CATALISI Printed Materials

Print materials with the branding of the project were produced ahead of in-person events and include the following elements:

Type	Specifications	Circumstances / dissemination
CATALISI roll-up	Vinyl foldable rollup banner with a stand size 850x2200mm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CATALISI GA in Spain - CATALISI

	2 pieces printed	MML/Twinning exchange in Gdansk
CATALISI posters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A5 size poster with CATALISI key highlights, and acceleration services information - 60x90 cm size poster with CATALISI goals and transformation methodology - 60x90 cm size poster - 60x90 cm size poster with Capacity Building Acceleration Service for European HEIs (CBAS4HEIs) - CATALISI LUISS poster 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Printed and distributed among the partners for the events participation - Printed by UJI for their ETHNA conference - Final conference - REINFORCING Open and Responsible Research and Innovation Forum
A replicable framework of acceleration services flyer	3-folded flyer in A4 size with the final report of the replicable framework for institutional change	Produced and printed out for the CATALISI final conference
Booklets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A5 Acceleration services booklet - A5 Stories of Transformation booklet 	Produced and printed for the final conference, which include specific information from each partner, such as Implementer success stories and details on each Facilitator acceleration services.
Promotional Materials (Merchandise)	Tote bags and Water bottle	For the CATALISI Final Conference

Table 5: CATALISI Printed Materials

Roll-up banners: For in-person activities, one high-quality roll-up banner was produced and used at multiple events. This roll-up was professionally printed with a glossy finish, making them bright and eye-catching for attendees with information of the project including CATALISI objectives, list of domains and acceleration services, consortium partners, and contact details. (<https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/2.0-CATALISI-Roll-up-banner-for-print.pdf>)

Figure 32: CATALISI printed Materials

CATALISI Posters: printed for events where CATALISI partners presented the project outcomes. These were adapted from the standard templates and designed to fit event-specific themes and purposes

- <https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/CATALISI-poster.pdf>
- <https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CATALISI-24x36-inches-poster-ETHNA-conference.pdf>
- https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/CATALISI_Poster_ORRI_A1-1.pdf

Figure 33: CATALISI posters

Flyers: A4 3-folded factsheet –on the replicable framework for institutional change. Validated in 7 European universities. Ready for adoption by other universities across Europe, University alliances, and EU programmes. It promotes inclusive, open and sustainable innovation. <https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/Archive.zip>

The CATALISI Replicable Framework is a structured, adaptable methodology designed to guide Higher Education Institutions through systemic institutional transformation in Research and Innovation (R&I). Aligned with the European Research Area (ERA) and European Education Area (EEA) priorities. It has a 5-Step Transformational Pathway

- Step 1: Strategic Definition: HEIs identify intervention areas (e.g., Open Science, Gender Equality, or Public Engagement) through institutional self-assessment and alignment with ERA priorities.
- Step 2: Co-creation & Engagement: Activation of Acting Living Labs to map stakeholder needs across the "Quadruple Helix" and design initial Action Plans.
- Step 3: Implementation & Formative Evaluation: The first execution cycle, underpinned by the Theory of Change (ToC) and monitored via SMART KPIs to ensure evidence-based adjustments.
- Step 4: Strategic Integration: A second implementation cycle focused on "Strategic Anchoring," where transformation goals are embedded into formal institutional governance and resource planning.
- Step 5: Consolidation & Transferability: Finalisation of results and the development of a sustainability roadmap to ensure the transformation persists beyond the project's duration.

The framework also provides a "toolkit" of acceleration services that HEIs can tailor to their specific context:

- Living Labs: Participatory environments for real-world co-creation and testing.
- Transformational Pathways: Tailored roadmaps linking operational actions to long-term impact.
- Counselling: On-demand mentoring and coaching to navigate implementation challenges.
- Predictive Study: Foresight analysis to align institutional skills with future workforce demands.
- Capacity Building & Outreach: Mutual learning through webinars, twinning schemes, and workshops.
- Communities of Practice (CoP): A collaborative digital space for peer-to-peer knowledge exchange.
- CATALYST HUB: A digital gateway for funding, partnerships, and technology transfer.

Figure 34: Replicable Framework for Institutional Change

Booklets: 2 (types of) booklets: 50 copies were printed for each booklet (100 pcs in total), with each booklet having 49 and 53 pages respectively. The booklets were printed in A5 format, in full colour matte paper with spiral bookbinding.

- <https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/CATALISI-ACCELERATION-SERVICES-vFINAL.pdf>
- <https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/CATALISI-booklet-Stories-of-Transformation-vfinal-2.pdf>

Figure 35: CATALISI booklets

When events were virtual, booklets and flyers were adapted into PDF format and shared digitally with participants ahead of or during the event. This ensured inclusivity and sustainability while maintaining a branded and professional experience across platforms.

Promotional items (merchandise) were also created and distributed at the final event and shared with project partners to bring to other external events. These included water bottles, and foldable textile tote bags, all aligned with CATALISI visual style. We gave one tote bag to each registrant that included the CATALISI water bottle, two booklets and the replicable framework flyer.

Figure 36: CATALISI Merchandising

CATALISI Digital Materials

In addition to the physical materials, the **CATALISI Media Kit** was developed to store and provide access to all project informational and promotional materials in digital formats. It was made available for download on the website.

CATALISI Branding Includes (<https://catalisi.eu/branding/>):

- **CATALISI logo package:** in multiple formats (PNG, EPS, SVG) for flexible use across print and digital platforms.
- **CATALISI brand guidelines:** designed to ensure consistency in promoting project activities,
- **Sister projects branding:** Design to keep consistency in promoting activities together with CATALISI sister projects, it includes: a branding guidelines, logos and colours.

CATALISI Media Kit includes (<https://catalisi.eu/media-kit/>):

- **A branded PowerPoint template** used for both internal and external presentations.
- **Posters:** formatted for digital use and adapted from physical designs to promote the project online and at virtual events. These reflected event-specific themes while maintaining core branding.
- **Roll-up:** provided in high-resolution digital format, featuring CATALISI unified visual identity.
- **CATALISI booklets:** CATALISI Implementers Success Stories and CATALIS Acceleration Services booklet made available as a downloadable PDF to present an overview of the partner's outcomes, objectives, activities, and key accomplishments in a professional, visually engaging format.
- **The CATALISI replicable framework 3-folded flyer:** provided in A4 glossy digital format for quick reference and distribution via email, social media, and digital booths at events.
- **CATALISI webinar flyers:** Including the agenda and speaker's presentations.
- **CATALISI CoP concept note and factsheet:** A visually appealing, in-depth explanation covering the Community of Practice's objectives, how to join, and the expertise's requirements.
- **CATALISI factsheet:** A simple informative factsheet about the project 's objectives and activities for quick reference and distribution via email, social media, and digital booths at events.
- **CATALISI Press Releases:** issued digitally to announce milestones and events, summarizing the project's results and shared widely through online platforms and media outreach.

CATALISI Deliverables and Reports includes (<https://catalisi.eu/deliverables/>):

- **Deliverables:** Public deliverables related to the project's core methodology and communication, plans, findings, outcomes on activities related to all the tasks of the project. These deliverables are the concrete outputs of the CATALISI project's work.
- **CATALIS Acceleration Services booklet**
- **CATALISI Implementers Success Stories booklet**
- **Report The CATALISI replicable framework of acceleration services:**
- **CATALISI Final Conference presentations:**
 - [CATALISI Final Conference_Accelerate Future HEI](#)
 - [CATALISI Final Conference_aUPaEU](#)
 - [CATALISI Final Conference_Marjon van Wijnbergen](#)

- CATALISI Final Conference_policy validation session
- CATALISI Final Conference_Research Culture survey
- CATALISI Final Conference_Research Culture workshop_Laura Bernal
- CATALISI Final Conference_Research Culture Workshop
- CATALISI Final Conference_Results & Replicable Framework of acceleration services
- Final Conference Rinske van den Berg

CATALISI webinar ppts (<https://catalisi.eu/learning-hub/>): A repository of all publicly available and presentations from the speaker

CATALISI Newsletters archive (<https://catalisi.eu/newsletters/>) includes:

- **CATALISI newsletters**, all editions available documented project progress, shared event highlights, and showcased the impact of CATALISI activities over time.

EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: BEST PRACTICES FROM UNIVERSITY OF GDANSK

25 NOVEMBER 2024 9.00 - 11.00 AM CET

09:00-09:05 Welcome and webinar introduction by EY
 09:05-09:10 Introduction of CATALISI project by APRE
 09:10-09:20 Ice breaker
 09:20-09:40 Centre for Sustainable Development as peer-to-peer learning platform
 09:40-09:50 Q&A Session and Open discussion
 09:50-10:10 Best Practice - Sustainability day - How organize and educate future students
 10:10-10:20 Q&A Session and Open discussion
 10:20-10:40 Experimenting with the transdisciplinaryarts on learning communities and empowering youth
 10:40-11:00 Closing Remarks and Next Steps

DR HAB. SYLWIA MROZOWSKA, Associate professor at the Institute of Political Science, University of Gdansk
 DR HAB. BARBARA PAWLOWSKA, Associate Professor at the Faculty of Economics, University of Gdansk
 DR. IRENA CHAWBILSKA, Director of the Academic Centre for Polish Language and Culture, University of Gdansk

OPEN LIVING LAB DAYS 2024 - CATALISI SIDE EVENT

Opening universities to Stakeholders through Living Labs for Institutional transformation

24 SEPTEMBER 2024 9.00 AM - 12.00 PM

9:00 - 9:10 Introduction to CATALISI Project- APRE
 9:10 - 9:20 CATALISI Acting Living Labs- ENoLL
 9:20 - 9:40 Engaging External Stakeholders - CATALISI UCC Acting Living Labs- Martin Galvin (UCC)
 9:40 - 9:50 Coffee Break
 9:50 - 10:50 World Cafe Discussions on External Stakeholders Engagement- All
 10:50 - 11:10 Recap on World Cafe Discussions
 11:10 - 11:30 Presentation of UVT Living Labs and its Experience with External Stakeholders- UVT Representative
 11:30 - 11:50 Q&A
 11:50 - 12:00 Conclusions and Closing- APRE & ENoLL

REINFORCING THE ROLE OF UNIVERSITIES IN LOCAL INNOVATION SYSTEM

22 MAY 2024 10.00 AM - 12.00 PM

10:00-10:05 Welcome and webinar introduction by EY
 10:05-10:10 Introduction of CATALISI project by APRE
 10:10-10:20 Ice breaker
 10:20-11:00 UniCity: Role of University in Local Innovation
 11:00-11:30 Q&A Session and open discussion
 11:30-12:00 Closing

ROBERTO SAN SALVADOR DEL VALLE, Director of Digital Skills Lab Chair, University of Daquis and Professor of the School of Social and Human Science

POLICY VALIDATION SESSION

11 November 2025
 CATALISI Final Conference

Changing researcher assessment and RC: policy insights

Saïll Fetz, Program Manager for the Netherlands Recognition and Rewards program, Utrecht University
 Marjon van Wijnenbergen, HR manager Research BV, Amsterdam UMC

Insights from CATALISI
 Miriam van Loon, Amsterdam UMC
 Rita F. Alves dos Santos, NRIIN Coordinator and RIOS project lead, Amsterdam UMC
 Laura Bernal Sánchez, Technical secretary for Ethics Committee, Universitat Jaume I (UJI)

Universities and Higher Education Institutions: Key Actors in the Research & Innovation Ecosystem

Rinske van den Berg
 REA - Research Executive Agency
 Policy Advisor

CATALISI STORIES OF TRANSFORMATION

Facilitate the transformation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to embrace more sustainable research and innovation, ensuring alignment with societal challenges and European values.

CATALISI PROJECT

CATALISI | Catalysation of institutional transformations of Higher Education institutions through the adoption of acceleration services is a Horizon Europe project funded by European Union 2023-2025 under the Grant Agreement n. 101094917
 CATALISI is supporting Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to successfully implement strategies for institutional transformation.
 Through the adoption of targeted and innovative acceleration services in the field of Research and Innovation CATALISI will strengthen European Universities collaborations and alliances to become lighthouses of European values.

CATALISI ACCELERATION SERVICES

Facilitate the transformation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to embrace more sustainable research and innovation, ensuring alignment with societal challenges and European values.

Figure 37: CATALISI digital materials and resources available on the website

Press Releases

In line with the CATALISI communication strategy, five official press releases were produced and disseminated throughout the project, aimed at raising public awareness and reaching key stakeholder audiences across Europe. These press releases were intended to cover key project milestones (project launch, validation process, project success stories and final results) and ensure visibility in both general and specialist media outlets.

- The **first press release** (<https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/CATALISI-Press-Release-1-About-the-project.docx-1.pdf>), was launched on January 2023. It introduced the project and its overarching goals to a broad European audience. Titled “*CATALYSATION OF INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS THROUGH THE ADOPTION OF ACCELERATION SERVICES*” it highlighted the project's ambition to help and support Higher Education Institutions to successfully implement a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation, through the adoption of acceleration services. The piece emphasised the project's relevance to research careers and talent support, open science and public engagement, and sustainable research and education.
- The **second press release** (<https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/CATALISI-Press-Release-2-Kick-off-meeting.docx.pdf>) issued on March 2023, focused on the project kick off, presenting our partners and their objectives as implementers and the Facilitators acceleration services.
- The **third press release** (<https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CATALISI-Press-Release-3.pdf>) released on February 2024 focused on the project General Assembly and promoting participation in the CATALISI CoP, composed of a group of people who share expertise and experiences in institutional transformation in HEI.
- The **fourth press release** (<https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/CATALISI-Success-Stories-Press-Release-5.pdf>) released in May 2025 in a more visually appealing style. It focused on the Success Stories campaign sent to more than 20 media outlets and shared a series of five webinars that shared the transformation pathway behind our Implementers partners, highlighting concrete actions that enabled institutional change. Our aim was to serve as a source of inspiration for other Higher Education Institutions across Europe.

These press releases contributed significantly to CATALISI visibility and were shared through various digital channels, including the project website, newsletters, social media, and partner networks. They were also pitched to targeted news websites, social media and share with the partners to distribute among their Media Outlets contacts to stimulate further coverage and engagement from both the public and expert audiences. CATALISI team have also strategically distributed the press release among the media outlets targeted in *D5.1 First Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability plan* being very successful among Spanish media such as El Diario, El Periodico Mediterraneo, Castellon Plaza and more. The full media outreach listing can be found in the *Annex2_ CATALISI Communication Activities and Media Coverage*.

Figure 38: CATALISI Press Releases

CATALISI Events

Throughout its lifetime, CATALISI actively participated in and organised a wide range of high-level conferences, co-creation workshops, forums, and public engagement events. These activities were fundamental to disseminating the project's objectives, results, and policy relevance, while fostering collaboration and dialogue with HEIs, policy, and civil society stakeholders in close collaboration with all project partners. The list of internal presence, online and hybrid events, organised (or co-organised) by the CATALISI consortium. The full list of events can be found in *Annex 1_CATALISI Internal Events*.

Figure 39: CATALISI KOM, Rome, Italy

Figure 40: KTU MML workshop, Kaunas, Lithuania

Figure 41: UJI MML workshop, Castellón, Spain

Figure 42: LUISS MML workshop, Rome, Italy

Figure 43: AUTH MML workshop, Thessaloniki, Greece

Figure 44: UG MML workshop, Gdansk, Poland

Figure 45: UCC MML workshop, Cork, Ireland

Figure 46: CoP Workshop, online

Figure 47: Gender inclusion webinar, online

Figure 48: CATALISI annual meeting at UJI, Spain

Figure 49: UJI MML/Twinning, Castellon, Spain

Figure 50: Recognition of qualifications webinar, online

Figure 51: AUMC MML/Twinning, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Figure 52: Reinforcing the Role of Universities webinar, online

Figure 53: UCC MML/Twinning, Cork, Ireland

Figure 54: 1st CoP workshop, online

Figure 55: MML/Twinning at LUISS, Rome, Italy

Figure 56: MML/Twinning at AUTH, Thessaloniki, Greece

Partners individual communication channels, Associations, and Media coverage

CATALISI partners are deeply committed to the dissemination of project results and activities. As established during the creation of Del. 5.1 *First Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability plan*, partners are encouraged to integrate dissemination and communication actions across all CATALISI activities.

A key focus for CATALISI implementers is to share best practices and detailed use-cases from their experiences. This is vital for fostering synergies with other partners and channels, and for reaching a wider audience. Furthermore, partners are encouraged to engage local and national media (press, radio, TV) by offering interviews, site visits, and demonstrations.

In line with the Grant Agreement (GA), partners are obligated to communicate and disseminate the project and its results, making them accessible to both targeted and general publics. The specific provisions and any restrictions on dissemination are detailed in the GA and the Consortium Agreement (CA).

For a complete record of all partner communication activities and media coverage, please refer to *Annex 2_CATALISI Communication Activities and Media Coverage*.

Figure 57: Communication Activities and Media Coverage from partners

2.4. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY AND RESULTS

CATALISI was featured in more than **25** international and European events, including conferences, forums, workshops, and science-policy dialogues through the participation of our partners in third party events. To manage and track participation, F6S developed an Events of Interest Tracker which includes section such as: Name of the event, Date of the event, Location, Event website, Submission deadline, and why is a relevant event to CATALISI. The project partners could regularly suggest relevant events (available on the CATALISI internal SharePoint).

Event type	Event name	Date of the event	Location	Event website/link	Submission deadline	Why you think this is a relevant event to CATALISI
Conference	IC2024 conference	June 5-8 2024	Ljubljana, SI	https://www.ic2024.eu/	April 13th	Clear dimension of public involvement
Forum	EDU University Forum in Kaunas	6-7 JUNE	Kaunas	https://www.eduforum.lt/	None mentioned	A Resilient and Sustainable Society (R&S) as the main theme for
Conference	SciComm South West Conference 2024	June 7 2024	Bristol	https://www.sci-comm.org.uk/2024-south-west/	1st of March	It is a science communication event where we can still submit a proposal
Webinar	Science communication and research integrity	June 6 2024	Online	https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/science-communication-and-research-integrity-tickets-690002396457	none mentioned	It is about science communication
Conference	Annual Conference of the Science Communication 2024	June 06-07 2024	Zurich	https://2024.scc2024.ch/	Dec 5 2023	They are still looking for people to speak and present at the conference
Webinar	Science Communication and Public Engagement Training	July 07 2024	Online	https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/science-communication-and-public-engagement-training-tickets-1261371405814#event=1261371405814	none mentioned	It is about science communication
Conference	Trust conference	October 22-23 2024	London, UK	https://www.trustconference.org/	none mentioned	The conference brings together world-leading experts, innovators and activists share their insights into pressing global issues including media freedom, the impact of technology on human rights, socio-economic inequality and the climate emergency
Forum	World Science Forum 2024	November 20-23	Budapest, HU	https://www.worldscienceforum.org/	No call	Journalism as well as responsibilities and influence of science
Web conference	Connect & Share the 2024 OCC Conference "Trust through Transparency"	March 14 2024	Online	https://www.bbc.com/news/health-67284309	none mentioned	"Trust through Transparency" and we look forward to a lively discussion on the role that the Data Management Community can play in increasing trust in academia and in separating fact
High Level Conference				https://scienceeurope.org/events/hq		
Conference	on Science Communication	March 12-13 2024	Brussels Belgium	https://scienceeurope.org/events/hq		
Conference	European Research and Innovation Days 2024	20-21 March 2024	Brussels and online	https://www.euridays.eu/		none mentioned
Conference	ECSA 2024 conference	April 3-6 2024	Vienna / Online	https://2024.ecsa.eu	15-mar-24	Some of our ADIMs are members of ECSA and the organization focuses on citizen sciences
Conference	EnTech Digital Europe	April 16-17 2024	London, UK	https://event.techpolicycentre.com/en-tech-digital-europe-2024		"Our best-in-class live journalism, exclusive content, and trusted insights from leading industry experts"
Conference	EUSEA conference 2024	May 15-16 2024	Thess, GE	https://euseaconf.europa.eu/	No call	"Public Engagement Beyond Boundaries" relevant for the vignette study and public involvement
Summit	THE Europe Universities Summit			https://www.timehighereducation.com/europe-universities-summit-2024		We need to keep an eye for 2024
	2024 5th International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research	22nd May-23rd May 2024	Berlin	https://www.confernet.org/2024/mr		Academics and practitioners around the world to discuss and share the contemporary issues of business and social science research
	15th International Conference on Management, Economics & Social Science - ICMESS 2024	19th - 20th June, 2024	Edinburgh, United Kingdom	https://researchfora.com/Conference/2024/ICMESS2024		Researchers and Academicians to share the knowledge and ideas in the recent trends in the field of Management, Economics & Social Science
	18th International Conference on Social Science and Economics 2024	7th- 8th June, 2024	Edinburgh, United Kingdom	https://www.confernet.org/Conference/2024/ICSSSE2024		Leading international conferences for presenting novel and fundamental advances in the fields of Social Science and Economics
	International Conference on					platform for the academicians, researchers, engineers, industrial

Figure 58: Events of interest

External events

Throughout 2024 and into 2025, the CATALISI project participated in a diverse range of conferences, webinars, training sessions, and meetings aimed at disseminating its goals, sharing outcomes, and fostering collaboration within the academic community. For a complete record of all partner communication activities and media coverage, please refer to *Annex 3_CATALISI External Events*.

Key events included the **Symposium of the Spanish Association of Ethics and Political Philosophy of Spain** and the **8th Conference on Research Integrity**, where CATALISI showcased its approach to scientific evaluation and research integrity. Partners also presented methodologies and shared best practices with stakeholders from European universities and research institutions. At the ORRI **REINFORCING Conference (Vienna, 2024)**, CATALISI highlighted its successful results from mutual learning and Twinning activities, while the **2024 EUA Funding Forum** provided a platform to discuss sustainable research financing.

The project further expanded its reach through events like the **Open Living Lab Days 2024** and Training at **Karolinska Institutet**, where its co-developed strategies for stakeholder engagement and provided insights into Open Science and Open Data. The INTERREG **Connecting Regions, Empowering Universities event** in 2025 where CATALISI participated together with WIDERA Sister Projects: Accelerate Future HEI and aUPaEU to discuss together with regional policymakers, university representatives, and Horizon Europe stakeholders' policy solutions and best practices. **Conference on Research Careers** (closed session) ERA structural policy 'Improving the Articulation between R&I and Higher Education Within the ERA and Unleashing the Full Potential of European R&I Ecosystems' to improve alignment between EU and MS on R&I.

These events were pivotal in strengthening CATALISI's impact and building connections across European Higher Education Institutions, promoting transformational change in research and education policies.

Figure 59: NCP WIDERA.NET workshop, Online, May 2023

Figure 60: ETHNA conference March 2023 at UJI, Spain

Figure 61: ORRI REINFORCING Conference, October 2024

Figure 62: Open Living Labs Day, Timisoara, Romania

Figure 63: INTERREG event, Online, October 2025

Figure 64: UJI Open Access Week

2.5. NETWORKING AND LIAISON WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

CATALISI initiated and sustained the core cluster with [aUPaEU](#), and [Accelerate Future HEI](#), two Horizon Europe-funded sister projects that share the overarching goal of helping HEIs in their transformative pathways through the adoption of acceleration services. While each project approaches this objective from a different perspective, all three are united by a common mission: **design, pilot and implement acceleration services and institutional transformation models that support HEIs in modernising their structures, processes and governance systems in line with ERA priorities.**

Sister projects ecosystem

CATALISI initiated and sustained the cluster meetings with aUPaEU and Accelerate Future HEI from May 2024. To foster closer collaboration and increase impact, the three projects convened once every month to align their dissemination, and communication joint efforts, while the coordinators of the projects met extensively and when needed, to discuss common initiatives, actions, joint workshops and the drafting of joint policy recommendations. Starting from the first year of implementation, more than 25 monthly meetings were conducted online, along with the joint participation in externally organized events. The joint communication engagements were supported by the co-design of cross-promotional strategies, such as shared cluster pages on project websites, joint newsletters exchanges, harmonised social media campaigns, and unified branding guidelines created by F6S and applied across visual and communication materials.

Our joint dissemination activities include:

- Monthly communication meetings
- Coordination of joint social media campaigns and cross-promotional activities
- Develop of a common brand identity
- Shared branding development
- Shared event spreadsheet for synergic participation
- Joint policy deliverables
- Feature on each-other websites
- INORMS Congress joint submission
- BOOSTER dissemination module collaboration
- CATALISI final webinar: Connecting Policies and Projects: Advancing the European Research Area Together
- Joint Zenodo community.
- Joint 2025 wishes video.
- Shared Excel file with potential events of interest
- Co-identification of shared challenges, needs and barriers and evidence mapping
- Joint policy, training and dissemination workshops (e.g. participation and organisation of joint events such as the webinar with Inspiring ERA project, Interreg Europe event, the aUPaEU Agora workshop (upcoming January 2026),
- Conference on Research Careers in Brussels
- Shared infrastructures, tools and services through the Agora Platform creating synergies with methodologies and services tested in CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI, also through the establishment of a signed "AGORA" Platform Users Agreement.
- Creation of a common policy dialogue space: shared positioning towards upcoming ERA Policy Agenda, development of a common set of policy recommendations, presentation and discussion of recommendations within EC workshop *Higher Education Institutions and Research Performing Organisations as enablers of the Fifth Freedom*

The joint branding concept was developed and proposed by F6S (unified templates for presentations, social media posts and other visual materials) and adopted by the sister projects for the joined C&D activities. It reflects the 3 projects' common mission and complementarity, reinforcing the idea that accelerating Europe HEI and Alliances systematically needs a bright vision with an optimistic and clear roadmap.

A unified brand identity enhances the visibility of the collective work, making it easier for stakeholders: policymakers, researchers, HEIs, and the public, to recognize and engage with the projects. This synergy:

- Strengthens outreach and dissemination efforts.
- Creates a recognisable and coherent narrative around Transformation Pathways for HEIs
- Facilitates cross-project events, publications, and policy dialogues. The Joint Final Conference in Amsterdam (November 2025) exemplified this approach, where all three projects co-hosted sessions, shared policy findings and recommendations.

On a practical level, we created a common SharePoint folder to document our communication activities and a common share slogan: **TOGETHER FOR HEI TRANSFORMATION.**

Figure 65: Common branding for the sister projects

Booster Dissemination service

In early 2025, we took our collaboration a step further, led by Accelerate Future HEI, we engaged with the European Commission initiative, the *Horizon Booster Platform (Booster)* service, to discuss the possibility of all three sister projects using their free services to support the work on dissemination and exploitation.

As communicated through the Booster portal, the delivery of **Service 2.1 – Dissemination Support** (DIS) to our projects has been successfully completed and uploaded to the Booster portal.

Booster Key Findings

Based on the actions carried out by the DIS service delivery team together with the project group, the following recommendations and findings can be highlighted:

- The cluster has a strong operational foundation, with identified Key Exploitable Results (KERs), initial branding elements, and coordinated actions. However, dissemination remains largely operational rather than strategic. There is a need for a comprehensive joint dissemination roadmap to leverage partner networks, channels, and resources to maximize the visibility and impact of project outcomes.
- A recognisable brand exists, supported by shared visual guidelines, but identity elements are only partially formalised. To strengthen visibility and coherence, the cluster requires a strategic messaging framework, consistent templates, and a stronger focus on storytelling.
- Joint events have been successfully initiated, including a planned large-scale event involving sister projects, policy officers, and Interreg representatives. While this demonstrates excellent coordination, a structured event strategy is still needed to systematically target wider audiences, strengthen engagement, and ensure the long-term impact of these events.

These comments were addressed by creating an official brand guidelines available in the web (<https://catalisi.eu/synergy-projects/>) and a more structured event planning involving the coordination team in advance and creating common visuals such as the ones developed for the final policy brief recommendations:

Figure 66: Policy brief infographics in the common branding

The projects are also utilizing the **Booster Module 3.5 Audio-Visual Support** service to produce a final joint video which will highlight key insights from the joint policy recommendations elaborated by the three projects, thus demonstrating the collaborative effort of the "3 sisters" regarding policy recommendations and implications of their findings. It will feature common branding and be leveraged for sustainability purposes, while the

sisters will keep using the common branding including CATALISI logo beyond the project lifespan.

Events and other joint activities

The three sister projects have also engaged in extensive collaboration, demonstrating a unified front at a variety of events and international conferences. This joint effort has been showcased and coordinated jointly, effectively amplifying the projects' combined message, results and impact. An example of such collaboration is the participation and organisation of joint events such as the webinar with Inspiring ERA project, Interreg Europe event, the aUPaEU Agora workshop (upcoming January 2026), CATALISI Final conference and policy session - November 2025, Conference on *Research Careers* in Brussels - December 2025, etc.

Together for HEI transformation

When we first started collaborating, we knew we needed a common slogan and date to highlight our objectives. We identified a shared focus: World Creativity and Innovation Day, observed on April 21st, which is designated by the UN to promote awareness of creativity and innovation's role in human development. Our chosen slogan, "Together for HEI transformation," encapsulates our common objectives. The sister projects leveraged this UN-designated day to collectively highlight our innovative methodologies and share preliminary results from each respective project.

Introducing the communications teams behind our three HORIZON sister projects and why are we sister projects

This campaign was meant to: introduce the team, emphasizing our collaborative approach, highlight how we work, share progress and challenges, and our joint communication actions. This collaborative framework is designed to empower our methodologies and maximize engagement, exploitation, and overall impact: <https://catalisi.eu/what-are-sister-projects-and-why-do-they-matter/>

Figure 67 Sister project communication teams' collaboration introductory post

INORMS Congress Madrid

EARMA hosted the INORMS Congress at the IFEMA Palacio Municipal, replacing its usual annual conference. This inaugural hosting by EARMA, under the theme "A Sustainable Profession in a Sustainable World" attracted over 2,200 research managers and administrators from 67 countries.

The three sister projects participated with a joint abstract submission called: *Acceleration services for HEIs' transformation Good practices from three Horizon Europe-funded projects.*

Reflecting on an Incredible Year & Looking Ahead to 2025

A compelling video featuring the Project Coordinators from the aUPaEU CATALISI project and the Accelerate Future HEI Project looking back at 2024 significant progress, key milestones, and notable achievements. It also looked ahead to 2025, outlining the ambitious promises and exciting opportunities anticipated in the fields of innovation, strengthened collaboration between partner institutions, and the projected impact on Higher Education Institutions and the wider community. The video aims to engage stakeholders by celebrating successes and clearly articulating the forward-looking vision and strategy for sustained growth and influence in the upcoming year. (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oV4CVRHMAHU>)

Figure 68: Joint video featuring our PC

Interreg Europe event "Connecting regions, empowering universities through stronger R&I policies"

Accelerate Future HEI, aUPaEU, and CATALISI project came together at the Interreg Europe event "Connecting regions, empowering universities through stronger R&I policies", a workshop co-organised by the Interreg Policy Learning Platform and UIIN. The session highlighted how HEIs can facilitate innovation and contribute to societal change through:

- A strong policy foundation: HEIs are pivotal to achieving Europe's innovation goals.
- Targeted acceleration: Accelerate's services help universities strengthen their role within regional innovation ecosystems
- Digital infrastructures: aUPaEU's Agora platform boosts collaboration, making innovation processes more efficient and scalable
- Sustainable transformation: CATALISI ensures that transformation is a permanent institutional shift

A joint campaign was also developed to boost attendees, and a joint article was produced and featured in each website: <https://catalisi.eu/widera-sister-projects-join-forces-at-interreg-europe-event/>

Three EU funded projects signed a collaboration agreement to accelerate research and innovation

A Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was signed between the 3 sister projects to collaborate in communication, dissemination and outreach activities. The agreement covers two major areas: (1) joint efforts in dissemination activities and (2) providing policymakers with insights and recommendations about the European research landscape. This shared commitment in dissemination will ensure the amplification of the respective projects' outcomes, beyond the individual project's reach. A unified voice strengthens the evidence

base, offering policymakers richer, more holistic insights into the European research and education landscape.

At the same time, it will support the projects' sustainability, by exploiting the synergies among the three parties on the acceleration services developed, and their inclusion in the Agora platforms created by the aUPaEU project. Shared events like the 2025 INORMS Congress, Interreg Europe workshop and CATALISI Conference, which is taking place in Amsterdam on 11 November 2025, will generate more impact from the three projects.

This agreement turns our positive cooperation into a formal partnership, making sure our work has a stronger and longer-lasting impact on Higher Education Institutions. By joining forces in sharing results and giving recommendations to policymakers, we can speak with one clear voice. Together, we'll reach more people, ensure our projects live on, and speed up innovation and change in universities across Europe.

The Collaboration Agreement was signed by Chiara Pocaterra (Head of Projects Department at APRE – CATALISI Coordinating partner), Jesus Angel Alcober Segura (Delegate of the rector for the Unite! Digital Campus and Associate Professor at UPC – aUPaEU Coordinating partner and Arno Meerman (CEO & Founder of UIIN – Accelerate Future HEI Coordinating partner).

The 3 sister projects created a joint article and Social Media campaign <https://catalisi.eu/three-eu-funded-projects-have-signed-a-collaboration-agreement-to-accelerate-research-and-innovation/>

CATALISI Final Conference

The three sister projects were present and collaborated during the CATALISI Final event (November 2025) in three different ways:

- A presentation of the projects: Rimante Rusaite (Accelerate Future HEI) and Jesús Alcober (aUPaEU), shared synergies and insights from their respective projects. Accelerate Future HEI showcased transformation pathways tested across nine universities, while aUPaEU presented the Agora digital platform, already deployed in 12 university alliances to support collaboration and shared infrastructures. Together with CATALISI, these projects demonstrated how acceleration services can act as systemic enablers of change.
- Poster presentation: As part of the Dissemination and Networking Session, sister and synergy projects working on initiatives related to topics such as institutional transformation, Open RRI and the empowerment of the European Research Area (ERA), were invited to present posters, roll-ups or any other relevant dissemination material highlighting their projects, initiatives and practices. This is a valuable opportunity to showcase their work, exchange experiences and connect with other projects across Europe.
- Joint Policy session: the debate highlighted both barriers and enablers of institutional change in HEIs and Alliances, stressing the need for shared frameworks, leadership mentoring, interoperable infrastructures, and harmonised monitoring systems.

Figure 69: Pictures from CATALISI Final Conference, Amsterdam, November 11th, 2025

“Connecting Policies and Projects: Advancing the European Research Area (ERA) Together” webinar

The three sister projects featured in the CATALISI webinar “Connecting Policies and Projects: Advancing the European Research Area (ERA) Together” to showcase the results and recommendations from WIDERA project on the empowerment of HEIs in line with the ERA policy.

Three HORIZON Europe WIDERA projects together with INSPIRING ERA project shared challenges, evidence and recommendations that can inform future policy developments and support the implementation of the next ERA Policy Agenda. The event was held on November 28th, 2025 and reached **100** attendees.

Figure 70: Screenshot from webinar

Conference on Research careers 2025

The 3 sister projects were invited by the European commission to present the joint policy recommendations during a closed workshop on the ERA Structural Policy *Improving the articulation between R&I and Higher Education within the ERA and unleashing the full potential of European R&I ecosystems* held on December 12th, 2025 in Brussels. The workshop titled “Higher Education Institutions and Research Performing Organisations as enablers of the fifth freedom” has been an important opportunity to present our joint recommendations to EU representatives and key stakeholders to stimulate reflections and give concrete inputs on how to improve alignment between EU and member states on R&I to support the realization of the fifth freedom. CATALISI project coordinator personally participated on behalf of the three sister projects. More info and details here: [Conference on Research Careers](#).

Policy briefs

As part of its strategy to influence science policy and support evidence-based decision-making, CATALISI together with the 2 sister projects developed targeted policy briefs

aimed at European policymakers and institutional actors working on the implementation of the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2022-2024 (Action 13), ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027.

- The first joint policy brief: Acceleration Services in support of the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions has been published in May 2024, after the first year of implementation https://catalisi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/CATALISI_D6.2_First-Policy-brief_APRE_1.1.pdf

The policy objective is identifying key policy gaps and formulating recommendations for the European Commission. The primary objective of this first policy brief is to align high-level European Research Area (ERA) policies and their practical application within HEIs. The results of this brief are based upon the activities of the first year of implementation of the three projects.

- The second joint policy brief (2025): Challenges and enablers of institutional transformation in Higher Education Institutions through acceleration services (upcoming publication).

The document goes in more depth and summarises the joint policy recommendations developed by the three sister projects after 3 years of implementation.

The policy recommendations presented here result from a close observation of institutional transformation processes implemented by universities, HEIs and their alliances across the three projects. They are based on data collection, exchanges and discussion, and comparative analyses conducted at different institutional levels.

3. MONITORING, EVALUATION AND REPORTING

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as outlined in the Grant Agreement have been revised to reflect the outcomes achieved over the course of the CATALISI project (see table below). These KPIs were designed to guide and measure outreach, engagement, and impact across target audiences.

3.1. PROJECT KPIs

Instrument	Objective	KPI	Achievements
Brand Identity: Logo and Templates	It will comprise brand guidelines, colours, and font codes, and the logo variants needed for all applicable online or offline channels and collaterals	1 Identity kit M2-M36	First presented during the KOM and further developed in the D5.1 <i>First Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability plans</i> .
Dissemination Events	The consortium will co-organise with projects under	3 workshops M1-M36	1. MML workshop with CoP members 11/7/2023: "Inspirational examples

	the same topic and other related projects a workshop		<p>on institutional transformation of HEIs in R&I agenda."</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. MML CoP workshop (2nd) 3/5/2025: The workshop brought together experts, researchers, and key stakeholders from across Europe to explore how to better equip researchers for the evolving labour market. 3. NCP WIDERA.NET workshop 5/30/2024: Workshop with the sister projects to define the Acceleration services provided by the projects 4. Open Living Lab Days 2024-CATALISI Side Event Opening universities to Stakeholders through Living Labs for Institutional transformation 11/15/2024 ENOLL workshop in response to the growing challenges that Higher Education Institutions face in engaging with external stakeholders.
Webinar series	Webinar with the project partners to present outcomes of the case studies available in YouTube	At least 5 webinars	<p>5 webinars were organised and available in YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yb-wWgvncg&list=PLN76rxvn8nt45LMwNZPGuvqXxQmifFeCr Partners: UJI, KTU, AUTH, and UG</p>
Meetings and Exhibitions	Bilateral meetings, internal conferences and relevant exhibitions and trade fairs identified in the Plan for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation of Results	5 bilateral meetings, 2 international conferences, 3 exhibitions	<p>CATALISI project participated in more than 20 external events, including bilateral meetings with all sister and synergy projects, Conference, and forums and exhibitions to showcase CATALISI results. More detailed information can be found under Dissemination strategy - Third Party events (<i>Annex 3</i>).</p>
Toolkits, contents and recommendations	Exploitable assets will include a package for project results dissemination	Reports, factsheets 1 policy briefs and 1 scientific poster	<p>All the materials are available in the website: https://catalisi.eu/resources/</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Brand kit 2. CATALISI Implementers Success Stories booklet 3. CATALIS Acceleration Services booklet

			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. A replicable framework for institutional change 5. CATALISI project presentation 6. CATALISI project poster 7. CATALISI Poster ETHNA conference 8. CATALISI project factsheet 9. CATALISI Community of Practice factsheet 10. CATALISI ORRI poster 11. CATALISI CoP concept note 12.4 Press Release 13. Newsletter archive 14. MML/Twinning presentations 15. Webinar PDF presentations from the speakers 16. Final conference presentations 17. Public deliverables and reports
Communication Materials package	Preparation of a set of communication material comprising project logo and visual identity	1 project brochure, 1 rollup banner, 2 posters, 2 flyers	<p>All the materials are available in the website: https://catalisi.eu/resources/</p> <p>- Media Kit:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 10 CATALISI webinar flyers 2. 1 CATALISI roll-up 3. 1 project brochure 4. 3 posters
CATALISI website	It will be the primary contact point for those external to the project, it will communicate	1 website 30.000 visits from more than 27 countries	<p>CATALISI website has 12.266 visits and 28.724 page views from more than 45 countries.</p> <p>For more detailed information, please look at website analytics section.</p>
Promotional videos	Short videos presenting the project	1 promotional video, 2 video teasers for SM campaign, more than 10 promotional banners, 10 thematic CATALISI cards	<p>1 promotional video</p> <p>Video teasers for SM campaigns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teaser 1 (CATALISI in On Word) - Teaser 2: CATALISI Farewell - 9 interviews available in YouTube <p>13 promotional banners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Assembly at UJI - GA AUTH - Intervention Areas in Research careers and talent support - Intervention areas in Sustainability in Finance - Intervention areas in Modus Operandi, - Capacity Building, - Living Labs,

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding Opportunities, - CATALISI Learning Hub, - Counselling - CoP1 - CoP2 - CoP_3 <p>10 thematic CATALISI cards disseminated in LinkedIn and the CoP</p>
Online Communication	A series of interviews and feature articles featuring each test cases' products published on the project website, distributed on the EC communication channels and to selected media. Also shared via e-newsletter	Bi-annual e-newsletters	<p>6 newsletters available in the web: https://catalisi.eu/newsletters/</p> <p>58 blog articles, amongst which the following are featuring test cases products:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UJI: How to boost open science in Spain: the new National Open Science Strategy (ENCA) - UG: Transformation of the University of Gdansk towards Sustainable Development – Selected Activities and Initiatives. - KTU: Discussing transformational changes with the international community of researchers and practitioners - UG: Reimagining Higher Education Research Financing -A Living Lab Approach - F6S: The need of effective communication and dissemination in European Projects - AUTH: Integration of Living Labs within the University: Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Lab. School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. - EY: Redefining Research Excellence: Predictive study on future transversal skills for researchers - EY: The Essential Role of Transversal Skills in the Academic-Industry Transition - LUISS: Luiss's Transition Towards Open Science: A Look at the Italian Landscape
Media Relations	Social Media networks and a	3 social media	<p>Linkedin: https://www.linkedin.com/company/c</p>

	YouTube channel will be used to host the videos and audio-visual material	accounts and 1 YouTube account	atalisi-project X: https://x.com/catalisiproject Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/catalisiproject/ Zenodo with sister projects: https://zenodo.org/communities/acceleration_services/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest YouTube account: https://www.youtube.com/@catalisiproject
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Table 6: Project KPIs

All planned KPIs related to communication and dissemination were **successfully met**, with several exceeding their targets.

3.2. MONITORING SPREADSHEET

A monitoring system was established with the aim: to regularly track and follow the outreach measurements defined in the communication and dissemination plan; to identify the effectiveness of the outreach and dissemination activities and to adjust the strategy if required. An excel file (hosted in the projects' internal SharePoint), regularly updated by all consortium partners. Its goal was to summarise and track systematically all C&D activities carried out, the events organised and the number and typology of audiences reached. It is available in the shared project space and contains the following tabs: Internal events, Events of interest, Communication report, Dissemination reporting, Opinion articles, Webinars.

The sheet was supplemented with monthly WP reporting and impact monitoring meetings with all partners, led by F6S. This monitoring spreadsheet was a living document and as such, all consortium partners were encouraged and reminded to keep track of each dissemination and communication activity (and the audience reached whenever possible) as they took place. The monitoring tool was designed to meet the EC requirements for project promotion and dissemination of results and filling it in is mandatory for mid-term and final reporting (part A of the Technical Report). For this reason, it has been developed following the new [Horizon Europe reporting template and includes](#):

- A sheet with guidelines for filling in the spreadsheet
- A sheet for events of interest
- A sheet for reporting internal events such as webinars, success stories, and MML/Twinning exchanges
- A sheet for reporting on all communication activities and the target audiences
- A sheet for reporting on all dissemination activities and the target audiences
- A sheet for Opinion articles and topics
- A sheet for success stories webinars

Figure 71: Monitoring spreadsheet tool, live document (print screens)

4. EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLANS

Exploitation and sustainability planning were developed in parallel throughout the CATALISI project because they are inherently interconnected and mutually reinforcing. Exploitation focuses on ensuring that project results are actively used and generate value, while sustainability guarantees their continuity and evolution beyond the project's lifecycle. For this reason, they are presented under the same section of the D5.2, even though each has its own dedicated chapters.

The exploitation and sustainability efforts in CATALISI come as a result of Task 5.4 Exploitation activities and preparation, aiming at ensuring the results and methodologies developed within CATALISI are effectively exploited by Higher Education Institutions, policymakers, and other stakeholders. This task was focused on preparing a structured plan for the uptake, replication, and sustainability of project outcomes beyond the project's lifetime. On its turn, the sustainability and exploitation plan goal is to facilitate the acceptance of CATALISI and a strong uptake and utilisation by HEIs, SMEs and stakeholders of the results. On another hand, ensure compatibility and interoperability with what already exists as a tool for dissemination of the project results and interaction with key enabling stakeholders.

The exploitation strategy of CATALISI was designed in the first year of the project implementation. It comprised different phases as explained further in the document and was periodically updated in consultation with the project partners.

4.1. SUSTAINABILITY IN THE FRAMEWORK OF CATALISI

Since the project start, the sustainability of the results and outputs was ensured by:

- Engagement of the project partners in the co-design process of the acceleration services and the developed tools.
- Constant evaluation and incorporating of the implementers' feedback into the acceleration services to adjust them to the context and specific needs.
- Providing continuous support and building capacity of the implementers to initiate, plan, organize, conduct the use of acceleration services independently with minimum or no help needed on behalf of the facilitators after the project end.
- Providing lasting resources and tools (e.g. CATALYST Hub, Community of Practice, etc.) supporting the institutional transformation adapted to the HEIs' needs and expectations.

Highlights:

In terms of **ensuring the continuity** of the CATALISI legacy, the responsible partners (F6S and APRE with the support of the other project partners) made sure that:

- The **project website** will remain active and will be maintained for 5 years after the project's end (by F6S) - in this way making sure that access to all project resources and tools is still freely available through the online platform **CATALYST Hub**.
- The project partners built a **strong network** of HEIs and supporting facilitators that will stay connected after the project end.
- The **Community of practice** (CoP) will continue to exist as independent from the project group of experts and practitioners, committed to remaining engaged and available after the project end, in support of all interested parties, but also as a dynamic online based collaboration environment that is self-driven.
- The connections with **synergy projects**, initiatives and teams of professionals will continue to reflect the striving for cooperation and desire for mutual growth, evidenced by the signing of the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with 8 synergy projects.
- The project resources (incl. Deliverables, publications, etc.) will remain available through the **open access** platforms, such as Zenodo.
- The partners will finalise the preparation of **case studies and success stories** (real life examples) for inclusion in the final reports and deliverables, and available on the project website for all interested parties.
- The **collaboration mechanisms** extend beyond the CATALISI website and consortium, by leveraging the opportunities provided by the F6S platform with more than 5 mil. registered users and potential cooperation and/or business partners who can be reached out for: valorisation of HEIs research results (offering services provided by the HEIs to the business); invitation to participate in new project proposals (business to academia cooperation); funding support for research and development activities, etc.
- Policy uptake and long-term impact is ensured by the CATALISI Policy Recommendation (ER13), as well as the Joint policy brief of the 3 sister projects: CATALISI, aUPaEU and AccelerateFutureHEI;
- An active usage of the most optimal ways and channels for storage and dissemination of the project materials is at place, including provision under open access to ensure that the dissemination outputs created will be permanently (or as necessary) available and accessible for the different stakeholder groups.
- Assessing the opportunities linked to the Horizon Results Platform, including drafting and publishing the appropriate Horizon Results Platform profile (a common approach at consortium level).

CATALISI Sustainability Plan:

The CATALISI Sustainability Plan was developed to ensure that the project's achievements extend well beyond its lifecycle and continue to generate impact across the European Higher Education landscape. Designed as a strategic roadmap, the plan outlines concrete measures to institutionalize transformation practices, maintain digital resources, and foster collaboration among universities, policymakers, and industry actors. The following sections detail the key pillars of this strategy and the steps required for their implementation.

1. Institutional Anchoring of Acceleration Services

- Integrate the CATALISI acceleration services like Living Labs, Counselling, Transformational Pathway, etc. into the strategic frameworks and operational plans of participating HEIs.
- Establish permanent structures (e.g. transformation offices, innovation hubs) to continue delivering these services post-project.

- Encourage HEIs to adopt internal policies that embed transformation pathways into governance, research, and education missions.

2. Catalyst Hub Continuity

- Maintain and expand the Catalyst Hub as a digital platform for collaboration, funding access, and peer learning (as a minimum of 5 years after the project ends, maintained by F6S and APRE).
- Consideration of transition of ownership or stewardship of the platform to a consortium of HEIs or a university alliance to ensure long-term maintenance (after that period of 5 years post-project is over).
- Regularly update content and tools to reflect evolving policy agendas and funding opportunities, as well as uploading new training contents as available.
- Linkage of the Catalyst Hub with other platforms and networks existing beyond the CATALISI project, e.g.: *F6S* platform, *Agora* platform, etc.
- Take advantage of the collaboration and opportunities provided by the *ERA* platform: <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/>. After the end of the project, the PC will share with CATALISI Project and Policy officers at the EC, relevant materials to be uploaded in this platform (so that to be further disseminated, sustained and exploited).
- Consideration and negotiation (by the PC) of the possibility of adding a link/connection in the *ERA* platform that redirect to the Catalyst Hub.

3. Community of Practice (CoP) Expansion

- Formalize the CoP as a standing network of HEI transformation experts, with annual convenings and thematic working groups.
- Develop an institutional partnership framework to support ongoing participation and knowledge exchange (signed Memorandums of Understanding and possible rotation of the responsibility).
- Promote the CoP as a resource for new HEIs seeking guidance on transformation, fostering a ripple effect across the sector.

4. Resource Mobilisation Strategy

- Support HEIs in developing investment strategies to access diverse funding streams (EU programs, national grants, private sector).
- Provide toolkits and training to enhance institutional capacity for proposal writing, partnership building, and financial planning.
- Advocate for alignment with European Research Area (ERA) priorities to increase eligibility and policy support.
- Use the success stories and case studies to demonstrate impact and attract future investment.

5. Policy Integration and Advocacy

- Translate project insights into policy briefs and recommendations for national and EU-level stakeholders. The joint policy brief (with sister projects) also acts as a multiplier for CATALISI's sustainability. It embeds its results into a broader European narrative, increases policy relevance, strengthens stakeholder buy-in, and ensures continuity of exploitation efforts beyond the project's end.
- Engage with policymakers to embed CATALISI principles into future funding calls, university evaluation frameworks, and innovation agendas.
- Position HEIs as key actors in regional development and societal resilience through strategic policy dialogue.

6. Replication and Scale-Up

- Use the comprehensive joint dissemination roadmap developed with the sister projects (at cluster level with the support of the Horizon Booster) to leverage partner networks, channels, and resources to maximize the visibility and impact of project outcomes.
- Active usage of the developed custom dissemination materials (incl. with the sister projects, e.g. the joint branding, the joined video, etc.) tailored to specific audiences, for targeted continuing KER-based dissemination of the results.
- Package CATALISI methodologies and tools into open-access resources for replication by non-partner HEIs.
- Promote MML, twinning and mentoring programs by the project partners to support institutions at earlier stages of transformation.
- Explore opportunities to scale the replicable framework through Erasmus+ partnerships, Horizon Europe clusters, or regional innovation ecosystems.

4.2. METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS FOR PROJECT EXPLOITATION

The exploitation strategy of CATALISI was built on a structured methodology designed to ensure that project outputs are identified, validated, and transformed into actionable benefits for diverse stakeholders. This approach combined systematic preparation activities with practical tools to maximize uptake and sustainability.

Scope of Exploitation

Some of the **milestone goals** of the overall exploitation and sustainability of the CATALISI project and results identified and pursued by the consortium were:

1. **Institutional Integration:** Embedding / adopting acceleration services (Living Lab, Counselling, Transformational Pathway) into HEI governance structures.
2. **Knowledge Transfer:** Ensuring that frameworks, tools, and methodologies are accessible and adaptable to other institutions.
3. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Involving policymakers, industry, and civil society to maximize impact.
4. **Capacity Building:** Training and supporting HEIs to continue transformation efforts and actions independently.

The preparation activities (such as mapping exploitable results, conducting strategy workshops, and engaging stakeholders) served as the foundation for launching the process. These actions informed the stages of the exploitation strategy, which included identifying outputs, validating their relevance, and defining pathways for uptake, while simultaneously shaping sustainability measures to embed these outputs into institutional frameworks and long-term structures.

1. **Mapping of Results:** Identification of exploitable outputs

A comprehensive mapping exercise was conducted to identify all exploitable outputs generated during the project using the planned key expected results as a basis. Each output was assessed for relevance, scalability, and potential impact beyond the consortium.

In this stage the methods and tools to support the consortium in identifying and confirming the project results and the KERs were:

- Workshops with partners to present the exploitation strategy to be followed (organized by F6S, online, June 2024)
- Focus on the identification of the results and aligning behind the KERs

- Exploitation questionnaire distributed to partners for getting initial input on results, background information, foreground information, interest for exploiting the results (both individually and jointly) (developed by F6S, filled in by all PPs)
- Analysis of the results and creation of a results table (implemented by F6S)
- Discussion with partners to review the results, discuss approaches and plan next steps (led by F6S during the monthly meetings)
- Exploitation Workshop for Results Validation (April 2025, online)

The analysis of exploitation assets began with the list of expected key results generated through the implementation of the project:

CATALISI Expected Results

- ER1. 1 replicable framework of acceleration services
- ER2. 1 coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various areas
- ER3. 1 Market Place
- ER4. 1 methodology for an investment strategy that facilitates the access of HEIs and surrounding ecosystems' access to resources that will support the delivery of the chosen institutional transformations.
- ER5. 7 Individual strategy and agenda setting elaborated to support a long term sustainable institutional transformation.
- ER6. 7 acting Living labs that support the institutional transformation established
- ER7. 7 Action-plan to support the utilization of acceleration services
- ER8. 1 Predictive Study
- ER9. 1 Learning hub realized
- ER10. 1 model for mutual knowledge sharing among the implementers
- ER11. 1 Community of practices to build a consensus building on institutional transformation
- ER12. At least 10 Collaboration established with other European initiatives
- ER13. 1 Policy Recommendation
- ER14. 7 comparable case studies

This served as the foundation for identifying which outcomes held potential for further development and impact beyond the project's lifetime. By systematically reviewing the expected results, the consortium was able to distinguish between outputs that could be classified as Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and those that represented specific deliverables with limited exploitation potential. This initial step ensured that the exploitation strategy was firmly anchored in the project's tangible achievements, while also providing a structured basis for prioritizing resources, tailoring support activities, and aligning exploitation pathways with the broader objectives of sustainability and long-term value creation.

The next step was to mobilize the project partners as key representatives of the project stakeholders and potential target groups for uptake of the project outputs in translating the expected results into Key Exploitable Results. A first attempt was done to group them together by type of results:

Acceleration Services	
ER1. 1 replicable framework of acceleration services	
ER7. 7 Action-plan to support the utilization of acceleration services	Exploitation path
ER3. 1 Market Place	KER
ER2. 1 coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various areas	KER
ER8. 1 Predictive Study	KER
ER9. 1 Learning hub realized	KER
ER6. 7 acting Living labs	KER
ER10. 1 model for mutual knowledge sharing among the implementers	KER
ER4. 1 methodology for an investment strategy that facilitates the access of HEIs and surrounding ecosystems' access to resources that will support the delivery of the chosen institutional transformations.	Not sure
ER5. 7 Individual strategy and agenda setting elaborated to support a long term sustainable institutional transformation.	Not sure
ER14. 7 comparable case studies	KER
ER13. 1 Policy Recommendation	KER
ER11. 1 Community of practices to build a consensus building on institutional transformation	KER
ER12. At least 10 Collaboration established with other European initiatives	Not KER - outcome

Figure 72: Grouping the CATALISI project results and assessing possible exploitation potential (working in progress situation in early 2024)

Following these steps, the first Exploitation Workshop was held during the General Assembly in February 2024. A detailed explanation of the exploitation purpose and goals was given by the exploitation lead F6S, while the partners were invited to brainstorm around the usability and replicability potential of the key expected results from the project. The chosen approach aimed at introducing the exploitation concept to the partners and preliminary assessment of the possible exploitation pathways.

I would also mention the ERA platform: <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/>. After the end of the project, we will share with our Project and Policy officers at the EC, some relevant materials to be uploaded in this platform (so that to be further disseminated, sustained and maybe exploited). We are also thinking if it would be possible to add a link/connection in this platform that redirect to the Catalyst Hub. From the 14 key Expected Results (ER) during this session, the consortium have identified **4 preliminary Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** grouped as follows:

- Group 1 - Acceleration Services
- Group 2 - Knowledge Sharing
- Group 3 - Policy Recommendation
- Group 4 - Community of Practice

This exercise moderated by F6S allowed the project partners to start thinking from the “what's next” perspective and value the results of the project that are not only one-time delivered/achieved but also will last in the time and will provide further support and assistance in pursuing the institutions' transformation goals.

Figure 73: CATALISI, General Assembly, Exploitation workshop, January 2024

2. Exploitation Strategy Workshops: Internal sessions with consortium partners to define pathways for uptake (during stage 2)

Internal workshops were organized with consortium partners to define clear pathways for uptake. These sessions facilitated alignment between institutional priorities and project objectives, ensuring that exploitation plans were both realistic and impactful.

With the start of the second phase the exploitation lead organized and conducted a series of online workshops (2 for implementers and 1 for facilitators) in which the initial list was again reviewed and each expected result was further evaluated against its limitations and potential, value proposition and strategic positioning. For this, a supporting tool was developed and provided by F6S to collect the attitudes, expectations and preferences of the project partners, as well as their capacity, opportunities and future plans in terms of exploitation of the project results. The questionnaire (*Annex 4_CATALISI Exploitation Questionnaire*) was filled in by all project partners (implementors and facilitators) and outlined the priorities and readiness of the project partners (and especially the potential KERs' owners) to take up the responsibility and ownership over the results and commit to certain exploitation efforts.

The analysis of the replies to the survey was implemented by F6S and discussed in the next consortium online coordination meeting. Further revisit of the potential KERs changed the approach as the consortium decided to focus on the exploitation assets with the highest potential and put explicit efforts in their conceptualization and further exploitation.

Another aspect that was considered was related to the sustainability of the exploitable results and in addition to the assessment of the exploitation potential and capacity, an effort for establishing strategic alliances was done. Such an alliance was built for example by leveraging from the proposed by our sister project aUPaEU opportunity to build a page in the Agora platform they developed for university alliances' support.

As a result of this stage, **three Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** were identified as having the greatest potential for further exploitation and were subsequently presented to the Booster as outlined below:

- (KER1) Multi-level knowledge sharing service strengthening HEI international competitiveness and achieving institutional reforms - owned by APRE
- (KER2) Coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various research areas - owned by EY
- (KER3) Living Lab Methodology for Institutional Transformation: A Practical Guide to Becoming a Living Lab - owned by ENoLL.

3. Characterisation of the selected KERs:

This stage was implemented for the identified three KERs with the highest potential for exploitation and with the support of the Horizon Booster. During this process, the KERs' owners supported by the Horizon Booster expert and with the facilitation of the exploitation lead F6S focused on:

- Identifying the specific UVP (unique value proposition) of each key result
- Exploring alternative solutions and highlighting unique selling points
- Assessing competitors and evaluating the potential market to strategically position the results
- Identifying usage options and conducting a risk assessment

The process of cooperation with the assigned experts, the work done by the partners as well as the outcomes of this stage are explained in detail in **section 4.6** below.

Although only several partners (APRE, EY, ENoLL and F6S) were directly involved in the exploitation capacity building sessions offered by the Horizon Booster, the results and lessons learnt were shared with all project partners during the regular monthly coordination meetings, and also the universities participating in CATALISI were actively involved in validating the relevance and applicability of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs). As potential future users of these outputs, their feedback was essential to ensure that the methodologies, tools, and resources developed during the project aligned with real institutional needs and can be effectively integrated into governance and operational frameworks. This collaborative validation process informed refinements to the exploitation strategy and strengthened its practical value for Higher Education Institutions.

This methodology ensured that exploitation was not an afterthought but an integral part of project design. By combining structured planning with stakeholder engagement and sustainability measures, CATALISI created a robust foundation for long-term impact and replication across the European Higher Education sector.

4.3. KEY EXPLOITABLE ASSETS AND RESULTS (KER)

The table below represents the results from the joint exploration of the project expected results and their exploitation potential. As mentioned, the consortium conducted a critical analysis and assessed the interest, readiness and ability of the partners to explore the project results, thus outlining **3 main KERs** to be developed further into individual exploitation plans of the KERs' owners.

Table 7: CATALISI Key exploitable assets and results

Type	Expected key results:	Tangible Results	Exploitable assets	Potential users
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Acceleration services	ER1. 1 replicable framework of acceleration services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mini-report (10 pages approx.) aiming to provide a tested, scalable and flexible approach that supports HEIs to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strategically embed transformation in HEIs ○ Align institutional efforts with EU policy priorities ○ Enable participatory decision making in HEIs ○ Facilitate peer learning and cross-institutional support ● Factsheet developed by F6S (with APRE support) starting from the mini-report. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A document / report (freely accessible and available on the project website) ● An exploitation pathway for using the project result (framework), outlining the stages and steps to be followed by the stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project partners ● HEIs and academic institutions pursuing institutional transformation ● University governance ● Innovation and strategic planning units, etc.
	ER7. 7 Action-plan to support the utilization of acceleration services	7 action plans developed and implemented by the implementers (HEI partners) in practice with the support of the facilitators.	7 documents developed and periodically updated	Project HEIs partners
	ER2. 1 coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various areas (WP3)	D3.1: Coaching and mentoring methodology	KER2: Coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various research areas (owned by EY)	KER owned by EY As described in the KER Characterisation table
	ER6. 7 acting Living labs that support the institutional transformation established (WP1)	D1.3: Acting-LLs evaluation report	KER3: Living Lab Methodology for Institutional Transformation : A Practical	KER owned by ENoLL As described in the KER Characterisation

			Guide to Becoming a Living Lab (owned by ENoLL)	table
ER8. 1 Predictive Study	D3.3 - Predictive study on skills anticipation		1 document, publicly accessible on the project website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project partners • HEIs and academic institutions • Individual practitioners, experts or academia representatives • Wide audience, etc.
ER3. 1 Market Place	The CATALYST Hub (formerly called Marketplace) is an online platform designed and structured to host all project resources while providing opportunities for funding and collaboration. Embedded within the project website, the Hub is organized into three main sections, each aligned with specific functionalities and tasks: learning , funding , and collaboration opportunities .		The Catalyst Hub as a platform itself.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project partners • HEIs and academic institutions • Individual practitioners, experts or academia representatives • Wide audience, etc.
ER9. 1 Learning hub realized			Learning hub (online repository of training and supporting materials) embedded into the CATALYST Hub and freely accessible.	
ER11. 1 Community of practices to build a consensus building on institutional transformation			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A database of individual experts, practitioners and other individuals involved and interested in the project topics (managed by the PC - APRE) • CoP members (who 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project partners • HEIs and academic institutions pursuing institutional transformation • University governance • Innovation and strategic planning units, etc. • Individual practitioners,

			provided consent) are presented on the project website in the Cooperation section of the CATALYST Hub and can be contacted based on the matching criteria	experts or academia representatives
Result	ER4. 1 methodology for an investment strategy that facilitates the access of HEIs and surrounding ecosystems' access to resources that will support the delivery of the chosen institutional transformations.	Included (as a chapter) in the D5.2 Final DCE and sustainability plans publicly accessible on the project website	1 methodology for an investment strategy that facilitates the access of HEIs and surrounding ecosystems' access to resources that will support the delivery of the chosen institutional transformations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Partner HEIs ● Other HEIs external to the project and consortium
Result	ER5. 7 Individual strategy and agenda setting elaborated to support a long term sustainable institutional transformation.	7 documents developed and periodically updated	D3.2 – Collection of transformational pathways	Project HEIs partners
Result	ER10. 1 model for mutual knowledge sharing among the implementers (WP2)	1 document publicly accessible on the project website: CATALISI Replicable Framework of Acceleration Services (A methodological pathway for institutional transformation in Higher Education Institutions.)	KER 1: Multi-level knowledge sharing service strengthening HEI international competitiveness and achieving institutional	KER owned by APRE As described in the KER Characterisation table

			reforms (owned by APRE)	
Result	ER12. At least 10 Collaboration established with other European initiatives	Project synergies established and 10 signed MoU agreements with sister and synergy projects	Informal network of collaborating actors in support of HEIs' institutional transformation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CATALISI consortium ● Sister and synergy projects, ● Other interested project, initiatives and institutions in joining the network
Document	ER13. 1 Policy Recommendation	1 document, publicly accessible on the project website: D6.3 – Final Policy brief	D6.3 – Final Policy brief	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policy makers, ● HEIs' governance ● Authorities: EU and national / regional authorities in the education sector, etc.
Result	ER14. 7 comparable case studies	<p>7 case studies accompanied by success stories and presented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In a booklet with the "story" of each CATALISI HEI partner, incl. challenges, pathways and achievements; ● On the project website as a learning materials for other HEIs to inspire and learn from the experience of the CATALISI implementers. <p>Additional information provided in D4.2: Monitoring and Implementation Report (including impact assessment tool</p>	Printed and online version of the CATALISI booklets - for physical and virtual distribution, supporting the dissemination efforts after the end of the project and making the project lessons learnt and best practices accessible to wide audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project partners ● HEIs and academic institutions pursuing institutional transformation ● University governance ● Innovation and strategic planning units ● Wide audience, etc.

		kit) in relation to evaluation and impact assessment (UCC).		
Document	Joined policy briefs with sister projects (not foreseen in the GA)	A result of the early sister projects cooperation and efforts for alignment of the findings and recommendations. Two documents jointly developed by AccelerateFutureHEI, CATALISI and aUPaEU.	2 documents: <i>First</i> joined policy brief: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First delivery: December 2023; • Revised in May 2024. <i>Second</i> joined policy brief: delivered in November 2025.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU and Member States; • Policymakers; • Universities

4.4. COLLECTIVE ACTIONS TO EXPLOIT ASSETS AND MAXIMISE VALUE

To ensure the long-term impact of CATALISI beyond the project lifecycle, participating universities and partners committed to **collective actions** that leverage shared assets, knowledge, and networks. These actions aim to maximize the value created during the project and embed transformation practices into institutional strategies. The approach focuses on collaboration rather than isolated efforts, enabling synergies across Higher Education Institutions and their ecosystems.

Key components include:

1. Shared Access to Resources and Tools

Partners will continue to utilize and expand the resources available through the Catalyst Hub, including training materials, methodologies, and best-practice guidelines, at their best capacity and in line with their strategic priorities. This effort is aimed at ensuring that the knowledge generated during the project remains accessible and actionable, while acknowledging that its application will depend on each partner's internal policies, priorities, and strategic decisions.

2. Joint Development of Funding Strategies

Universities will collaborate on identifying and pursuing funding opportunities through the Catalyst Hub and based on shared interests and the collaborations established during the project. This collective approach accelerates resource mobilization and strengthens the financial sustainability of transformation initiatives.

3. Knowledge Exchange and Capacity Building

Through living labs, MMLs, and twinning exchanges, HEIs will maintain active knowledge-sharing practices. These initiatives foster innovation, support continuous professional development, and encourage the adoption of proven strategies across institutions.

4. Pooling Expertise for Strategic Impact

By leveraging individual and institutional expertise (incl. The CATALISI CoP pool of practitioners), partners will co-create solutions to address common challenges, align research with national and regional innovation policies, and enhance the overall quality of outputs. To ensure the community remains active, engagement will be supported through light-touch coordination (e.g. any new applications for joining the CoP will be added to the contact database, incl. F6S will publish the profiles of experts who chose to be publicly showcased on the project website), streamlined communication channels such as the established LinkedIn group for the CoP members, and the integration of community activities into existing institutional routines.

5. Network Continuity and Expansion

The established R&I networks will be maintained and progressively expanded to include new stakeholders from academia, industry, and policymaking, ensuring that collaboration remains dynamic and responsive to emerging needs. To support continuity with minimal additional effort, partners will be encouraged to continue to invite relevant contacts to join the community, facilitate introductions between their network members and the wider group, and share opportunities for engagement through their existing communication channels.

4.4.1. Exploitation Pathways

To extend the impact of CATALISI beyond the immediate project partners and ensure broad uptake of its results, the project has investigated and outlined exploitation pathways that guarantee its outputs deliver value across multiple stakeholder groups and continue to generate impact beyond the project lifecycle. These pathways are designed to translate project achievements into actionable benefits for Higher Education Institutions, policymakers, industry actors, society, and European networks. By doing so, CATALISI not only secures the sustainability of its outcomes but also fosters systemic change across the European Higher Education Area.

- **For Higher Education Institutions:** Adoption of governance models and acceleration services.

The adoption of governance models and acceleration services developed during CATALISI provides universities with structured mechanisms to **embed transformation into their core strategies**. These models enable HEIs to strengthen decision-making processes, improve resource mobilization, and foster innovation ecosystems that support long-term competitiveness. However, their full uptake will remain at the discretion of each partner university, depending on internal priorities, policies, and strategic considerations.

- **For Policymakers:** Policy recommendations aligned with ERA priorities.

Policy recommendations and briefs produced within the project (and in collaboration with the sister projects) are aligned with European Research Area (ERA) priorities, offering actionable insights to guide national and regional strategies. By leveraging these recommendations, policymakers can promote systemic change, enhance research alignment with societal needs, and support the modernization of higher education governance.

- **For Industry and Society:** Collaboration opportunities through involvement in co-creation, Living Labs and regional empowerment initiatives.

Living Labs and regional empowerment initiatives are creating new collaboration opportunities between academia, industry, and civil society. These platforms encourage co-creation, accelerate knowledge transfer, and stimulate innovation-driven solutions to societal challenges, reinforcing the role of HEIs as engines of regional development. In addition, the presence of all partners on the F6S platform strengthens this commitment by providing a shared digital space where universities can connect with businesses, identify potential collaborators, and stay informed about key events and opportunities related to knowledge transfer and innovation. This enables partners to expand their networks with minimal additional effort while maintaining active engagement with industry and societal stakeholders.

- **For EU Networks and Alliances:** Replication potential across alliances and European consortia.

The methodologies and tools developed under CATALISI have strong replication potential across European consortia and university alliances. Such as: twinning mechanism within Erasmus+ and staff exchange; Living Labs in the Era Action 7 on knowledge valorisation; framework for acceleration service at EC level and so on. By adopting these frameworks, networks can scale transformation practices, harmonize governance approaches, and contribute to the broader objectives of the European Higher Education Area.

These exploitation pathways demonstrate how CATALISI's outputs transcend the boundaries of the consortium, creating a foundation for systemic impact. By addressing the needs of HEIs, policymakers, industry, and EU networks, the project ensures that its legacy is embedded in future collaborations, policy frameworks, and institutional strategies.

4.4.2. Partner Benefits from Exploitation and Sustainability

The exploitation strategy ensures that all partners derive tangible and strategic benefits from the assets and knowledge generated during CATALISI. These benefits are structured around three key dimensions:

1. Strategic Positioning

- *Visibility of institutional innovations and transformation models*
Partners gain recognition for their pioneering approaches to institutional transformation, showcasing best practices and innovative models developed during the project.
- *Enhanced reputation through Horizon Results Booster engagement*
Active participation in Horizon Results Booster activities strengthens the visibility of partners at the European level, positioning them as leaders in research and innovation policy alignment.

2. Future Opportunities

- *Utilization of CATALISI outputs for ongoing initiatives*
Resources such as the Learning Hub and Cooperation Section remain accessible, enabling partners to integrate these tools into future projects and capacity-building efforts.
- *Foundation for new collaborations and funding proposals*
The networks and methodologies established during CATALISI serve as a springboard

for joint proposals, partnerships, and participation in upcoming EU and national funding schemes.

3. Ownership & Impact

- *Individual exploitation plans empower partners*
Each partner retains autonomy to pursue tailored exploitation pathways, ensuring alignment with institutional priorities and long-term strategies.
- *Joint plan ensures collective legacy and EU alignment*
The shared exploitation framework within the consortium guarantees coherence across partners, reinforcing the collective impact and alignment with European Research Area objectives.

4.5. INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLANS

Following the cycle adopted throughout the project implementation—planning, consultation, initial implementation, monitoring and evaluation, assessment of results, corrective measures and plan updates, and subsequent implementation cycles—the universities participating in CATALISI have drafted their sustainability plans. These sustainability plans will serve as a roadmap to ensure the long-term impact of institutional transformation initiatives, embed best practices into core operations, and guide future strategic actions beyond the project's lifecycle.

The individual sustainability paths as identified by the university partners in CATALISI were included in another project document, namely Deliverable D3.2 Collection of transformational pathways. The deliverable reviews the CATALISI model by exploring the transformational pathways design methodology, the domains and intervention areas, the acceleration services designed and implemented within the project, etc. Further, the report reveals the individual transformational pathways of the university-implementers, developed with CATALISI facilitators and stakeholders, and represents a living document, updated to reflect new goals, feedback, evolving priorities, and demonstrates the progress toward institutional transformation. It describes the journey of each university from their first action and its updates, each stage followed by evaluation. From the sustainability perspective D3.2 is important as it also includes the implementers' adaptation strategy for their transformational pathway for the post-project period 2026-2028, as well as the planned sustainability measures by each university partner.

Below, we present a **consolidated overview** of the sustainability measures proposed by the universities as they are presented in D3.2:

Kaunas University of Technology (KTU)

KTU has developed a set of sustainability measures, informed by guidance from the External Advisory Board (EAB) and project facilitators, to ensure its transformational pathway continues beyond the project's formal end. These measures align with post-project activities and incorporate best practices and lessons learned. By embedding them into its long-term strategy, KTU aims to secure lasting institutional change and maintain the benefits achieved through CATALISI.

To ensure that the achievements of its transformational pathway continue beyond the project's lifetime, KTU has committed to a comprehensive set of sustainability measures across multiple intervention areas. In the field of talent circulation and mobility, the university

plans to embed mobility activities into academic assessment frameworks, establish long-term international partnerships, diversify funding sources, and strengthen knowledge-sharing practices. Blended mobility and ongoing virtual collaboration will further support continuity after physical exchanges end.

In strengthening human capital, KTU aims to build internal capacity by training staff and senior researchers as mentors, establishing peer-support mechanisms, and developing a digital repository of resources to ensure lasting access to guidance and tools. Incentive systems and integration of writing support into PhD training will help embed these practices into the broader research lifecycle.

For public engagement and societal outreach, KTU will cultivate long-term partnerships with community actors, enhance recognition for citizen scientists, and ensure transparency through open data practices. A strengthened digital platform will support continuous citizen involvement, while diversified funding and targeted capacity building will help sustain the Citizen Science ecosystem. The establishment of a long-term Living Lab structure will further anchor collaboration between citizens, researchers, local authorities, and industry.

Across all intervention areas, KTU plans to formally integrate key actions—such as mobility initiatives, mentoring systems, peer-review structures, and the Citizen Science hub—into institutional strategies to secure long-term support. The university also intends to develop fully operational Living Labs, introduce a structured stakeholder engagement framework, and maintain internal capacity-building programmes. Finally, KTU will leverage its expanded networks and strengthened institutional capabilities to mobilize new resources through Horizon Europe, regional development funds, and partnerships with municipalities and industry, ensuring sustained impact well beyond the CATALISI project.

Aristotele University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

AUTH's sustainability framework builds directly on the EAB's recommendation to strengthen the integration of project outcomes into the university's governance and long-term strategic planning. The approach is designed to ensure that the achievements of the transformational pathway are institutionally embedded and continue to generate impact well beyond the project's duration.

A key element of this framework is institutional integration, with activities such as skills certification and FAIR data training becoming part of AUTH's regular operations, coordinated by the Medical School's Laboratory of Digital Innovation and the IT Department. This is complemented by strong policy alignment, linking AUTH's actions to national higher education priorities and major European initiatives like ERA and EOSC, thereby ensuring strategic coherence and access to future funding opportunities.

To secure long-term continuity, AUTH is also establishing dedicated structures, including a FAIR Data Office and a permanent Task Force on Educational Digitisation and Citizen Science. These bodies will maintain and update resources, certifications, and training programmes. Finally, sustained stakeholder engagement is ensured through long-term collaboration with civil society, academic partners, and business stakeholders, supported by annual co-creation forums and formal cooperation agreements.

University College Cork (UCC)

UCC's sustainability measures have been designed to secure the long-term impact of its transformational pathway, drawing directly on the guidance and best practices provided by the EAB and project facilitators. By integrating these insights into its operational strategy, the

university aims to maintain momentum, strengthen institutional resilience, and ensure that the benefits of the project continue well into the future.

A central component of this approach is the implementation of a revised overhead model across the institution, overseen by the Vice-President for Research and Innovation. UCC has also strengthened its internal structures by appointing a Head of Research Culture, Engagement and Impact, ensuring dedicated leadership for ongoing cultural and strategic development.

In addition, UCC is leveraging the CATALISI Acceleration Services methodology, which contributed to securing a Wellcome Trust Fund for engaged research and research culture. The university's dual role as both implementer and facilitator has also deepened its expertise in evaluation and impact assessment, enabling it to apply these competencies to other initiatives.

Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC)

AUMC has developed a set of sustainability measures designed to embed the outcomes of its transformational pathway into long-term institutional practice. Informed by the guidance of the EAB and project facilitators, these measures aim to reinforce the progress achieved during the project and ensure that its benefits continue to grow in the years ahead. By integrating these actions into its organisational structures, AUMC is positioning itself for lasting cultural and operational change.

A key component of this sustainability plan is the long-term implementation of the *Empowering Responsible Supervision* training. In collaboration with the doctoral school, AUMC will make this programme a mandatory requirement for all supervisors, with full rollout and scaling planned from spring 2026. Complementing this, the theatre play *Science Hoops*—developed to stimulate a positive research culture—will be performed multiple times in 2026 and made available on demand for departments seeking tools to facilitate discussions on research culture.

Another major pillar is the continued operation of the RIOS (Research Integrity and Open Science) Center, established through CATALISI. The center will remain a permanent structure staffed with dedicated personnel who support initiatives related to responsible conduct of research and the promotion of a positive research culture. With secured funding for the coming years at VU, RIOS will continue organising network meetings, Communities of Practice, and targeted activities that strengthen research integrity across the institution.

Universitat Jaume I (UJI)

UJI has established a strong sustainability framework to ensure that the outcomes of its transformational pathway continue well beyond the CATALISI project. Central to this approach is the integration of reforms into two multi-year institutional action plans running through 2027: the CoARA-UJI Action Plan on research assessment reform and the ENCA-UJI Open Science Action Plan. Both plans have been formally approved by the UJI Governing Council and published in three languages, ensuring institutional commitment, transparency, and broad uptake across the university community.

The CoARA-UJI plan provides a structured roadmap for implementation, outlining objectives, governance mechanisms, and a participatory approach that aligns UJI with European and national reform processes. Because these plans are officially endorsed and publicly registered, they remain binding commitments regardless of leadership changes, including the 2026 election cycle. This institutional anchoring ensures continuity, clear deliverables, and ongoing accountability.

To reinforce sustainability in the area of career recognition and research ethics, UJI will maintain continuity within its governance structures by retaining two CATALISI team members in key roles. Their ongoing involvement ensures consistent implementation, monitoring, and alignment with established codes and procedures. Together, the formal institutionalization of policy frameworks and the stability of operational leadership create a robust foundation for sustaining UJI's reforms through 2026–2028 and beyond.

Luiss Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli (LUISS)

LUISS has put in place a set of sustainability measures to ensure that the institutional transformation initiated through CATALISI continues well beyond the project's lifetime. The university is embedding the most impactful elements of the Action Plan into its long-term strategic and operational structures, particularly in the areas of research excellence, talent attraction, Open Science, and the Third Mission. Key institutional units, such as the Research and Third Mission Office, will continue to play a central role in supporting and institutionalising these practices.

Looking ahead, LUISS will evaluate how selected actions can be consolidated, adapted, or scaled in line with evolving strategic priorities. Progress will be monitored through indicators such as external research funding, the number of funded projects, participation in national and international networks, and the strengthening of Open Science practices. By maintaining this momentum and ensuring continuity, LUISS aims to transform successful project-driven initiatives into long-term structural improvements.

University of GDANSK (UG)

The University of Gdańsk has developed a comprehensive set of sustainability measures to ensure that the transformation initiated through CATALISI continues well beyond the project's duration. These measures reflect the university's commitment to integrating EAB recommendations and facilitator insights into its long-term strategy. By embedding lessons learned and best practices into its operational framework, UG aims to secure lasting impact and support the continued growth of its transformation pathway.

The planned activities for 2026–2028 form a systemic and forward-looking foundation for sustainability. Strengthening cooperation with external stakeholders—particularly the business sector—will support ongoing knowledge transfer, stable research partnerships, and opportunities for student engagement. Collaboration with local government institutions in supervising master's theses further embeds UG within the regional ecosystem and ensures that educational and research activities respond to local needs.

UG also plans to deepen stakeholder involvement in teaching, especially in courses on sustainable development, where contributions from business and public institutions will foster continuous knowledge exchange. At the same time, the promotion of group assignments, project-based learning, and electronic examinations introduces durable innovations aligned with digitalisation and the green transition.

Finally, UG intends to build on the collaborative potential developed during the project, particularly through continued cooperation with partners in running the Citizen Science Lab and preparing joint proposals for international funding. With the lab now embedded in the Rector's strategic agenda, its long-term development is secured. Monitoring these initiatives through defined KPIs will ensure continuity and measurable progress, positioning UG as a modern, sustainable university strongly connected to its socio-economic environment.

In addition as a general framework, the next table is summarizing the intentions and the planned sustainability measures actions by the CATALISI university partners in terms of post-project sustainability and use of the project results:

Table 8: Sustainability measures actions planned by the CATALISI HEIs partners

Action	KTU	UJI	UG	LUISS	UCC	AUTH	AUMC
The project results will serve as a foundation for the university's strategic planning and guide the development of its strategic agenda toward institutional transformation.	V	V	TBD	V	V	V	V
The project results will be utilized in annual and periodic institutional accreditation processes and procedures.	TBD	V	TBD	V	X	TBD	X
The project results will facilitate future collaborations with other universities and/or entities in the development of project proposals and/or joint R&D activities	V	V	V	V	V	TBD	V
The project results will assist in identifying and pursuing funding opportunities	V	TBD	TBD	V	V	TBD	X
The project results will help identify and foster cooperation and collaboration opportunities, including leveraging individual expertise	V	TBD	V	TBD	V	TBD	V
The university will establish a dedicated structure (e.g. office, unit, etc.) or a responsible person to guide and support the institutional transformation process (or assign the tasks to an existing one)	TBD	X	TBD	TBD	X	V	V
The university will continue to organize experience sharing events (e.g. MMLs, twinning exchanges, webinars, virtual mobility, etc.) to build capacity and strengthen knowledge sharing, innovation, and best practices across institutions.	V	V	V	TBD	V	V	X
The university will continue to leverage the training resources available in the Learning Hub to enhance skills and support	V	V	V	V	X	V	V

continuous professional development and/or to							
The university will organize internal training programs to build staff capacity, enhance understanding of institutional transformation processes, and ensure effective implementation of sustainability measures.	V	V	V	V	TBD	V	V

Legend:

- "V" - YES/planned action
- "X" - NO/not planned action
- "TBD" - to be further discussed and decided
- "NA" - Not applicable

Although the individual sustainability plans differ among university partners due to the varying focus of their institutional transformation priorities within the defined intervention areas, the partners' overall commitment to project sustainability can be summarized in the following key areas and corresponding measures (with examples):

Table 9 Summary of key areas for sustainability measures and example actions for their implementation (extracted from D3.2)

Sustainability measure	Example actions
Institutional integration:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Establishment of dedicated structures to guide and support the institutional transformation within the university. ● Appointment of a person / group or position as responsible for institutional transformation (task force), maintaining and updating resources, etc. ● Embedding change and the adopted measures and key activities in the university strategic and / or policy documents (e.g.: commit to change in the institutional action plan/s; include mobility into teacher academic assessment framework; embedding certification of skills, MOOCs, and FAIR data training into the regular operations of the university; add key modules to curriculum, etc.).
Partnership continuity and stakeholders engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Negotiating long-term agreements with foreign institutions, not just one-off exchanges. ● Building long-term relationships with schools, NGOs, municipalities (shape and engage a community) to ensure recurring participation. ● Creating recognition systems for citizen scientists (certificates, acknowledgement

	<p>in publications, open days) and retaining volunteering.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strengthening long-term collaboration with civil society, academic partners, and business stakeholders through annual co-creation forums and Memoranda of Understanding.
Funding diversification:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Applying for EU and national science communication programmes for funding. ● Identify and apply cross-funding models like combining Erasmus+, Horizon and other EU funding with university co-funding to reduce reliance on one source. ● Cooperating with the business on R&D tasks and sharing of research results, research infrastructure, etc.
Knowledge transfer:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Requiring the returning teachers (from mobilities, exchanges, international conferences, etc..) to share lessons learned (e.g., workshops, internal reports, peer mentoring). ● Establishing peer-support mechanisms
Capacity building:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training of internal staff and senior researchers to act as mentors/trainers, reducing reliance on external experts (in Train-the-Trainer schemes or seminars). ● Train researchers in public engagement skills, funding opportunities identification skills, project proposals development skills, etc..
Digitalization (digital resources and platforms)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Creating online repositories of guides, recorded webinars, templates to ensure continuing support beyond live sessions. ● Strengthening an online hub where citizens can continuously engage (upload observations, access results, participate in discussions). ● Integrating MOOCs into the curriculum. ● Support blended mobility – maintain virtual collaboration with host institutions after physical stay.
Open data & transparency Mainstreaming Open Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing internal documents (e.g. policies, strategies, guidelines, handbooks, etc.) requiring and/or informing on Open Access and Open Science principles and rules. ● Integrate dedicated lectures/seminars on Open Data Sharing, Open Science, Open Access, etc. into an existing course.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide ad-hoc training sessions for researchers on principles and practices of data sharing. • Provide clear feedback to citizens on how their contributions are used and what impact they have.
Policy Alignment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking universities' actions with national higher education strategies and European initiatives (like ERA, EOSC, etc.), ensuring compatibility and access to future funding opportunities.

4.6. HORIZON BOOSTER WORK

Initially, the application for support services was submitted by one of the sister projects, aUPaEU, on behalf of the three sister projects as a joint group seeking Booster support. Once the application was approved, the individual contexts, timelines, and strategic visions of each project were discussed with the Horizon Booster experts. Based on the subsequent analysis of the information provided through the Readiness Assessment Tool by all three projects, it was decided to split the exploitation support service to better address the specific needs of each project.

For this purpose, the assessment of the three projects was carefully considered, including their progress and level of advancement, the exploitation strategies already adopted, and the degree of confidentiality required in sharing details of their exploitation plans. This analysis led to the conclusion that, while the three projects would jointly participate in the Dissemination support services, the Exploitation support would be provided independently by Horizon Booster experts, tailored to the specific status and needs of each project. In this way, the Booster Go-to-Market (G2M) Service was activated for CATALISI, and the involved partners were granted access to the project dashboard.

Finally, the partners agreed to leverage the services offered by the Horizon Booster to strengthen the development of exploitation activities. As mentioned above, three Key Exploitable Results (KERs) were identified as having the greatest potential for further exploitation and were subsequently presented to the Booster as outlined below:

- **(KER1) Multi-level knowledge sharing service strengthening HEI international competitiveness and achieving institutional reforms** - owned by APRE
- **(KER2) Coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various research areas** - owned by EY
- **(KER3) Living Lab Methodology for Institutional Transformation: A Practical Guide to Becoming a Living Lab** - owned by ENoLL

The partners engaged in the Booster support were the owners of the three KERs (APRE, EY and ENoLL), with all sessions coordinated and facilitated by F6S in its capacity as exploitation lead.

As explained in the previous section, the work with the Horizon Booster was kicked off in June 2025. The process was structured into the following modules, each with specific discussions and outcomes:

Module A (Date of the session with expert: 26.06.2025; period for completion: June-July 2025)

- **Participating partners:** APRE, EY, and ENoLL (F6S as moderator and exploitation leader)
- **Objective:** Align participants on the main concepts of “use,” exploitation, and commercialization of KERs; identify the KERs to be considered during the overall Go-to-Market (G2M) service.
- **Results achieved:** Selection of three KERs for inclusion in the G2M module; definition of preliminary exploitation intentions for each KER; completion of the Exploitation Intentions Table using the Booster canvas.

Module B (Dates of sessions with expert: 28–29.07.2025; period for completion: August-September 2025)

- **Participating partners:** APRE, EY, and ENoLL (F6S as moderator and exploitation leader)
- **Objective:** Review and define the potential market for each KER and assess related competitive advantages. The focus was placed on end-users/customers and their needs, demonstrating clear market potential for the selected KERs; evaluate the relevance of an IP strategy; prepare KERs for showcasing on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP).
- **Results achieved:** Market definition/review for each KER; identification of competitive advantages; development and refinement of KER profiles for HRP; completion of UVP and MD canvases for the three selected KERs.

Module C (Dates of sessions with expert: 08.10.2025 and 31.10.2025; period for completion: October-November 2025)

- **Participating partners:** APRE, EY, and ENoLL (F6S as moderator and exploitation leader)
- **Objective:** Complete and discuss the Exploitation Strategy and Sustainability (ESS) templates.
- **Results achieved:** Completion of characterization tables, exploitation roadmaps, use options, risk assessments and priority maps, and Lean canvases for the three selected KERs.

The capacity building sessions were scheduled with the assigned expert for the service in advance and represented 1 to 4 hours online calls with pre-defined agenda, goals and templates to be used and filled in. After each module, the KER owners had a period of time to work offline and finetune/finalize the contribution, as well as to validate their findings and statements with representatives of the potential end users (or early adopters) like the project university partners.

Get started Refreshing on activities of MODULE A

1 - Go-To-Market Support (G2M)

Module A: Kick-off

- 2 online meetings
- Setting the ground (today)
- Exploitation pillars training on the G2M process and related concepts

Module B: Unique Value Proposition (UVP) & KERs

1 UVP workshop per KER (3-4h each):

- Assess/review/identify the KERs
- Definition of the market
- Draft the UVP
- Address Intellectual Assets
- Draft/review of the Horizon Results Platform profile

BOOSTER

The Value Proposition Canvas (VPC)

Value Map

Customer Profile

BOOSTER

MARKET DEFINITION CANVAS

Multi-level knowledge sharing service strengthening HEI international competitiveness and achieving institutional reforms

STAR HERE

1 TRADITIONAL MARKET DEFINITION

2 JOB EXECUTOR DETERMINATION

3 ABSTRACTED JOB EXECUTOR

4 JOB EXECUTOR

5 FUNCTION OF THE PRODUCT

6 OTHER PRODUCTS USED & THEIR FUNCTIONS

7 ABSTRACTED JOB STATEMENT

8 JOB-TO-BE-DONE

KER1 APRE

PROBLEM Top 3 problems	SOLUTION Top 3 features	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION Single, clear, compelling message that states why you are different and worth buying	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE Can't be easily copied or bought	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS Target customers
1	4	3	9	2
	KEY METRICS Key activities you measure		CHANNELS Path to customers	
	8		5	
COST STRUCTURE Customer Acquisition Costs Distributing Costs Hosting People, etc.		REVENUE STREAMS Revenue Model Lifetime Value Revenue Gross Margin		
7		6		

BOOSTER

An initiative of the European Commission

Exploitation roadmap for KER 1 - Multi-level knowledge sharing service strengthening HEI international competitiveness and achieving institutional reforms

Actions

- Briefly describe actions planned to be executed 3-6 months after the end of the project. Make sure you do not just focus on technical activities (realisation of a prototype, software interface, etc.) but also consider the finalisation of a business plan, the protection of intellectual property, the collection of authorisations, all of it will be needed to start implement what is in your exploitation plan.
- Refinement of the KER: definition of the service package (e.g. number and type of MML workshops, frequency of Twinning activities, optional add-ons), ensuring clarity for adopters.
- Finalisation of the business plan, including pricing models (consulting service, digital toolkit, premium memberships).
- Definition of IP strategy (open-access vs premium content, licensing options, attribution rules).
- Preparation of a digital self-service toolkit (templates, KPIs, stakeholder mapping, guides) to ensure scalability.
- Identification and engagement of early adopters through APRE's network, ELIA, alliances of universities.
- Formalisation of cooperation agreements with experienced HEIs (CATALISI implementers) to host Twinning visits.
- Integration of the KER into new EU/national project proposals (e.g., WIDERA, Reforming HEI, Erasmus+).
- Communication & dissemination actions, including casebook publication and dedicated webinars.

Roles

Roles of partners involved in the actions defined above. Start with the identification of the organisation which will be the main responsible for the exploitation roadmap (exploiting the KER)

- APRE: main responsible for exploitation, business model design, service delivery, management of IP, and outreach to adopters.
- HEI partners (CATALISI implementers): provide feedback, act as reference cases, and host twinning activities.
- Other CATALISI partners: support integration of the KER into new proposals, dissemination, and promotion across European networks.

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BOOSTER

An initiative of the European Commission

Characterisation table

Project Acronym	CATALISI		
HRBOOSTER Expert	PAOLA AMATO		
Version	Date	Elaborated by	Notes
V0	14/07/2025	PAOLA AMATO	BOOSTER TEMPLATE (10/03/2025)
V1	16/09/2025	Stefania Latescu	Filled in by APRE
V2	19/09/2025	Violeta Nuydenova	Suggested (and accepted) adjustments and add-ons on behalf of the CATALISI Exploitation Lead FRS

To be filled in for each of the proposed KERs

- Please use a single document for ALL KERs and do not split it into separate word files.
- Please keep "track-change" function on across the different versions. NB This function will be activated by the export when commenting on your first version(V1)

prepare a characterisation table for each selected KER

KER name: Multi-level knowledge sharing service strengthening HEI international competitiveness and achieving institutional reforms	Input from the beneficiary
Description	Describe in a few lines your KER and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple words, avoid acronyms, and make sure you explain how your solution solve adopters' problems/needs. Our multi-level knowledge sharing service helps institutional change agents in Higher Education who aim to strengthen their institution's international competitiveness and implement meaningful reforms, by providing structured, peer-driven learning processes that reduce capacity gaps, internal fragmentation and resistance to change, and by enabling the co-creation of tailored transformation strategies aligned with EU priorities, boosting institutional viability and fostering long-term collaboration across the HEI landscape, unlike traditional, top-down consultancy or training models that lack contextual adaptation, mutual learning and sustained stakeholder engagement.
Target market/end users	Describe the market in which your product/service will be used (can "compare to", answering the following questions): - What is the target market? - Who are the customers/beneficiaries? Use the information collected from the Market Definition Canvas (if available)

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Figure 74: Template and model canvas and documents used in the work with the Horizon Booster

What's next?

During the last session, the partners involved discussed with the Horizon Booster expert the opportunity to take advantage of another module provided by the programme and work on the **Module D: Intellectual Assets Management (IAM)** starting from December 2025. The request was accepted and the sessions will be scheduled to start during the last project month, but will continue after its end, too, as the exploitation efforts will continue in the next months and years as well.

After the end of the CATALISI project and upon completing the module for IAM, the KERs' owning partners committed to publish the KERs on the Horizon Results Platform and make them available for uptake, under the condition that they will not protect them with an IPRs and provide them as services (which was discussed as an option in the sessions).

Documentation

We present in *Annex 5_CATALISI Exploitation documents set for the 3 KERs (Horizon Booster templates)* a selection of the exploitation documents sets developed for the for the 3 project Key Exploitable Results as follows:

- Characterisation table
- Exploitation Roadmap

The full set of documents developed within the Horizon Booster support service (e.g. Exploitation intentions table, Unique Value Proposition canvas, Market Definition Canvas, and other ESS templates) are extensive in volume as well as may hinder potential future intellectual property rights of the KERs' owners, thus will not be displayed in full publicly. Hence, these will be provided within the project technical report, and also some key annexes (e.g. exploitation roadmap) are attached to the current deliverable.

5. CONCLUSION

The communication and dissemination strategies implemented during CATALISI have played a pivotal role in amplifying the project's visibility and ensuring the uptake of its results. Through a structured, multi-channel communication approach (including a strong digital presence, targeted messaging, and consistent branding) the project successfully expanded the outreach of its communication and dissemination activities to key target groups such as policymakers, higher education institutions and alliances, and civil society. These efforts positioned CATALISI as a reference point for institutional transformation and innovation in higher education.

Dissemination activities complemented this by ensuring that project outputs were not only shared but actively integrated into broader initiatives. Open-access publications, participation in international events and conferences, and the creation of the Catalyst Hub as a central repository guaranteed that knowledge generated during the project remains accessible and actionable. These measures foster replication, scalability, and long-term impact beyond the consortium.

Finally, the CATALISI project has laid a strong foundation for long-term impact through a comprehensive approach to exploitation and sustainability. By implementing structured exploitation planning, engaging with the Horizon Results Booster, and creating enduring digital resources such as the Catalyst Hub, the project ensures that its outputs remain accessible and actionable beyond the project lifecycle. The sustainability strategy developed by the consortium provides a clear roadmap for continued use, adaptation, and evolution of project results. This strategy empowers partners to integrate transformation practices into their institutional frameworks while fostering collaboration across ecosystems.

By embedding acceleration services into governance structures, sustaining the Catalyst Hub as a central knowledge and networking platform, and formalizing a Community of Practice, the project sustainability plan guarantees continuity and scalability of CATALISI outputs. It

also emphasizes resource mobilization, policy integration, and systematic monitoring to secure long-term relevance and alignment with European priorities.

Together, communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts have strengthened the project's legacy by creating awareness, building trust, and enabling continuous engagement with stakeholders. Moving forward, the established channels and resources will serve as a foundation for sustaining collaboration and promoting the adoption of CATALISI methodologies across the European Higher Education landscape.

Ultimately, the project has delivered not only tools and methodologies but also a **culture of collaboration and innovation** that will continue to drive institutional transformation. The next phase focuses on maintaining momentum—leveraging established networks, resources, and strategies to achieve sustainable impact at national, regional, and European levels.

6. ANNEXES

Annex 1: CATALISI Internal Events

Annex 2: CATALISI Communication Activities and Media Coverage

Annex 3: CATALISI External Events

Annex 4: CATALISI Exploitation Questionnaire

Annex 5: CATALISI Exploitation documents set for the 3 KERs (Horizon Booster templates)

CATALISI INTERNAL EVENTS

Event	Date	Place	Description
KoM	1/26-27/2023	Rome, Italy	The official Kick off the meeting with all the partners participating.
EAB meeting	9/18/2023	Teams	An online meeting to meet our EAB members organised by APRE under WP4
Market Place Workshop	10/12/2023	Teams	Organised under WP3 by F6S with all partners participating. A brainstorming session to understand the needs and next steps of the Market place. The new name of the online platform was chosen: CATALYST Hub
1 st Online MML workshop with CoP members	11/7/2023	Teams	Organised by APRE in the context of T.6.3: Inspirational examples on institutional transformation of HEIs in R&I agenda. The CoP workshop was proven to be successful in gathering a wide pool of experts and professionals in the field of institutional transformation of HEI around the priorities of the European Research Agenda (ERA) illustrating the profound interest in the topic as well as the urgent need to continue creating mutual learning spaces.
1st Webinar: Gender and Inclusion	11/23/2023	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S. Dissemination of best practices and research findings in the realm of gender and inclusion within higher education. Speakers: Sabina Pellizzoni, Magdalena Zadkowska. Available in the Learning Hub platform.
CATALISI General Assembly	1/18/2024	Spain Castellon (UJI)	All partners attended to discuss the status of the project and next steps
1st MML workshop at UJI	1/19/2024	Spain (UJI)	e Mobilisation and Mutual learning workshop organised by UJI and facilitated by APRE with all the implementers HEIs in the context of T,2,3.

2nd Annual Project Meeting	1/21/2024	AUTH (Thessaloniki, Greece)	All partners attended to discuss the status of the project and next steps.
2nd Webinar: Mainstreaming of Open Science and Digitisation of Research	2/8/2024	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S. Sharing best practices and research findings on Open Science Fostering dialogues and collaboration among experts in this sector Identifying Multilingualism as a catalyst for Open Science
Intellectual Property & Innovation Days		UG Gdansk	The second edition of the event, aimed at scientists creating innovations – this year organized under the slogan: “PATENTS, INNOVATIONS, ENTREPRENEURS – Science 4 Business cooperation”.
3rd webinar: Recognition of research careers	4/5/2024	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S. Erica Feliziani, Research Advisor at the University of Macerata, explored the essential skills and training required for European research managers, drawing insights from the CARDEA project. Rrap Kryeziu, a senior consultant at EY, presented a predictive study on the soft skills researchers need to thrive in the labor market.
2nd MML workshop VUMC	4/11/2024	Amsterdam (VUMC)	Organised by AUMC in the context of T,2.3 and facilitated by APRE. All CATALISI HEIs Implementers invited stakeholders to think along about two main intervention areas focused on institutional transformation: 1) Recognition of qualifications and research careers and 2) Reform of research assessment.
1st Twinning KTU hosting AUMC	5/10/2024	Lithuania (KTU)	Organised by KTU in the context of T,2.4 and facilitated by APRE. AUMC participated as a visiting institution. The twinning visit aims to share the experience and present the main streams of open science at Kaunas University of Technology.
4th webinar: Reinforcing the Role of Universities in	5/22/2025	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S. Roberto San Salvador del Valle, highlighted how universities must serve as beacons of innovation, making

Local Innovation Systems			conscious choices about areas to innovate that genuinely benefit local communities.
UCC Evaluation online workshop	6/4/2024	Zoom	Following the submission of Deliverable 4.1, UCC is organising an online workshop for all partners on the evaluation approach, with a focus on the Theory of Change method.
2nd Twinning VUMC hosting UJI and UG	6/11/2024	Amsterdam (VUMC)	Workshop on Research ethics, sharing insights from the Academic Integrity Committees in the Netherlands, and Research ethics and Research Integrity training; interactive workshop sharing materials and assessment of training needs visiting partners
Third Exploitation workshop	6/15/2024	Zoom	Internal exploitation workshop to align with the partners on the next steps and BOOSTER support
5th webinar: Digitisation of Higher Education Institutions	6/24/2024	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S. We explored the evolving landscape of digital strategies in higher education with insights from experts like Dr. Thijs Broekhuizen from the University of Groningen, Maddalena Illario, and Erminia Attaianese from the Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II (UniNa) / University of Naples Federico II.
6th webinar: Accurately Addressing Live Long Learning	10/4/2024	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S. Prof. Ass. Dr. Florim Gallopeni and Prof. Ass. Dr. Bujar Gallopeni discussed the critical importance of continuous learning in today's rapidly changing professional landscape.
3rd MML workshop LUISS	10/17/2024	LUISS	Organised by LUISS in the context of T,2.3 and facilitated by APRE The aim of the MML event was to collectively explore the concept of the Third Mission and the activities associated with it, particularly in relation to research. All Implementers HEIs participated in this workshop.
3rd Twinning LUISS	10/18/2024	Italy, (LUISS)	Organised by LUISS in the context of T,2.4 and facilitated by APRE. In-depth discussion on local

hosting AUTH and KTU, UJI			ecosystem engagement (including collaboration strategies) with visiting institutions.
4th Twinning UCC hosting LUISS, VUMC, KTU and UJI	11/13/2024	UCC	Organised by UCC in the context of T.2.4 and facilitated by APRE. Conversation with visiting institutions pivoted around: Open Science and COARA, Third Mission and Societal Engagement, and: Integrity and Ethics
4th MML workshop at UCC hosting all Implementers	11/14/2024	UCC (Cork, Ireland)	Organised by UCC in the context of T.2.3 and facilitated by APRE. Enabling structured dialogue around the topic of Financial Sustainability in Research. Inviting a peer interrogation of UCC intervention areas and activities, an anticipated outcome was the identification of potential follow up opportunities to enhance the effectiveness and impact-making efforts of local action plans and overall exploitation of CATALISI acceleration services.
5th Twinning KTU hosting UCC, UJI, UG, AUTH, LUISS	12/9/2024	KTU (Kaunas, Lithuania)	Organised by KTU in the context of T.2.4 and facilitated by APRE. The Twinning visit aimed to share the experience and present the main streams of open science, public engagement in science and sustainability in research at Kaunas University of Technology with the visiting HEIs.
5th MML workshop in KTU with all Implementers HEIs	12/10/2024	KTU (Kaunas, Lithuania)	Organised by KTU in the context of T.2.3 and facilitated by APRE. The event aimed to discuss infrastructure, strategic guidelines, and real-world applications of citizen science projects across different fields.
6th MML workshop in AUTH with all Implementers HEIs	1/22/2025	AUTH (Thessaloniki, Greece)	Organised by AUTH in the context of T.2.3 and facilitated by APRE. The event aimed to bring together academic, professional, and community stakeholders to explore how Open Science and Citizen Science principles can be effectively integrated into higher education institutions.
6th Twinning AUTH hosting UCC, UG and VUMC	1/23/2025	AUTH (Thessaloniki, Greece)	Organised by AUTH in the context of T.2.4 and facilitated by APRE. The Twinning exchange focused on reforming research assessment, particularly emphasizing sustainable research funding, alternative financing models, and the integration of Open Science practices.

7th webinar: Support Talent Circulation / Mobility	2/26/2025		Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S. We explored best practices from various institutions, uncovering valuable strategies for attracting and supporting top talent. The presentations were packed with interesting statistics and practical tools being utilised across different countries.
MML CoP workshop (2nd)	3/5/2025	Teams	Organised by APRE in the context of T.6.3 with the participation of CoP members. The workshop brought together experts, researchers, and key stakeholders from across Europe to explore how to better equip researchers for the evolving labour market.
Webinar – UVT Digital & Green Living Lab Case Study	3/21/2025	Teams	A webinar hosted by EnOLL that provided the framework for open innovation activities at the Western University of Timișoara.
8th webinar: CoARA: a unique opportunity for a better [Open] research assessment	3/31/2025	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S. It focused on transforming higher education; the session explored actionable strategies for Open Science practices and reforming research assessment. The CoARA example
7th Twinning UJI hosting AUMC, and, LUISS	4/3/2025	UJI (Castellon de la Plana, Spain)	Organised by UJI in the context of T,2.4 and facilitated by APRE. The event opens the topic of Open Access, current situation, and future perspectives
Twinning at UG hosting AUTH and KTU	4/10/2025	Gdansk (UG)	Organised by UG in the context of T,2.4 and facilitated by APRE. The first session focused on public engagement and outreach to society. The second session highlighted Open Science practices and society-oriented initiatives. The final session illustrated how academic spaces and media platforms can be leveraged to engage the public.
7th MML workshop at UG hosting	4/11/2025	Gdansk (UG)	Organised by UG in the context of T.2.3 and facilitated by APRE. To strengthen societal engagement in higher education by fostering

AUTH and KTU			collaboration between universities and external stakeholders.
8th Twinning AUMC hosting UCC, LUISS and AUTH	5/15-16/2025	Amsterdam (VUMC)	Organised by AUMC in the context of T,2.4 and facilitated by APRE. The event focused on Public Engagement and Outreach to society to solve social challenges. It covered presenting existing societal actions (labs, library, radio, etc.) and open science initiatives.
Success Story webinar: UJI	5/16/2025	Spain (UJI)	Organised within WP5 by F6S. Transforming Research Ethos: Open Science and the Reform of Ethical Governance. Laura Mentini A. Feenstra and Ramon showcased its successful transformation in research ethics and Open Science.
Success Story webinar: KTU	9/22/2025	Zoom	Organised within WP5 by F6S. Transformational pathway towards enhancing public participation in research. Dr. Egle Butkeviciene shared how the university has been actively engaging with citizens to become a truly interdisciplinary and internationally competitive institution, one that drives transformation, knowledge, and innovation.
9th webinar: Academic Freedom	9/30/2025	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by EY in collaboration with F6S and AUMC. The webinar shared how universities should have the freedom to choose their topic of research focused on their capacities and ecosystems.
Success Story webinar: AUTH	10/7/2025	Zoom	Organised within WP5 by F6S. During the European Sustainable Development Week, CATALISI, represented by AUTH had the opportunity to explore how EU-funded projects are driving progress towards SDG 4: Quality Education through innovation, collaboration, and inclusion. The webinar brought together five inspiring Horizon Europe and Erasmus+ initiatives: GREENVERSITY, CATALISI project, DS4Skills - Data Space for Skills, XR4ED, and Youlead.
Success Story webinar: UCC	10/8/2025	Zoom	Organised within WP5 by F6S. Evaluating HE Institutional Change Through a Participatory Approach. The UCC team discussed the topics:

			Why the Theory of Change is such a powerful approach for evaluation and impact assessment. Key lessons learned about the use of Key Performance Indicators from the CATALISI project. The significant difference a participatory approach to evaluation and impact assessment can make to institutions.
Success Story webinar: UG	10/29/2025	Zoom	Organised within WP5 by F6S. Transforming Research Ethos: Open Science and the Reform of Ethical Governance. The University of Gdańsk (UG), introduced their focus on strengthening commercial collaboration with business, understanding partners' needs, improving cooperation for both commercial and research purposes, and building long-term relationships
CATALISI final General Assembly	11/09/2025	Amsterdam	All partners attended to discuss the status of the project and final steps.
Final CATALISI Event	11/10/2025	Amsterdam	Organised by APRE. The event gave the opportunity to present co-created KPIs and peer-learning practices. Discussions on research culture, policy validation with our PO, and acceleration services. With the presence of our sister projects aUPaEU, Accelerate Future HEI, and synergy projects GILL, PATTERN Horizon Europe, Skills4EOSC, and REINFORCING Project.
10th Webinar: Connecting Policies and Projects: Advancing the European Research Area (ERA) Together	11/28/2025	Zoom	Organised in the context of T,2.1 by APRE, EY in collaboration with F6S. The last webinar of the project was a success with over 100 attendees, the presence of our PO and sister projects. We discussed project outcomes, the joint policy and next steps of the ERA policy.

CATALISI COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES AND MEDIA COVERAGE

Partner/Project	Date	Communication Activity Name	Communication channel	Link
APRE	11/04/2023	Dissemination of call for CoP members through APRE segnala mailing list. "Progetto EU CATALISI Invito a partecipare alla Comunità di Pratica di CATALISI"	Newsletter	(internal communication to APRE R&I mailing list network)
APRE	02/18/2024	Promotion of Webinar Preparing for the future: key skills for research careers	Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/apre-agenzia-promozione-ricerca-europea_apreprogetti-apre-pattern-activity-7297542824625893376-689E/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACBy99UBrGtU3beG7Hb-wDyv9MVCVNIVRLYs
UJI	04/19/2024	Interview to Ramon Feenstra in Onda Cero Spanish national radio to talk about Open Science	TV/Radio campaign	https://www.ondacero.es/emisoras/comunidad-valenciana/castellon/eventos/uji-divulga/entrevista-ramon-feenstra_2024041866210ce4c0b95c000102edb3.html
PATTERN	05/10/2024	Partnering with CATALISI Feature in their website	Website	https://www.pattern-openresearch.eu/similar-initiatives/
NCP Wideranet	06/02/2024	Results from the Horizon Europe ERA Calls: Exploring the Facts and Figures	Media Article	https://www.ncpwideranet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/ERA_Factsheet_No_5_03.pdf
KTU	07/1-5/2024	IIAS - International Institute of Administrative Sciences conference 2024	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_horizoneurope-project-transformationalchange-activity-7169568959468417024-S1UH?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

ERA Project	07/15/2024	Entry about CATALISI project	Website	https://www.inspiring-era.eu/era-project-highlights/
EUA	07/22/2024	A Living Lab Approach to the Financial Sustainability of Research University College Cork (UCC) EUA Funding Forum 2024, Helsinki	Website	https://www.eua.eu/images/FF_2024_presentations/IC_-_A_-_Stronger_together_acceleration_upscaling_of_financial_strategies.pdf
UJI	07/28/2024	Hacia una ciencia sin barreras Article about UJI work in Open Science	Media outlet	https://www.elperiodicomediterraneo.com/opinion/2024/07/28/ciencia-barreras-106173083.html?utm_source=twitter&utm_medium=social&utm_campaign=btn-share
UJI	08/18/2024	¿El mejor negocio del mundo? Las editoriales científicas disparan los precios y multiplican su facturación	Media outlet	https://www.eldiario.es/sociedad/mejor-negocio-mundo-editoriales-cientificas-disparan-precios-multiplican-facturacion_1_11532874.html
UJI	09/26/2024	L'exministre Subirats a Castelló: «La universitat ha d'evidenciar que contribueix al país»	Media outlet	https://www.elperiodicomediterraneo.com/castello-provincia/2024/09/26/lexministre-subirats-castello-universitat-devidenciar-108612484.html
UJI	09/26/2024	Participation in the 8th conference on research integrity	Media outlet	https://www.elperiodic.com/castellon/subirats-universidades-tenemos-obligacion-aportar-evidencias-estamos-contribuyendo-bienestar-este-pais_980953
UJI	09/26/2024	V Ethics in Research Conference: Ethics and Transparency in Alternative Scientific Evaluation Metrics	Youtube video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lgpJ6znZHbU
UJI	09/27/2024	Subirats: «Las universidades tenemos la obligación de aportar evidencias que demuestren que estamos contribuyendo al bienestar de este país»	Media Article	https://www.uji.es/com/noticias/2024/9/29/jornades-etica-investigacio/
UJI	09/29/2024	¿Qué ciencia apoyar?	Media outlet	https://www.elperiodicomediterraneo.com/opinion/2024/09/29/ciencia-apoyar-108694420.html
KTU	10/20/2024	About MML and Twinning event in LUISS Information about learnings from Twinning and MML in UCC	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_transformationalchange-catalisi-accelerationsservices-activity-7253337126237356032-

				QNdJ?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
GILL	11/14/2024	CATALISI features in their web	Media Article	https://gi-ll.eu/gill-and-catalisi-collaborate-to-foster-an-inclusive-innovation-ecosystem-in-europe/
KTU	12/12/2024	About MML and Twinning event in KTU. This is the information about the MML and Twinning that KTU hosted	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272229761999900674/
KTU	12/13/2024	About Twinning event in KTU This is the information about the last Twinning that KTU hosted	Website	https://library.ktu.edu/news/at-the-catalisi-project-event-discussions-were-held-on-citizen-science-and-sustainability-in-research/
KTU	12/15/2024	About MML and Twinning event in UCC. Information about learnings from Twinning and MML in UCC	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_heis-activity-7267785288129642496-fqQg?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
REINFORCING	01/14/2025	Learning Hub	Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7284976465756983296/
aUPaEU	02/12/2025	Mention on their Newsletter	Media Article	https://aupaeu.widening.eu/newsletter-3
EUA	02/19/2025	How universities can overcome roadblocks to citizen science in academia	Media Article	https://www.eua.eu/our-work/expert-voices/how-universities-can-overcome-roadblocks-to-citizen-science-in-academia.html
APRE	02/24/2025	Promotion through APRE weekly newsletter of CoP MML workshop: mutual learning "Preparing for the future: key skills for research careers"	Newsletter	(internal communication to APRE R&I members)
REINFORCING NEWSLETTER	02/25/2025	CATALISI entry on the website	Newsletter	https://us8.campaign-archive.com/?u=1ae387ec287bfbfd605ee84134&id=063d05c17e
UNIVPM - Università Politecnica delle Marche	03/5/2025	Invito a partecipare all'evento di mutual learning "Preparing for the future: key skills for research careers"	Media Article	https://www.univpm.it/Entra/Servizi_agli_studenti/Job_Placement/Progetto_europeo_CATALISI

EURAXESS	03/05/2025	Preparing for the future: key skills for research careers	Webinar entry	https://www.euraxess.nl/netherlands/events/preparing-future-key-skills-research-careers
APRE	03/05/2025	Promotion through APRE segnala mailing list of mutual learning "Preparing for the future: key skills for research careers"	Newsletter	(internal communication to APRE R&I mailing list network)
F6S website	03/19/2025	CoARA: a unique opportunity for a better [Open] research assessment Webinar	Media Article	https://innovation.f6s.com/event/co-ara-a-unique-opportunity-for-a-better-open-research-assessment/
APRE	03/27/2025	Promotion of webinar Webinar A Unique Opportunity for a Better [Open] Research Assessment	Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/apre-agenzia-promozione-ricerca-europea-apreprogetti-catalisi-apre-activity-7311016664265842688-5-LC/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACByp9UBrGtU3beG7Hb-wDyv9MVCVIVRLYs
VERITY	03/28/2025	CATALISI features in their newsletter	Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/31c3c687215b/verity-4-newsletter-10879007%20
APRE	03/31/2025	Promotion through APRE segnala mailing list WEBINAR CATALISI PROJECT. CoARA: a unique opportunity for a better Open research assessment	Newsletter	(internal communication to APRE R&I mailing list network)
UG	04/2/2025	Intellectual Property & Innovation Days	Media Article	https://ctt.ug.edu.pl/en/intellectual-property-innovation-days-en/
UG	04/10/2025	Faculty of Economics at the University of Gdańsk hosts CATALISI project events	Media Article	https://ekonom.ug.edu.pl/en/news/33220/faculty-economics-university-gdansk-hosts-catalisi-project-events
UJI	04/15/2025	CoARA y ENCA-UJI	Media Article	https://repositori.uji.es/collections/509c8e95-120e-43df-9f62-5984d9c69b04
UJI	04/15/2025	CoARA y ENCA-UJI	Media Article	https://www.uji.es/com/investigacio/arxiu/noticies/2025/9/enquesta-avaluacio-cientifica/?urlRedirect=https://www.uji.es/com/investigacio/arxiu/noticies/2025/9/enquesta-avaluacio-cientifica/&url=/com/investigacio/arxiu/noticies/2025/9/enquesta-avaluacio-cientifica/

UJI	04/15/2025	La UJI reflexiona sobre el sistema de evaluación científica y presenta la visión de su equipo	Media outlet	https://ruvid.org/la-uji-reflexiona-sobre-el-sistema-de-evaluacion-cientifica-y-presenta-la-vision-de-su-equipo/
APRE	05/19/2025	Promotion of the webinar "Public engagement and outreach" Sharing news to promote the webinar "Public engagement and outreach" among the APRE network through the use of a specific communication channel called APRE weekly.	Newsletter	https://a5f3g7.emailsp.com/f/rnl.aspx/?fhh=s_zox1&x=pv&je=r1.j=-syvz&d1-b=&x=pv&7e5k0&x=pp&s17ag02.kx-gf=/tn_NCLM
APRE	05/19/2025	Promotion through APRE weekly newsletter of Final Conference: "Shaping the future of institutional changes in Higher Educational Institutions"	Newsletter	(internal communication to APRE R&I members: screenshot available)
APRE	05/26/2025	Sharing a newsletter fully dedicated to the promotion of the webinar "Public engagement and outreach" among the APRE network through the use of a specific communication channel called APREsegnala.	Newsletter	https://a5f3g7.emailsp.com/f/rnl.aspx/?fhh=s_zox1&x=pv&je=r1.j=-szsz&d1-b=&x=pv&7e5k0&x=pp&s17ag02.kx-gf=/tuyNCLM
APRE	05/28/2025	Promotion of the webinar "Public engagement and outreach"	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/apre-agenzia-promozione-ricerca-europea_apreprogetti-apre-catalisi-activity-7332744853472079874-Z8tk?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAADS_BhjMB1vL5KmPgj6-GG8nz17GQRQ1nXDo
EURAXESS	06/10/2025	Dissemination of CATALISI success stories webinar	Website	https://www.euraxess.nl/netherlands/events/catalisi-success-stories-universitat-jaume-i-ujj
UJI	06/10/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers	Media Article	https://repositori.uji.es/items/602dfb78-0f37-472d-8f48-1fd706785b24

		know about Open Access and its results		
UJI	06/11/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	Castellónplaza https://castellonplaza.com/castellonplaza/educacion2/la-comunidad-investigadora-de-la-uji-apuesta-por-la-ciencia-abierta-sin-restricciones
UJI	06/12/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media Article	UJI news https://www.uji.es/com/investigacio/arxiu/noticies/2025/6/ciencia-oberta/?urlRedirect=https://www.uji.es/com/investigacio/arxiu/noticies/2025/6/ciencia-oberta/&url=/com/investigacio/arxiu/noticies/2025/6/ciencia-oberta/&urlRedirect=https://www.uji.es/com/investigacio/arxiu/noticies/2025/6/ciencia-oberta/&url=/com/investigacio/arxiu/noticies/2025/6/ciencia-oberta/
UJI	06/13/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	Crónica local https://www.cronicalocal.es/noticia/6980/noticias-de-castellon/la-uji-respalda-la-ciencia-abierta-con-mas-del-90-de-apoyo-entre-sus-investigadores.html
UJI	06/13/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	El periòdic. https://www.elperiodic.com/pcastellon/comunidad-investigadora-apuesta-ciencia-abierta_1020210
UJI	06/13/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	Actualidad universitaria. https://ruvid.org/la-comunidad-investigadora-de-la-uji-apuesta-por-la-ciencia-abierta/
UJI	06/13/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	Castellón información. https://www.castelloninformacion.com/el-personal-investigador-de-luji-aposta-per-la-ciencia-oberta/

UJI	06/13/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	La plana al día. https://laplanaaldia.com/castello/noticias/245671/la-comunidad-investigadora-de-la-uji-apuesta-por-la-ciencia-abierta
UJI	06/13/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	Mediterráneo https://www.elperiodicomediterraneo.com/castello-provincia/2025/06/04/els-investigadors-luji-aposten-per-118223886.html
UJI	06/13/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	Actualidad Castellón https://actualidadcastellon.com/comunidad-investigadora-uji-apuesta-ciencia-abierta/
UJI	06/13/2025	Communication about UJI survey coverage. Survey to learn how much researchers know about Open Access and its results	Media outlet	El Mundo Castellón. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://ujiapps.uji.es/ade/rest/storage/ORYRRN7VDTDIHPDCKZNCDRSBBAH9gUUH?url=/com/revista/base/2025/06/05/noticiesuji/11j/0605j11.pdf
Agência Nacional Erasmus+	06/10/2025	Promotion of webinar	Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ane-rasmuseducacaoeformacao_eu-funded-projects-are-operating-tools-activity-7379074207235784704-CE8j?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABQLA4UBkNNgOzjqNkL1escoOCYVALbnf18
UJI	06/16/2025	Universitat Jaume I la VI Jornada de Ética de la Investigación: CoARA y la reforma del sistema de evaluación.	Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ram%C3%B3n-a-feenstra-562234241_2025-coara-i-la-reforma-del-sistema-davaluaci%C3%B3-activity-7373713847754452992-zam?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABQLA4UBkNNgOzjqNkL1escoOCYVALbnf18
UJI	06/30/2025	Reviewing Code of Best	Media outlet	Castellón Información
UJI	06/30/2025	Pactices in Research and Doctoral Studies (CBPID)	Media outlet	El Mundo

UJI	06/30/2025		Media outlet	Castellón Plaza
UJI	06/30/2025		Media outlet	El periódico Mediterráneo
UJI	06/30/2025		Media outlet	Crónica Local
UJI	06/30/2025		Media outlet	Fotos Europa Press
UJI	06/30/2025		Media outlet	Actualidad Castellón
UJI	06/30/2025		Media outlet	El periòdic
UJI	06/30/2025		Media outlet	Punto Comunica
EURAXESS	06/16/2025	CATALISI Success Story: UJI	Webinar entry	https://www.euraxess.nl/netherlands/events/catalisi-success-stories-universitat-jaume-i-uji
UJI	07/02/2025	La UJI introduce la inteligencia artificial en el código ético por la investigación responsable	Media outlet	https://www.elperiodicomediterraneo.com/castello-provincia/2025/06/30/uji-introduce-codigo-etico-inteligencia-artificial-codigo-etico-deontologico-castellon-universidad-119225813.html
VERITY	07/23/2025	About CATALISI	MENTION IN NEWSLETTER	https://mailchi.mp/feabc5dcab02/verity-4-newsletter-13048922
ENOLL	07/23/2025	About CATALISI	Website	https://enoll.org/expertise_projects/capacity-building/page/2/
VERITY	08/25/2025	About CATALISI	Media Article	https://verityproject.eu/about-verity/verity-cluster
UJI	09/01/2025	La UJI reflexiona sobre el sistema de evaluación científica y presenta la visión de su equipo	Media outlet	https://www.elperiodic.com/pcastellon/reflexiona-sobre-sistema-evaluacion-cientifica-presenta-vision-equipo_1033020
UJI	09/01/2025	La UJI reflexiona sobre el sistema de evaluación científica y presenta la visión de su equipo	Media outlet	https://x.com/vivecastellon/status/1962475079373086901
UJI	09/01/2025	La UJI reflexiona sobre el sistema de evaluación científica y presenta la visión de su equipo	Media outlet	https://www.vivecastellon.com/noticiario/la-uji-reflexiona-sobre-el-sistema-de-evaluacion-cientifica-y-presenta-la-vision-de-su-equipo-48003.html

UJI	09/01/2025	La UJI reflexiona sobre el sistema de evaluación científica y presenta la visión de su equipo	Media outlet	https://www.valenciaextra.com/es/cultura/uji-reflexiona-sobre-sistema-evaluacion-cientifica-presenta-vision-su-equipo_576643_102.html
European Sustainable Development Week	09/05/2025	Shaping the future of quality & sustainable education: the impact of EU projects" webinar	Media Article	https://www.esdn.eu/esdw/country-detail/portugal
APRE	09/22/2025	Promotion of the CATALISI Final conference. Sharing news to promote the Final conference among the APRE network through the use of a specific communication channel called APREweekly.	Newsletter	https://a5f3g7.emailsp.com/f/rnl.aspx/?fhh=s_zox1&x=pv&je=r1.j-=tz/z&d1-b=&x=pv&7e5k0&x=pp&s17ag02.kx-gf=//srNCLM
INSPIRING ERA	09/22/2025	Promotion of CATALISI in INSPIRING ERA	Media Article	https://www.inspiring-era.eu/catalisi-project-acceleration-services-for-systematic-transformation-in-universities/
UJI	09/24/2025	VI Ethics in Research Ethics Conference: CoARA and the Reform of the Evaluation System	Media Article	https://www.uji.es/investigacio/base/etica/Agenda/IVJornadaetica/?urlRedirect=https://www.uji.es/investigacio/base/etica/Agenda/IVJornadaetica/&url=/investigacio/base/etica/Agenda/IVJornadaetica/
UJI	09/24/2025	VI Ethics in Research Ethics Conference: CoARA and the Reform of the Evaluation System	Media outlet	https://castellonplaza.com/castellonplaza/educacion2/la-uji-reformara-su-sistema-de-evaluacion-para-impulsar-una-investigacion-mas-diversa-y-responsable
UJI	09/24/2025	VI Ethics in Research Ethics Conference: CoARA and the Reform of the Evaluation System	Media outlet	https://www.cronicalocal.es/noticia/7765/actualidad/la-uji-impulsa-una-reforma-en-su-sistema-de-evaluacion-para-fomentar-la-investigacion-inclusiva.html
UJI	09/24/2025	VI Ethics in Research Ethics Conference: CoARA and the Reform of the Evaluation System	Media outlet	https://ujiapps.uji.es/ade/rest/storage/ZGHUHQZRRMM4MVMEB5FKUIV/CW4D3GTZF?url=/com/revista/base/2025/09/02/noticiesuji/3j/0902i03.pdf
UJI	09/24/2025	VI Ethics in Research Ethics Conference: CoARA and the	Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ram%C3%B3n-a-feenstra-562234241_2025-coara-i-la-reforma-

		Reform of the Evaluation System		del-sistema-davaluaci%C3%B3-activity-7373713847754452992-za-M/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABQLA4UBkNN9OzjqNKl1esc0OCYVALbnf18
APRE	09/26/2025	Promotion of the CATALISI Final conference. Sharing a newsletter fully dedicated to the promotion of the Final conference through the use of a specific communication channel called APREsegnala.	Newsletter	https://a5f3g7.emailsp.com/f/rnl.aspx/?fhh=s_zox1&x=pv&je=r1.j=-tyxz&d1-b=&x=pv&7e5k0&x=pp&s17ag02.kx-gf=//tzNCLM
UG	09/23/2025	XXIII Konferencja Naukowa Zarządzanie Wartością	Media Article	https://wzr.new.ug.edu.pl/wydzial/wydarzenia/konferencje/katedra-strategicznego-rozwoju-i-nauk-o-jakosci/xxiii-konferencja-naukowa-zarzadzanie-wartoscia
Verity	09/29/2025	Promotion CATALISI webinars in Verity	Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/verityproject_join-the-catalisi-project-tomorrow-for-ugcPost-7378445678613696513-g8Gp?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABQLA4UBkNN9OzjqNKl1esc0OCYVALbnf18
DS4Skills	09/29/2025	Promotion of CATALISI webinar . D4SKILLS		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7378726368064286720/?actorCompanyId=90950711
KTU	10/02/2025	International Social Innovation Research Conference (ISIRC2025)	Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_isirc2025-livinglabs-counselling-activity-7370983141609607168-ZIDe?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABQLA4UBkNN9OzjqNKl1esc0OCYVALbnf18
EU Newsletter	10/02/2025	Connecting regions, empowering universities through stronger R&I policies	Media Article	https://eunewsletter.eu/connecting-regions-empowering-universities-through-stronger-ri-policies/
Inspiring ERA	10/14/2025	Inspiring ERA newsletter	Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/2ec0b097fd11/inspiring-era-newsletter-17270035?e=7399aef2dc#CATALISI
GILL	10/14/2025	GILL section about CATALISI	Media Article	https://gi-ll.eu/gill-and-catalisi-collaborate-to-foster-an-inclusive-innovation-ecosystem-in-europe/

SKILLS4E OSC	10/14/2 025	CATALISI Final conference	Media Article	https://www.skills4eosc.eu/news/catalisi-final-conference-to-take-place-on-11-november-2025-in-amsterdam
UJI	10/20/2 025	Open Access Week 2025	Media Article	https://www.uji.es/serveis/cd/base/reservori/2025/setmanAO2025/
UJI	10/20/2 025	Open Access Week 2025	Media outlet	https://www.vivecastellon.com/noticario/la-semana-del-acceso-abierto-en-la-uji-impulsa-la-ciencia-abierta-con-la-presentacion-del-distintivo-os-uji-y-el-nuevo-portal-de-materiales-docentes-48439.html
Luiss	2025	Luiss's Transition Towards Open Science: A Look at the Italian Landscape	Article	Luiss's Transition Towards Open Science: A Look at the Italian Landscape - CATALISI
Luiss	11/12/20 23	Research and Third Mission at Luiss University - 2/2023	Newsletter	Newsletter 2/2023
Luiss	16/04/2 024	Research and Third Mission at Luiss University - Newsbook 1/2024	Newsletter	R&TM Newsletter 1.2024
Luiss	11/12/20 24	Research and Third Mission at Luiss University - Newsbook 3/2024	Newsletter	R&TM Newsletter 3.2024
Luiss	20/03/2 023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	21/03/2 023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	17/04/2 023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	18/04/2 023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	15/05/2 023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	16/05/2 023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication

Luiss	20/06/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	06/07/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for ENGAGE.EU	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	10/07/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Marie Curie	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	25/07/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	26/07/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	18/09/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	19/09/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	17/10/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	20/11/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	21/11/2023	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	22/01/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	23/01/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	19/02/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	20/02/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication

Luiss	18/03/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	19/03/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	22/04/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	23/04/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	20/05/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	21/05/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	17/06/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	18/06/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	22/07/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	23/07/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	16/09/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	17/09/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	21/10/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	22/10/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication

Luiss	18/11/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	19/11/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	17/12/2024	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	20/01/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	21/01/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	18/02/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals + 1 Forth	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	17/03/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	18/03/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	22/04/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	23/04/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	26/05/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	27/05/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	16/06/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	17/06/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication

Luiss	28/07/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	29/07/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	23/09/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	20/10/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Forthcoming Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	23/09/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	24/11/2025	Luiss Research Funding Opportunities_Open Calls for Proposals	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	03/07/2023	Research Training Opportunities_Catalisi Workshop	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	31/08/2023	Luiss Research EU Funding Research Project_Catalisi Survey	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	08/02/2024	Luiss Research EU Funded Research Project_CATALISI Workshop	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	13/02/2024	Luiss Research EU Funded Research Project_CATALISI Workshop_REMINDER	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	08/10/2024	Luiss Research EU Funded Research Project_CATALISI MML Event	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	14/10/2024	Luiss Research Research Project_CATALISI MML Event REMINDER	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	14/10/2024	Luiss Research Research Project_CATALISI MML Event REMINDER	Newsletter	Internal communication
Luiss	10/12/2025	Luiss Research Open Science Survey	Newsletter	Internal communication

UCC	May 25	Public Engagement and Outreach, UCC and ENoLL	Website and social media	Webinar
UCC	June 25	Article - Catalisi partner providing global leadership on impact assessment	Website and social media	Article
UCC	July 23	Article on UCC's Change agenda in Catalisi	Website and social media	Article, In person event and workshop
KTU	Oct 2024	Information about MML	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_transformationalchange-catalisi-acceleration-services-activity-7253337126237356032-QNdJ?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAE RLXIBMhbTrHb2lbnVoWDgW/WJjTIS18FM
KTU	Sept 25	Information on presentation of CATALISI results at ISIRC 2025	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_isirc2025-socialinnovation-catalisi-activity-7358446272011223041-z6VS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAE RLXIBMhbTrHb2lbnVoWDgW/WJjTIS18FM
KTU	Sep 2025	Information about the webinar	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_ktu-success-story-webinar-activity-7364226305606721536-5Ul8?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAE RLXIBMhbTrHb2lbnVoWDgW/WJjTIS18FM
KTU	Sept 2025	Information about the presentation of results of CATALISI in ISIRC 2025	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_isirc2025-livinglabs-counselling-activity-7370983141609607168-ZIDe?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAE RLXIBMhbTrHb2lbnVoWDgW/WJjTIS18FM
KTU	Nov 2025	Information about presentation of CATALISI results in EMES 2025	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_emes2025-socialenterprise-socialinnovation-activity-7391833793310924800-

				rslv?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAE RLXIBMhbTrHb2lbnVoWDgWWJtIS18FM
KTU	Nov 2025	Information about CATALISI final conference	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_highereducation-institutionalchange-researchculture-activity-7394463159182319616-hMsT?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAE RLXIBMhbTrHb2lbnVoWDgWWJtIS18FM
KTU	Nov 2025	Information about presentation of CATALISI results in WAPOR 2025 and ACE 2025	Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eglebutkeviciene_environmentaleducation-ocean-waterliteracy-activity-7400038160044560385-MJSX?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAE RLXIBMhbTrHb2lbnVoWDgWWJtIS18FM

CATALISI EXTERNAL EVENTS

Name of the event	Date	Partner participant	Type of event	Impact
ETHNA conference	7/3/2023	UJI	Conference	CATALISI team had the opportunity to participate in the ETHNA SYSTEM Final Conference on Ethics and Responsible Research and Innovation in Practice in Castellón de la Plana (Spain).
NCP WIDERA.NET workshop	5/30/2023	APRE	Workshop and training event	Workshop/ Training Event for WIDERA National Contact Points with the sister projects to present approaches to supporting HEIs in implementing strategies and individual pathways for institutional transformation.
Symposium of the Spanish Association of Ethics and Political Philosophy of Spain	2/7/2024	UJI	Education and training events	Symposium of the Spanish Association of Ethics and Political Philosophy of Spain (with special emphasis on the evaluation system). To publicise the CATALISI project and to consult initiatives on scientific evaluation that are being adopted by other institutions in the Spanish context.
Participation in the 8th conference on research integrity	6/2-5/2024	UJI and AUTH	Conferences	To disseminate CATALISI project goals and current outcomes among the academic community. A poster has been submitted also a brief lecture on research integrity at UJI delivered
The Netherlands Research Integrity Network (NRIN) webinar	6/24/2024	AUMC	Webinar	Dr. Serge Horbach (Radboud University), who presented the outcomes of a study on researchers' perceptions of the ethics and integrity of using GenAI
IIAS - International Institute of Administrative	7/1-5/2024	KTU	Conference	KTU presented results of the CATALISI project, speaking about transformational changes at universities towards strengthening

Sciences conference 2024				capacities of human resources, together with Egle Vaidelyte. This presentation included findings from stakeholder workshops, that were organized to develop strategic steps towards implementing transformational changes at Kaunas
Open Living Lab Days (OLLD) 2024 – CATALISI side event “Opening universities to stakeholders through Living Labs for institutional transformation”	9/24/2024	ENoLL, APRE	Workshop	This workshop was organized in response to the growing challenges that Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) face in engaging with external stakeholders. The session aimed to co-develop strategies to foster stakeholder collaboration and enhance the accessibility of universities, aiming to support mutually beneficial transformations within academic institutions across Europe. CATALISI project and the Acting Living Lab acceleration service were presented.
3rd ERA EXCHANGE & MUTUAL LEARNING at NCP WIDERA meeting	10/24/2024	APRE	Conferences and Collaboration with EU funded projects (NCP Widera)	Dissemination of the project acceleration service and methodology with a focus on Capacity Building Acceleration Service (MML and Twinning exchanges), methodology, results and processes.
V Jornades d'Ètica de la Investigació:	9/25-27/2024	UJI	Conferences	An essential forum for debate and reflection on issues related to research ethics, open science and scientific evaluation systems.
EUA Funding Forum 2024, Helsinki	10/1-5/2024	UCC	Conferences	A Living Lab Approach to the Financial Sustainability of Research University College Cork (UCC) EUA Funding Forum 2024, Helsinki
CATALISI participates in the REINFORCING ORRI Conference	10/11/2024	APRE	Conferences and Collaboration with EU projects	Presented the CATALISI Capacity Building Acceleration Service for European HEIs in a dedicated workshop, where they had the opportunity to share the methodology and first successful results of mutual learning, peer

				learning and Twinning activities carried out with the aim to support transformational pathways of European HEIs.
UJI Open Access week	10/22-23/2024	UJI	Conferences	An annual event on a global scale to promote open access to research and open science, this year with the motto: " Who owns our knowledge? ", to raise awareness of the benefits of open access.
2024 EUA Funding Forum	11/3-4/2024	UCC	Conferences	present the UCC CATALISI Living Lab initiative on the sustainability of research financing. The event had significant attendance from the European Commission, Ministers of Education, Funding Agencies and University policy makers - which make this a high impact dissemination activity for CATALISI.
Open Living Lab Days 2024- CATALISI Side Event Opening universities to Stakeholders through Living Labs for Institutional transformation	11/15/2024	ENoLL	Education and training events	This workshop was organized in response to the growing challenges that Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) face in engaging with external stakeholders. The session aimed to co-develop strategies to foster stakeholder collaboration and enhance the accessibility of universities, aiming to support mutually beneficial transformations within academic institutions across Europe.
Meeting with AuPAEU	4/24/2025	F6S	Meetings	CATALISI was invited to discuss Agora capabilities
INORMS: "Enhancing Policy Impact and Excellence in EU-Funded Research: The Role of Research Managers"	5/8/2025	APRE	Conference and collaboration with EU projects	A conference to align on the policy impact of the ERA - CATALISI insights in a panel discussion together with VERITY, PATTERN, iRECs, RE4Green and other projects
EDUC. Improving the Metodology for Assessing Scientific Research in Ukraine:	May 2025	UJI		Online Presentation: Towards a Responsible use of Metrics in Research Evaluation. Ramón A. Feenstra

Experience of EU Countries				
Training at Karolinska Institutet	6/23/2025	AUTH	Education and training events	AUTH delivered a presentation and training session on Open Science and Open Data, highlighting it as a key intervention within the CATALISI project and an essential part of the broader effort toward Higher Education Institutional Transformation.
Course Science and Public Policy Summer university UJI	6/25/2025	UJI		Course Science and Public Policy Summer university UJI
INTERNATIONAL SOCIAL INNOVATION RESEARCH CONFERENCE 2025	9/4/2025	KTU	Conference	CATALISI poster presentation: Fostering Social Innovations through Acceleration Services: a Case of CATALISI Project Egle Butkeviciene
VI Ethics in Research Ethics Conference: CoARA and the Reform of the Evaluation System	09/24/2025	UJI	Conference	VI Ethics in Research Ethics Conference: CoARA and the Reform of the Evaluation System
Connecting regions, empowering universities through stronger R&I policies (INTERREG event)	10/2/2025	APRE	Collaboration with EU funded projects	The event brought together Interreg Europe project partners, regional policymakers, university representatives, and Horizon Europe stakeholders to discuss effective policy solutions and share good practices from across Europe. Around 70 participants participated in the online event. CATALISI participated together with the sister projects aUPaEU and Accelerate Future HEI
Open Access Week 2025	10/20/2025	UJI		Open Access Week 2025

LLNet conference	05/30/2025	KTU	Conference on Living Labs	CATALISI presentation: Exploring Living Labs approach: a case study of CATALISI project Egle Butkeviciene
Summer School for Early Career Researchers Methodological Perspectives for Social Research on Energy and Environmental Issues Organized by ESA RN12 Environment & Society, jointly with Energy and Society Network	09/22/2025	KTU	Summer School for Early Career Researchers	Plenary presentation and discussion: Citizen Science for Building Resilience: Environmental Social Research Perspective Eglė Butkevičienė
IASIA 2025 international conference	10/15/2025	KTU	Conference	CATALISI presentation: Building Capacities and Competences for Future Public Service Professionals: the Role of University Eglė Butkevičienė
EMES 2025 international conference	11/2-7/2025	KTU	Conference	CATALISI presentation in the session "SE Ecosystems 1: Cross-country & Comparative Studies" Eglė Butkevičienė
WAPOR 2025 international conference	11/23-21/2025	KTU	Conference	Poster presentation on CATALISI results Eglė Butkevičienė
IAFOR 2025 international conference	11/23-27/2025	KTU	Conference	Poster presentation on CATALISI results Eglė Butkevičienė
OPEN LIVING LABS DAYS Conference	11/1-3/2025	UCC	Conference	Matteo Palloca on UCC's use of living Labs in Catalisi to accelerate institutional change.

<p>Conference on Research Careers (closed session) ERA structural policy 'Improving the Articulation between R&I and Higher Education Within the ERA and Unleashing the Full Potential of European R&I Ecosystems'</p>	<p>12/12/2025</p>	<p>APRE</p>	<p>Conference and Collaboration with EU projects and the EC</p>	<p>How to improve alignment between EU and MS on R&I. APRE presents the Draft joint policy recommendations for joint policy brief developed by the three Horizon Europe sister-projects CATALISI, Accelerate Future HEI and aUPaEU, working to promote institutional transformation across European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) through the development and use of acceleration services.</p>
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Annex 4: CATALISI Exploitation Questionnaire

EXPLOITATION QUESTIONNAIRE

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Foreword and terms

Dear partners,

Following the discussion about exploitation and Key exploitable results (KERs) during the online exploitation workshops, we would like to delve deeper into your perspectives and better comprehend your expectations for the CATALISI exploitation strategy. This will enable us to customise our approach and tools effectively for executing the process.

Please take time to fill in this questionnaire which will help the F6S team to collect partners' vision and ideas regarding the sustainability and exploitation of the results from the CATALISI project. The ideas collected will be analysed, in order to identify the possibilities for further deployment and exploitation of the results and outcomes of the project.

Task	5.4 Exploitation activities and preparation
Period of project implementation	M1-M32
Leader	F6S
Contributors	All
Deliverable	D5.2 - Final Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability plans

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What is Exploitation?

Exploitation

"The use of results in **further research and innovation** activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, **commercial exploitation** such as developing, creating manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in **standardization activities**."

- Value generated beyond the project duration (impact)
- Results with use to a broader audience

Exploitation aims to make a concrete use of the project results for commercial, societal or political purposes.

Key Terms

Result

Results include the actions **tangible effects** – data, prototype, product and intangible effects know-how, formulas, as well as any attached rights (e.g. patent rights and database rights).

The result typically has defined **target stakeholder** groups, and usage either as a self-contained product/service or as a constituent part of a broader scheme of solutions within any other project, product, service, research initiative or wider application.

Key Exploitable Result (KER)

KER (or Key Exploitable Results) are the selected subset of the above ERs (designated as "key") which present, according to the consortium view, the **biggest potential in innovation, exploitability, market impact and readiness to market launch**.

Background – means any data, know-how or information (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights – that is: (a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and (b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results (AGA, p.180)

Foreground – results developed during the project for which it should be established whether they are individually or jointly owned by partners depending on their inputs

Owner – the person/entity which has generated the results

Exploitation of results (from the grant agreement)

*Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant **must – up to four years after the end of the action** – use their best efforts to **exploit their results** directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing.

not

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Who is Involved:

- Researchers
- Industry, incl. SMEs
- Those that can make a good use of the results: authorities, policymakers, sectors of interest, civil society, etc.

How it's done:

- Creating roadmaps, prototypes
- Sharing knowledge, skills, data

Why?

- Lead to new legislation or recommendations
- For the benefit of innovation, the economy and the society
- Help to tackle a problem and respond to an existing demand

not

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Questionnaire

SECTION 1: CATALISI PROJECT RESULTS

Below, please provide details regarding **all project results** you can identify.

A result can be any tangible or intangible output of the project, such as data, knowledge, and information whatever their form or nature. In the broader sense, they can be commercial, societal, political, or for improving public knowledge and action. This list should be extensive and should contain all project results, including KERs and OERs

Add rows as necessary.

1. --
2. --
3. --
4. --

Each organisation reviews its results considering the following **criteria** in mind:

1. Can it be exploited by my organization with the purpose to reach a larger stakeholder group?
2. How will my organization exploit it?
3. Can it be exploited by more than one partner in the consortium?
4. Can it be considered as part of another result within the project? - If "yes" then the larger result might be considered as an exploitable result, instead of this one.

We have prepared a table listing all expected results in the CATALISI project - in **ANNEX A**.

In this table we already included the partners' ideas and contribution collected during the exploitation workshops conducted during the General Assembly, as well as the online workshops with facilitators and implementors in the summer of 2024.

Please use the **ANNEX A**, when filling in your contribution, as well as if you need some reminders of the expected results or to charge some ideas from the previous discussions.

SECTION 2: KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS (KERs)

A **Key Exploitable Result (KER)** is an identified main interesting result (as defined above) which has been **selected and prioritised** due to its high potential to be "exploited" - meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

In order for you to **select and prioritise** your results use the following criteria:

- a) degree of innovation
- b) exploitability
- c) impact

Please provide information regarding the project's identified KERs.

If at this stage you have any other consideration in terms of KER grouping and identification, you can list them in the table below.

Please take under consideration that if all 7 acceleration services of CATALISI will be as well exploited together as a product and a holistic service (for e.g. through the Marketplace/a platform) this should be indicated and constitute a KER as well.

KER (please see ANNEX A)	DESCRIPTION OF POTENTIAL ¹ (elaborate on the selected choice)	OF HIGH	MARKET MATURITY ²
KER 1:			
KER 2:			
KER 3:			

Please mark with "x" the KERs your organisation will contribute to:

¹ High scientific potential; High societal potential (other than climate or environmental); High societal potential; High technological, business or economic potential; High policy or regulatory potential; Other

² Not yet existing and not clear if market can be created; Market creating; not existing but potential for the creation of a new market; Emerging; growing demand, scarce supply; Mature: the market is already supplied with similar products

KER 1:	
KER 2:	
KER 3:	

Please fill in information regarding your contribution to each of the KERs you have selected. What are you developing as part of the KER? (Foreground IPR identification)

Background IP (existing IP, before project start) related to KERs

Does any of the selected KERs rely on any existing IP/background IP. What is it? How does it relate to the development of the KER? Is it owned by your organisation or a third party? How is this background IP protected?

SECTION 3: OTHER EXPLOITABLE RESULTS (OERs)

In the table below, mark the OERs you are interested in and add any additional ones you might consider

OER NAME	TYPE OF RESULT ³	DESCRIPTION	Interested (Y/N)

BEFORE YOU CONTINUE FURTHER PLEASE REFLECT ON THESE QUESTIONS:

- In which areas might the work and results in CATALISI altogether create more impact in the future?
- Which of the KERs would you use / develop further?
- Where in the strategic planning of your organization/institution do you see the usage of the CATALISI results? Does any of these results fits into the usual activities and / or vision for future activities?
- Do you expect to reach the market with the selected KERs? If not, is a future development needed in order to prepare them for market? Can you elaborate on your opinion what is needed?

At this stage you may need to discuss and consult internally the approach towards the selected KER and the exploitation paths envisioned.

SECTION 4: INDIVIDUAL AND COMMON EXPLOITATION PLANS

At this stage we recognize three main possible exploitation models for the project results:

- 1) the research exploitation model
- 2) the commercial exploitation model
- 3) the technological exploitation model (not really applicable?)

³ Software; Workflow; Protocol; Prototype; Other

What is your Individual Exploitation Plan - research; commercial; technological; standardisation? Provide information considering the results you are interested in. Indicate the result and anticipated plan at this stage. Please provide a concise overview of the steps you plan to take in order to carry out your envisioned individual exploitation activities.

Considering the research model CATALISI focuses on three main options:

Intended exploitation:

- (1) Use in future projects
- (2) Internal service development
- (3) Dissemination and capacity building
- (4) Other (please specify)

Based on the information provided, we would like to investigate further your interest, so please respond to the questions below:

Intensity of interest

Please indicate your organization interest using the colour coding (and colour the cell as shown in the example below):

High / Moderate / Low

KER / Intended exploitation (research)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
KER 1: -1 replicable framework of acceleration services				
KER 2: -1 coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various areas				
KER 3:				

Please, indicate if according to your opinion each of the identified KERs should be exploited as a standalone product/ service (**commercial**) and whether the two or more KERs can be exploited together (as a group)?

As an organisation are you willing to lead the exploitation of a KER?

Yes (indicate which KER are you interested in) / No

As an organisation would you like to take part in a common exploitation?

Yes/No

If you are interested in commercial exploitation, would you be able to secure funds and resources for further development and promotion of the KER (after projects ends)? If "yes" please describe.

Please indicate the consortium partners you are willing to collaborate with for the various exploitation paths (research (R); technological (T); commercialization (C); standardization (S) by marking with an "x" the selected ones.

PARTNER	R	T	C	S
APRE				
EY				
F6S				
ENoLL				
KTU				

UJI				
LUISS				
UG				
UCC				
AUTH				
VUMC				

Describe the potential collaboration with each of the partners you have selected:

Strategic alliances: In the CATALISI GA there is opportunity foreseen for establishment of strategic alliances. In this regard, do you see opportunities for future collaboration in exploitation of the project KERs and formation of strategic alliances? What could be the ground for cooperation and with who?
 Please elaborate on the: Strategic Alliance(s) goals, scope, participants, activities, etc.:

Share any other ideas you may have on the exploitation plan

Useful references:

Result types:

- IPROD – Product (new or improved)
- ISERV – Service (new or improved)
- IPROC – Industrial process (new or improved)
- IBUS – Business model (new or improved)
- IDSG – Design (new or improved)
- IMETH – Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)
- IPO – Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy
- IEVNT – Event (conference, seminar, workshop)
- ISTAFF – (qualified personnel exchanges)
- ILEARN – learning and training (learning modules, curricula)

Potential exploitation paths:

- **Individual exploitation plans:** Specific strategies will be developed to derive the highest benefit from a partner's involvement in the Project. These strategies aim to optimize the utilization of project outcomes, ensuring the most efficient and effective utilization.
- **Open-source Community:** The focus will be on creating a thriving community to drive the exploitation of the CATALISI marketplace (HUB) and platform beyond the Project.
- **Joint Exploitation:** This approach could include a commercial offering for HEIs and other organizations looking to adopt the CATALISI framework for acceleration services.

What's next?

- The **exploitation strategy** will comprise different phases including value proposition and strategic alliances.
- For all exploitable results, a **dedicated sustainability plan** will be developed. This includes market and competition analysis, SWOT and PESTLE analysis in order to define the external proposition of marketing activities and seeking of additional funding opportunities, in collaboration with the next task.

ANNEX A: CATALYST LIST OF POTENTIAL KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

RESULT NAME	WP	Partners Involved in development (potentially named)	INDICATE WHETHER KER/OTHER/OTHER	RESULT TYPE*	Possible exploitation paths (in bold are introduced the notes taken during the General Assembly)	AUDIENCE/TARGET GROUP
ERs 1 replicable framework of acceleration services		APRE?		SERV Portfolio of services (description, validated through R4?)	APRE/ course for APRE associates on acceleration services	
ERs 1 coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various areas				SERV	Coaching & support for institutional transformation in Open Data, IP sharing, crowdsourcing	
ER3 1 Market Place CATALYST Marketplace (The CATALYST HUB) (D5.1)	WP 3		NER Online Single Entry Point showcasing different services offered by CATALIST partners and different learning opportunities, such as matchmaking events with SMEs, learning hub, coaching	SERV? BUS?	ER3-Marketplace URL not listed one WP www.marketplace-tool.com/api/marketplace-tool/	

* PROD – Product (new or improved); SERV – Service (new or improved); PROC – Industrial process (new or improved); BUS – Business model (new or improved); DES – Design (new or improved); METH – Method, material, technology, design (new or improved); PO – Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy; EVNT – Event (conference, seminar, workshop); STAFF – (qualified) personnel exchange; LEARN – learning and training (learning modules, courses); OTHER

? If the result is an OER the result type can be one of the following: Software; Workflow; Protocol; Prototype; Other

					and funding opportunities (BUSINESS CASE: CATALIST Marketplace (The CATALYST HUB) for research commercialisation and innovation	
ER4 1 methodology for an investment strategy that facilitates the access of HEIs and surrounding ecosystems' access to resources that will support the delivery of the chosen institutional transformations.				SERV	METH? Knowledge sharing?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RI system which is an open-source platform-universities/researchers & businesses exchange data through a standardized/for way MOOCs-Lifelong learning specially in the medical department VUMC- (methodology) we can also edit together (which is a direct KER)
ER5 7 Individual strategy and agenda setting elaborated to support a long term sustainable institutional transformation.				SERV	METH? Knowledge sharing?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> alumni oriented life-long education program (micro-modules training) UG-se have one report include sustainable institutional transformation, will be updated? ATU-a digital platform for matchmaking scientific interests + interest to participate in research

ER6 7 acting Living labs that support the institutional transformation established Living Labs (D5.1)	WP 1		This service aims at guiding and mentoring implementers on co-creation methodologies and competencies in line with the Living Lab (LL) methodology. This will enable the institutional transformation of HEIs (acting-LLs) into user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings BUSINESS CASE: Living Labs for open innovation ecosystems	SERV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Living labs to train user in establishing their own LL Benefit our network from learned lessons when it comes to stakeholder engagement UCC-financial sustainability of research financial sustainability of research outputs: policy brief toolkit to support transferability, resource hub UCC, ATU-financial sustainability of research, webinar, expert training 	
ER7 7 Action-plan to support the utilization of acceleration services			This is not a KER but an exploitation path of the LL (AG)	NOT EXPLOIT / its a product of the LL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UG-ER7 Action plan to support 	
ER8 1 Predictive Study		EV/Owner?			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> predictive study event (in person or online) on results, email study to all stakeholders involved in data collection 	
ER9 1 Learning hub realized Learning Hub (D5.1)	WP 2		BUSINESS CASE: Learning hub for the implementation of actions leading to institutional transformation.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UG-se have SEA-UE MOOC 	

ER12 1 model for mutual knowledge sharing among the implementers				SERV acceleration services	Knowledge sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UG as partner model for mutual knowledge sharing APRE-training module for universities (APRE members) on mutual knowledge sharing
ER13 1 Community of practice to build a consensus building on institutional transformation				NOT EXPLOIT? Sustaining? KER?		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VUMC-Co-P-Building a network of teachers, coordinator WUT/NER- citizen science hub APRE-European community of experts/professionals in the field of R&I
ER14 At least to Collaboration established with other European initiatives				NOT EXPLOIT, COMBINED IN R4? Not KER, an outcome?	Collaboration in Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UG's collaboration established with other European initiatives (eg support of SEA-UE partners in strategic team for report)
ER15 1 Policy Recommendation Policy Briefing (D5.1)	WP 4 and WP 5			PO	Policy feedback on the acceleration services, and widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups to promote Reform and increase trust in science and R&I outcomes, also	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> policy 'two' exploit the 'recon' by EoLL Wg on Education build-on the results 14-VUMC-policy recommendations, research culture, training in RCR, policy makers, R coordinators/educational

Annex 5: CATALISI Exploitation documents set for the 3 KERs (Horizon Booster templates)

Characterization tables

Characterisation table

Project Acronym	CATALISI
HRBOOSTER Expert	PAOLA AMATO

Version	Date	Elaborated by	Notes
V0	16/07/2025	PAOLA AMATO	BOOSTER TEMPLATE (10/03/2025)
V1	16/09/2025	Stefania Laneve (APRE)	Filled in by APRE (for KER1)
V2	19/09/2025	Violeta Naydenova (F6S)	Suggested (and accepted) adjustments to KER1 and add-ons on behalf of the CATALISI Exploitation Lead F6S
V3	25/09/2025	Mariam Chakroun (ENoLL)	Filled in by ENoLL (for KER3)
V4	06/10/2025	Subida Dermami (EY)	Filled in by EY (for KER2)
V5	08/10/2025	Violeta Naydenova (F6S)	Consolidating the 3 KERs in one document and final adjustments and formatting on behalf of the CATALISI Exploitation Lead F6S

KER name: Multi-level knowledge sharing service strengthening HEI international competitiveness and achieving institutional reforms (KER1)	
	Input from the Beneficiary
Description	Our multi-level knowledge sharing service helps institutional change agents in Higher Education who aim to strengthen their institution's international competitiveness and implement meaningful reforms, by providing structured, peer-driven learning processes that reduce capacity gaps, internal fragmentation and resistance to change, and by enabling the co-creation of tailored transformation strategies aligned with EU priorities, boosting institutional visibility and fostering long-term collaboration across the R&I landscape, unlike traditional, top-down consultancy or training models that lack contextual adaptation, mutual learning and sustained stakeholder engagement.
Target market/end users	The target market is the Higher Education sector in Europe, with a focus on institutions engaged in governance reform and institutional transformation to enhance competitiveness, cooperation, and alignment with societal needs. Within this market, there is a growing demand for participatory, knowledge-sharing approaches that go beyond traditional consultancy to deliver sustainable institutional change. The customers and end-users are actors responsible for initiating and managing institutional change in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This includes academic staff in charge of strategy and development, research managers and support staff implementing change, heads of departments reforming research practices, project managers and

	administrators coordinating EU-funded reforms, as well as rectors, vice-rectors, and delegates for research, innovation, or quality. To sum-up, these end-users can be described as institutional actors responsible and/or engaged in academic governance, who seek tools and processes to design, implement, and sustain transformation strategies that strengthen their institutions' international competitiveness and make science more responsive to societal needs.
End-users needs / problems	Potential end-users in Higher Education institutions (HEIs) encounter several barriers when pursuing institutional reforms. They often face a lack of internal capacity to design and manage complex transformation processes, constrained by limited time, fragmented resources, and high effort. At the same time, they suffer from low visibility of good practices and peer experiences, making it difficult to learn from or adapt models tested in other institutions. The absence of trusted external guidance, especially from peers or facilitators with direct expertise in institutional change, further limits their ability to move forward effectively. Finally, fragmented internal communication hampers engagement with key stakeholders, slowing down consensus building and the implementation of reforms. The KER addresses these needs by offering a structured capacity-building and outreach service designed to support HEIs in planning and implementing institutional transformation strategies to enhance cooperation and international competitiveness. The service combines Mutual Learning Workshops and Twinning exchanges to foster peer-to-peer learning and co-creation. The KER also reduces complexity, facilitates access to proven approaches, strengthens institutional capacities, and creates a collaborative environment for sustainable transformation.
Competitive advantages	The KER offers a clear competitive advantage compared to traditional consultancy or training approaches, which are often top-down, generic, and disconnected from the real challenges of Higher Education institutions (HEIs). Unlike such solutions, this service is built on a peer-driven and multi-level knowledge-sharing model that directly addresses the end-users' pains and desired gains. It alleviates core problems, such as lack of internal capacity, fragmented communication, and absence of trusted guidance, by providing structured support, tested methodologies, and safe spaces for exchange among peers facing similar challenges. At the same time, it creates long-term benefits by empowering change actors to lead transformation, strengthening cross-institutional networks, and fostering collaboration and trust within HEIs. What distinguishes the KER is its combination of mobilisation and mutual learning (MML) workshops and twinning exchanges, which ensure contextualised, participatory, and adaptable support tailored to each institution's needs. This approach not only accelerates institutional reforms but also enhances HEIs' international competitiveness and reputation, delivering sustainable impact that competing solutions often fail to achieve.
Use model	The KER will be put into use through the provision of a service, specifically a multi-level knowledge-sharing and capacity-building service for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The use model is based on the delivery of Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops and Twinning exchanges, offered as structured activities that can be tailored to the specific needs and priorities of each institution. The service will be made available to potential adopters (universities, alliances of HEIs, or other academic organisations) either as a stand-alone offer or as a component of broader European or nationally funded projects. It can also be integrated into institutional development strategies as a recurring capacity-building tool.

	<p>In practice, the use model relies on contracted service provision: APRE will deliver the methodology and facilitation, while HEIs adopt and implement the service to design and manage institutional transformation processes. This model ensures scalability, flexibility, and adaptability, making the KER accessible across different institutional contexts. In particular, to maximise flexibility and scalability, the service can be deployed through multiple complementary formats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consulting provision, positioning APRE as service providers for HEIs. • Digital self-service toolkit, a modular online resource including roadmap templates, KPIs, stakeholder mapping frameworks, and planning guides for MML and Twinning activities, available either freely or through tiered access (e.g. premium for APRE members). • Partnership agreements with experienced HEIs (e.g. from CATALISI) to host Twinning visits. • Integration into future EU or national projects, where the KER can be embedded as a methodology or dedicated work package (e.g. WIDERA, Reforming R&I). • Member benefit, offering the service or parts of it as a value-added tool for APRE members to increase engagement and loyalty.
Early Adopters	<p>The early adopters of the service are expected to be Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) that are already engaged in or planning institutional reforms, and therefore feel most strongly the pains of lacking internal capacity, limited visibility of good practices, and fragmented stakeholder engagement. In particular, universities involved in EU-funded projects on R&I reform (e.g. WIDERA, ERA, Reforming R&I calls), members of university alliances, and institutions seeking to improve their competitiveness and international visibility represent the most promising early adopters.</p> <p>To reach them, multiple channels will be activated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APRE's network and membership base, especially Italian HEIs already engaged in R&I initiatives; • EU-level networks and associations (e.g. EUA, Science Europe, European R&I alliances); • Dissemination through policy events and stakeholder workshops where institutional transformation is discussed; • Integration in Horizon Europe project proposals, where the service can be piloted with new partners; • Targeted communication campaigns (webinars, newsletters, casebook publications) showcasing benefits and success stories; • Direct outreach and twinning agreements with HEIs expressing interest in structured capacity-building support. <p>This approach ensures that the service is first adopted by institutions that are most motivated and ready to experiment, creating demonstrators and references that will facilitate scaling to a broader market.</p>
Adopters' problems/needs	<p>Potential adopters, e.g. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and their institutional change agents, face persistent challenges when implementing reforms. They often lack the internal capacity and resources to design and manage complex transformation processes, while also suffering from limited visibility of good practices and peer experiences that could inform their strategies. Many institutions also struggle with the absence of trusted external</p>

	<p>guidance to facilitate change, and with fragmented internal communication that makes it difficult to engage key stakeholders and build consensus.</p> <p>The service directly addresses these problems by offering a structured capacity-building and outreach service designed to support HEIs in planning and implementing institutional transformation strategies to enhance cooperation and international competitiveness. The service also provides a model that reduces uncertainty, provides access to validated approaches and case-based learning, empowers internal teams to co-design transformation pathways, and fosters collaboration within and across HEIs. In this way, adopters are supported in overcoming their main barriers to institutional change and in achieving greater competitiveness and alignment with EU priorities.</p>
Alternative solution	<p>So far, potential adopters in Higher Education Institutions have been addressing the challenges of institutional reform mainly through internal working groups, ad-hoc committees, and project-based initiatives often linked to EU or national funding. They rely on traditional consultancy or training services, which tend to be top-down, generic, and not fully adapted to their specific institutional contexts. Some institutions attempt to learn from peers informally, through bilateral collaborations or participation in European networks, alliances and staff mobilities exchanges (e.g. through the Erasmus+ programme), but these collaborations are usually fragmented and not structured for long-term impact.</p> <p>While these approaches provide partial support, they often result in limited ownership, discontinuity, and slow progress, leaving HEIs without a sustainable mechanism to build internal capacity, engage stakeholders effectively, and ensure alignment with EU policy priorities.</p>
Unique Value Proposition	<p>The competitive advantage of the KER lies in its multi-level knowledge-sharing model, which goes beyond the limits of traditional consultancy or training services. While alternative solutions are often generic, top-down, and disconnected from the specific challenges of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), the KER directly addresses adopters' needs by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing capacity gaps and internal fragmentation through structured, participatory processes that empower HEIs to co-design and own their transformation pathways. • Providing contextualised guidance based on tested methods and peer experiences, rather than one-size-fits-all recommendations. • Strengthening collaboration and trust both within institutions and across European HEIs, creating networks that outlast project cycles. • Aligning reforms with EU policy priorities (e.g. ERA, Open Science, Gender Equality), increasing institutional visibility and access to future funding opportunities. • Ensuring sustainability by combining direct facilitation (MML workshops, Twinning exchanges) with scalable formats such as toolkits, casebooks, and replication through trained providers. <p>In this way, the KER delivers more relevant, participatory, and long-lasting results than competing approaches, making it a unique asset for HEIs seeking to achieve meaningful reforms and enhance international competitiveness.</p>
Competitors	<p>Possible competitors are Consultancy agencies and training providers specialised in Higher Education management, education technology platforms and/or European university associations and networks.</p>

Possible Competitors	Strengths:	Weaknesses Compared to APRE:	APRE Advantage:
<p>Consultancy Agencies & Training Providers (Examples: Bain & Company, L.E.K. Consulting, European Quality Training & Management Consultancy)</p>	<p>Deep strategic expertise in higher education management, operational efficiency, and digital transformation.</p> <p>Proven methodologies and global experience across sectors.</p> <p>Access to high-level decision-makers and tailored executive training.</p>	<p>Often expensive and inaccessible for smaller or less-resourced HEIs.</p> <p>Focused on short-term consulting engagements rather than long-term ecosystem building.</p> <p>Limited integration with EU policy frameworks and funding mechanisms.</p> <p>Less emphasis on peer-to-peer knowledge sharing and community-driven reform.</p>	<p>Offers a collaborative, multi-level approach rooted in EU transformation agendas.</p> <p>Builds capacity through shared learning, not just top-down consulting.</p> <p>More accessible and mission-aligned for public HEIs seeking systemic change.</p>
<p>Education Technology Platforms (Examples: WeUni, OPIT, European Digital Education Hub)</p>	<p>Scalable digital tools for learning, student engagement, and institutional performance.</p> <p>Strong alignment with digital transformation and workforce readiness.</p> <p>Innovative use of AI, micro-credentials, and online delivery models.</p>	<p>Primarily focused on teaching and learning—not institutional governance or strategic reform.</p> <p>Often product-driven rather than process-oriented.</p> <p>Limited capacity for policy alignment or multi-stakeholder engagement.</p>	<p>Goes beyond digital delivery to support structural transformation and international positioning.</p> <p>Facilitates cross-sector dialogue and policy integration.</p> <p>Tailors support to institutional maturity and reform goals—not just tech adoption.</p>

	<p>European University Associations & Networks (Examples: European University Association (EUA), European Universities Alliances,)</p>	<p>Strong policy influence and advocacy at EU level.</p> <p>Established peer-learning structures and thematic working groups.</p> <p>Deep understanding of European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and ERA priorities.</p>	<p>Services often limited to members or alliance partners.</p> <p>Focused more on coordination and policy dialogue than on hands-on institutional support.</p> <p>May lack operational capacity to deliver tailored transformation services.</p>	<p>Offers direct, actionable support for institutional reform—not just policy positioning.</p> <p>Bridges the gap between strategic vision and implementation.</p> <p>Open to a broader range of HEIs and ecosystems, fostering inclusivity and scalability.</p>
Timing	<p>The time to market for the KER is short to immediate, as the service has already been designed, tested, and validated within the CATALIS project through Mutual Learning Workshops and Twinning exchanges. The methodology is ready for uptake and can be deployed directly by APRE or trained partners.</p> <p>However, we would start working on its refinement starting from January 2026 (after the end of the project). We did not define a detailed and realistic timeline yet. We estimate that at least 1 year of work would be necessary to offer this service to APRE members, European university alliances and HEIs engaged in ongoing transformation initiatives.</p>			
IP Strategy	<p>We think that IP strategy is not relevant for our KER. We would like to use CC-BY licenses options.</p>			

KER name: Coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various research areas (KER2)	
	Input from the Beneficiary
Description	A consultancy service combining coaching and mentoring to support Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in designing and implementing institutional transformation strategies. The service includes workshops, one-on-one sessions, and digital resources, embedded in a broader ecosystem of acceleration services. It helps HEIs address complex change processes, align with EU policy agendas, and improve competitiveness and governance
Target market/end users	Target Market: HEIs across Europe, especially those engaged in or planning institutional transformation in research and innovation. End Users: University leadership, research managers, innovation officers, and transformation facilitators within HEIs
End-users needs / problems	HEIs face challenges in managing complex institutional change, accessing experienced external guidance, aligning reforms with EU frameworks, and building internal capacity for innovation and governance. The service addresses these needs by providing tailored support and strategic planning.
Competitive advantages	- Tailored, co-designed transformational pathways for each HEI - Integration of strategic and operational support - Embedded in a broader ecosystem (Living Labs, predictive studies, marketplaces) - Developed by EY with extensive experience in strategic consulting - Scalable and replicable across diverse contexts
Use model	Provision of a consultancy-style service, delivered through workshops, one-on-one sessions, and digital resources. Early adopters receive direct support, with potential for broader dissemination via the CATALISI Marketplace and policy engagement
Early Adopters	The seven HEIs participating in CATALISI as implementers, with outreach to other HEIs through dissemination and policy engagement channels.
Adopters' problems/needs	Adopters (HEIs) need effective strategies and support to manage institutional transformation, improve competitiveness, and align with EU priorities. They often lack internal capacity and require external expertise to drive change.
Alternative solution	Existing solutions include internal change management initiatives, ad-hoc consultancy, and participation in EU-funded projects. However, these often lack the tailored, integrated, and scalable approach offered by KER2.
Unique Value Proposition	KER2 offers a unique combination of tailored coaching, mentoring, and strategic planning, embedded in a broader ecosystem of support services. Its scalability, integration with EU policy, and proven methodology distinguish it from other solutions..
Competitors	Other consultancy firms, internal university change management teams, and EU-funded support projects. Competitors may offer similar services but often lack the integrated, scalable, and policy-aligned approach of KER2. Strengths: established networks, experience. Weaknesses: less tailored, less integrated
Timing	Service is ready for launch at the end of the project (Q4 2025), with immediate post-project exploitation possible
IP Strategy	No formal IP protection; the methodology is shared under open access principles aligned with Horizon Europe guidelines. Background: EY's expertise and prior work. Foreground: new methodologies and tools developed in CATALISI

KER name: Living Lab Methodology for institutional Transformation: A Practical Guide to Becoming a Living Lab (KER3)	
	Input from the Beneficiary
Description	A practical, institution-ready methodology that helps Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) adopt participatory, user-driven approaches—co-creation, real-life experimentation, and continuous feedback loops—to drive institutional transformation. The KER consists of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) a concise PDF guide explaining the methodology and the process used in CATALISI to define HEIs' action plans; (ii) training modules/webinars for staff, students, and stakeholders; and (iii) a comprehensive framework to evaluate Acting Living Labs. Together, these resources enable HEIs to embed Living Lab practices into strategies and transformation plans, making innovation more inclusive, relevant, and impactful. It directly addresses the widespread problem of fragmented and top-down innovation by offering a structured pathway for stakeholder engagement. It also helps HEIs overcome the challenge of translating technical research into practical, socially relevant solutions for their ecosystems.
Target market/end users	Primary market: universities and other institutions seeking to become Acting Living Labs and to structure institutional transformation with strong stakeholder engagement. End users include: (a) institutional transformation leads and senior administrators; (b) academic and professional services staff running engagement/innovation units; (c) student and external stakeholder groups participating in co-creation.
End-users needs / problems	HEIs struggle to translate stakeholder engagement into sustained institutional change: cooperation across internal/external actors is limited; open innovation practices remain underdeveloped; highly technical research often lacks accessibility and practical relevance for startups/SMEs and wider ecosystems; and diverse societal perspectives are not consistently integrated. End users need an applied, step-by-step way to organize co-creation in real settings and to connect it to institutional strategies. The KER responds by systematizing engagement into a methodology that links co-creation activities directly with institutional governance and transformation agendas.
Competitive advantages	This is the first formal pilot framework tailored specifically to HEIs operating as Living Labs for institutional transformation. Unlike generic innovation toolkits, it is purpose-built for academic contexts and pairs a methodology with training and an evaluation framework, emphasizing real-life experimentation and iterative engagement with diverse actors. This specialization and practical orientation give it a clear first-mover advantage. It uniquely addresses the problem that most existing tools are either too generic or too fragmented to create real institutional change in HEIs.
Use model	The KER will be put into use as a productised service package: open, downloadable guide; facilitated training/webinars; and an evaluation framework offered through ENOLL's service and capacity-building channels. HEIs can adopt the guide independently and/or contract facilitation, coaching, and evaluation support for implementation and scaling. This use model ensures that institutions no longer have to rely on ad-hoc workshops or disconnected toolkits, but instead gain an integrated pathway from learning to implementation and evaluation.
Early Adopters	Non-partner HEIs that are actively advancing "third mission" agendas (civic universities, engaged research), European University Alliances, and universities building or restructuring innovation/engagement units. Reach-out channels: ENOLL network communications,

	<p>thematic webinars, conference workshops, and targeted outreach to university networks and rectors' conferences.</p> <p>These early adopters face the most pressure to prove engagement impact, and the KER provides them with a ready-to-use solution instead of forcing them to build frameworks from scratch.</p>
Adopters' problems/needs	<p>Institutional leaders and innovation units need a credible, field-tested approach to (i) design engagement that is meaningful for citizens and partners, (ii) operationalise co-creation across faculties and external ecosystems, and (iii) connect these activities to governance, KPIs, and long-term transformation—without “reinventing the wheel.”</p> <p>The KER addresses this by combining methodology, training, and evaluation into one package, filling the current gap between practice and governance.</p>
Alternative solution	<p>Today, adopters piece together generic publications/toolkits, ad-hoc workshops/project-based learning, or broad Living Lab methodologies not specifically adapted to HEI transformation. These help in parts, but do not offer a single, integrated guide for becoming an Acting Living Lab at institutional level.</p> <p>The KER solves this by consolidating fragmented practices into a single, HEI-specific methodology that is coherent and scalable.</p>
Unique Value Proposition	<p>A HEI-specific, hands-on pathway that combines methodology + training + evaluation to institutionalise co-creation and real-world experimentation. It bridges the gap between engagement activities and organisational change by embedding stakeholder involvement and iterative learning into strategies, action plans, and governance—something generic toolkits rarely achieve. This directly addresses the problem of “pilot fatigue,” where engagement initiatives fail to scale or influence governance, by ensuring continuity and institutional embedment.</p>
Competitors	<p>Type 1: Generic innovation/engagement toolkits and publications (strength: breadth; weakness: not tailored to HEIs as Acting LLs).</p> <p>Type 2: Stand-alone workshops or project-based learning (strength: experiential; weakness: limited institutional embedment).</p> <p>Type 3: Broad Living Lab methodologies (strength: principles; weakness: lack of HEI-specific transformation guidance).</p> <p>The KER differentiates by offering a unified, HEI-tailored approach with evaluation to sustain adoption.</p> <p>This means HEIs no longer have to choose between broad but unfocused tools and narrow but non-scalable workshops—they gain both breadth and depth in one solution.</p>
Timing	Available immediately after project end
IP Strategy	<p>ENoLL will register the outcome as its intellectual property and manage rights for the guide, training materials, and evaluation framework. Background: existing ENoLL know-how and Living Lab expertise; Foreground: the CATALISI-developed HEI transformation methodology, training assets, and evaluation framework. Post-project, ENoLL will maintain, update, and license/use the materials in capacity-building services.</p>

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Exploitation Roadmap

The exploitation roadmap

Fill in the template thinking at what happens when your current project will finish.

Project Acronym	CATALISI		
HRBOOSTER Expert	PAOLA AMATO		
Version	Date	Elaborated by	Notes
V0	16/07/2025	PAOLA AMATO	BOOSTER TEMPLATE (10/03/2025)
V1	16/09/2025	Stefania Laneve (APRE)	Filled in by APRE (for KER1)
V2			
V3	25/09/2025	Mariem Chakroun (ENoLL)	Filled in by ENoLL (for KER3)
V4	06/10/2025	Suhida Dermami (EY)	Filled in by EY (for KER2)
V5	08/10/2025	Violeta Naydenova (F6S)	Consolidating the 3 KERs in one document and final adjustments and formatting on behalf of the CATALISI Exploitation Lead F6S

Exploitation roadmap for KER 1 - Multi-level knowledge sharing service strengthening HEI international competitiveness and achieving institutional reforms (KER1)	
Actions	<p><i>Briefly describe actions planned to be executed 3-6 months after the end of the project. Make sure you do not just focus on technical activities (realisation of a prototype, software interface, etc) but also consider the finalisation of a business plan, the protection of intellectual property, the collection of authorisations, all it will be needed to start implement what is in your exploitation plan.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refinement of the KER: definition of the service package (e.g. number and type of MML workshops, frequency of Twinning activities, optional add-ons), ensuring clarity for adopters. Finalisation of the business plan, including pricing models (consulting service, digital toolkit, premium membership). Definition of IP strategy (open-access vs premium content, licensing options, attribution rules). Preparation of a digital self-service toolkit (templates, KPIs, stakeholder mapping, guides) to ensure scalability. Identification and engagement of early adopters through APRE's network, EUA, alliances of universities. Formalisation of cooperation agreements with experienced HEIs (CATALISI implementers) to host Twinning visits. Integration of the KER into new EU/national project proposals (e.g., WIDERA, Reforming R&I, Erasmus+). Communication & dissemination actions, including casebook publication and dedicated webinars.
Roles	<p><i>Roles of partners involved in the actions defined above. Start with the identification of the organisation which will be the main responsible for the exploitation roadmap (exploiting the KER)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> APRE: main responsible for exploitation, business model design, service delivery, management of IP, and outreach to adopters. HEI partners (CATALISI implementers): provide feedback, act as reference cases, and host twinning activities. Other CATALISI partners: support integration of the KER into new proposals, dissemination, and promotion across European networks.
Milestones	<p><i>List the milestones and KPIs to be used for monitoring the implementation of the actions listed above. Add timeline.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> M1 (Month 3 post-project): Final business plan validated (KPI: availability of pricing model and service formats). M2 (Month 6 post-project): First 2 early adopters engaged (KPI: signed agreements/MoUs).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> M3 (Year 1): Digital toolkit released and disseminated (KPI: N. downloads/accesses; N. institutions reached). M4 (Year 1): Integration into at least 1 new EU-funded project (KPI: inclusion of KER in proposal WP). M5 (Year 3): At least 10 HEIs engaged as adopters/customers (KPI: service contracts signed, Twinning visits delivered).
Costs	<p><i>Cost estimation to implement planned activities (1 year, 3 years). Provide information on the costs/investments needed to bridge the end of the project to the next steps planned and increase TRL or go to market (you may invest in a patent, in the realisation of a prototype, etc.).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Year 1 (€80,000 approx.): refinement of the KER, business plan finalisation, toolkit set-up, piloting activities, initial outreach. Year 2 (€120,000 approx.): consolidation of service delivery (more MML and Twinning activities), scaling of toolkit, strengthened dissemination and early adopters' engagement. Year 3 (€200,000 approx.): full roll-out with wider adoption, continuous updates, larger number of service contracts, and international outreach campaigns.
Revenues	<p><i>Projected revenues and eventual profits once the KER will be used (1 and 3 years after use). Consider revenues you will expect to collect by licensing, or thanks to service provision or sale of devices. They generate the cash flow that will make the use of the result sustainable over time (provide an estimation concerning the first year and what is expected after 3 years, if possible). It is recommended that you estimate the revenues according to your early adopters and potential customers and include the information in the draft exploitation plan.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Year 1 (after use): €40,000-50,000 approx.: revenues will mainly come from direct service provision to early adopters (2-3 HEIs purchasing a first package of MML workshops and Twinning exchanges), and from premium membership/access to the digital toolkit within APRE's network. A smaller share may derive from the integration of the KER as a methodology in at least one EU-funded project (e.g., WIDERA, Reforming R&I). Profits are expected to be limited, as revenues will mostly reinvest in service refinement and dissemination. Year 3 (after use): €150,000-180,000 approx.: by this stage, the KER is expected to achieve broader adoption, with at least 8-10 HEIs (including alliances) engaging through service contracts or twinning agreements. Additional revenues will come from scaled uptake of the digital toolkit, consultancy/licensing agreements with trained providers, and multiple EU/national projects embedding the service. By year 3, the KER is projected to approach financial sustainability, with revenues covering most operational costs and enabling reinvestment.
Other sources of coverage	<p><i>Resources needed to bridge the investment needed to increase TRL and ensure the result is used. Financial resources to cover costs incurred before collecting the first revenues (during the "time to market" – see costs) and their sources. Sources can be partners' own budget, other project grants, national/regional incentives, risk capital, loans, etc. Make sure to obtain them at the right timing.</i></p>

	<p>To bridge the investment needed before sufficient revenues are generated, several complementary sources of financial coverage will be mobilised:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners' own budget and in-kind resources: APRE and selected partners will allocate internal staff time and organisational support to sustain refinement and piloting of the KER in the first months after the project. Integration in new project grants (EU/national level): early inclusion of the KER in Horizon Europe (WIDERA, Reforming R&I) or Erasmus+ proposals will ensure external funding for piloting and dissemination. National and regional incentives: opportunities linked to higher education innovation, digitalisation, and capacity building will be explored to co-finance the digital toolkit and dissemination campaigns. Membership contributions: APRE's network (Italian HEIs and R&I actors) can support early adoption, with premium access models ensuring partial cost recovery during the first year. External funding instruments (if needed): in case of larger-scale investment (e.g. to digitalise and scale the toolkit faster), other mechanisms such as competitive grants, innovation funds, or small-scale risk capital could be considered.
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Exploitation roadmap for KER 2 - Coaching and support mechanism for HEIs to pursue institutional transformation in various research areas (KER2)

Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launch the consultancy service for HEIs, offering tailored coaching and mentoring for institutional transformation. Organize workshops, one-on-one sessions, and provide digital resources to early adopters (the seven HEIs in CATALISI). Finalize and disseminate the business plan for scaling the service to other HEIs across Europe. Integrate the service with the CATALISI Marketplace and policy alignment tools. Collect feedback from early adopters and refine the service model. Prepare open-access documentation and resources in line with Horizon Europe guidelines. Explore partnerships for further dissemination and uptake post-project.
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EY: Main responsible for exploitation, service delivery, and further development. CATALISI Consortium Partners: Support dissemination, provide feedback, and facilitate connections with HEIs. Early Adopter HEIs: Pilot the service, provide testimonials, and contribute to refinement. Other Stakeholders: Potential partners for scaling and policy engagement.
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service launch to early adopters (Q4 2025) Completion of business plan (within 3 months post-project) Integration with CATALISI Marketplace (within 6 months) Collection of first feedback and refinement cycle (within 6 months) KPIs: Number of HEIs engaged, user satisfaction, number of workshops delivered, uptake beyond initial adopters
Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Year 1: Costs for service delivery to early adopters, business plan development, and digital resource creation. Year 3: Costs for scaling, additional staff, and broader dissemination. Investments may include: development of digital platforms, marketing, and potential IP management (though the methodology is open access).
Revenues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Year 1: Service fees from early adopter HEIs, potential grants for further development. Year 3: Increased revenues from expanded service provision, possible licensing of advanced modules, and consulting for additional HEIs. Revenue streams: consultancy fees, workshops, digital resource subscriptions, and policy advisory services. According to your early adopters and potential customers and include the information in the draft exploitation plan.
Other sources of coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applications for additional EU project grants and national/regional incentives. Contributions from partners (e.g., staff time, facilities).

Exploitation roadmap for KER 3 - Living Lab Methodology for Institutional Transformation: A Practical Guide to Becoming a Living Lab (KER3)

Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refinement of the methodology: consolidate the guide, training modules, and evaluation framework into a coherent service package (Living Lab for Institutional Transformation Toolkit). Finalisation of the business plan, including options for training/webinars, consultancy, and membership-based access to materials. Definition of IP strategy (open guide vs. premium training services, ENoLL brand licensing). Preparation of an online resource hub with templates, tools, and best practices for HEIs. Engagement of early adopters through ENoLL and CATALISI partner networks. Case collection from pilot HEIs to showcase impact and inspire uptake. Integration of the KER into new EU/national project proposals (e.g. Erasmus+, WIDERA, Reforming R&I). Communication & dissemination actions, including publication of the methodology guide and dedicated webinars.
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENoLL: main responsible for exploitation, IP management, business model development, training delivery, and outreach. HEI partners (CATALISI implementers): act as reference cases, contribute testimonials, and host peer-learning sessions. Other partners: support integration into proposals, dissemination through EU networks, and regional outreach.
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> M1 (Month 3 post-project): Business plan finalised (KPI: pricing model and service formats defined). M2 (Month 6 post-project): 2 early adopters engaged (KPI: signed agreements/MoUs). M3 (Year 1): Publication of toolkit and guide (KPI: downloads/accesses, HEIs reached). M4 (Year 1): Integration into 1 EU-funded project (KPI: methodology embedded in proposal WP). M5 (Year 3): 12 HEIs engaged as adopters/customers (KPI: service contracts signed, trainings delivered)
Costs	<p>Year 1 (): refinement of KER, business plan, toolkit setup, pilots, initial outreach.</p> <p>Year 2 (): consolidation of training offers, expanded dissemination, wider adopter engagement.</p> <p>Year 3 (): full roll-out, continuous updates, broader service contracts, and global outreach</p>
Revenues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Year 1 (): revenues from early adopters (2–3 HEIs purchasing training/webinars and consultancy), plus partial funding via inclusion in EU projects. Limited profits, reinvested in refinement. Year 3 (): revenues from 10–12 HEIs (training contracts, consultancy, peer-learning sessions) and expanded integration into EU/national projects. Approaching financial sustainability, with reinvestment in service improvement
Other sources of coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners' own budget and in-kind support for refinement and piloting (ENoLL, HEIs). Inclusion in new project grants (Horizon Europe, Erasmus+, national programmes).

- National/regional innovation incentives for HEIs adopting Living Labs.
- Membership contributions (ENoLL network, premium access).

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